

Deliverable 3.3

Final Consolidated Summary Report of Desk Activities in the Target Regions

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ABOUT COME RES

COME RES - Community Energy for the uptake of renewables in the electricity sector. Connecting long-term visions with short-term actions aims at facilitating the market uptake of renewable energy sources (RES) in the electricity sector. Specifically, the project focuses on advancing renewable energy communities (RECs) as per the EU's recast Renewable Energy Directive (RED II). COME RES takes a multi- and transdisciplinary approach to support the development of RECs in nine European countries; Belgium, Germany, Italy, Latvia, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, and Spain.

ISSUES ADDRESSED AND MAJOR STEPS

COME RES covers diverse socio-technical systems including community PV, wind (onshore), storage and integrated community solutions, investigated in nine European countries. The project has a specific focus on a number of target regions in these countries, where community energy has the potential to be further developed and model regions where community energy is in a more advanced stage of development. COME RES analyses political, administrative, legal, socioeconomic, spatial and environmental characteristics, and the reasons for the slow deployment of RECs in selected target regions. COME RES synchronises project activities with the transposition and implementation of the Clean Energy Package and its provisions for RECs in policy labs. Policy lessons with validity across Europe will be drawn and recommendations proposed.

ABSTRACT

One of the objectives of COME RES is to initiate, engage and feedback with major stakeholders and market actors. In all participating countries, these have been actively involved in regular solution-oriented stakeholder dialogues to co-create solutions to overcome existing barriers for the growth of community energy and setting up an enabling framework. Throughout the project lifetime, the country desks ensured wide engagement of market actors and stakeholders and created new or reinforced existing networks. Dialogues with major stakeholders in thematic workshops, policy labs and dedicated stakeholder consultations helped to address critical barriers and drivers for RECs in each target region, to identify and select good/best practices and to derive policy recommendations. The stakeholders involved in the desks accompanied all work phases and tasks, provided advice, and supported the dissemination of the results. Although there are stakeholder groups that are present in each country, there are some stakeholder groups that are more influential in one country than in another or that are specific to a country (e.g. ethnic minorities). Moreover, the activities of the country desks varied from country to country according to the regional needs while being inspired by the same specific objectives.

The engagement of local stakeholders in the so-called target regions represented a valuable resource especially when identifying and discussing major hurdles and the possibilities to co-create solutions in order to overcome existing barriers. They acknowledged the benefits for growth of community energy in their regions by learning from the experience of other COME RES countries and by discussing the chance of implementing best-practices initiated elsewhere.

The final consolidated report of the country desk activities comprises the activities performed within the framework of Work Package 3 “*Country Desks and stakeholder dialogues*” and summarises and documents all events and accomplishments of the eight COME RES country desks between September 2020 and December 2022.

The report is composed by four main sections and is structured as follows:

- A brief introduction, with the background and purpose of the report.
- An overview of the activities undertaken by all the country desks, providing an aggregated review of the major activities and respective outputs. The desks have been successful in engaging a wide set of stakeholders and market actors, covering all the major stakeholder groups identified in D3.1. The current progress is compliant with the project’s expected outputs, fully aligned with the description of the Grant Agreement.
- A more detailed description of the activities held by each of the country desks, with the identification of the main topics, participants and outputs. The breakdown of the participants per stakeholder group is also available for the different events, showing the diversity of stakeholders participating in the different activities.
- A final section with the main conclusions of the report and reflections on future steps.

Overall, the report shows the compliance with the KPIs, both in terms of the number of events organised as well as in terms of stakeholders’ engagement. Some KPIs have even been outperformed. Moreover, the report also highlights the relevance of the desk activities in the respective country/regional context,

and how they gave impetus to both other project activities and the national and regional policy formulations in fostering enabling frameworks for renewable energy communities.

At the end of the project, there are positive signals that the infrastructure, set up with the establishment of the country desks, could continue after the end of the project and that ways for further cooperations could be found. The core stakeholders in almost all country desks pledged that they would seize all the opportunities to ensure the continuation of the networks. Actions plans have been sketched for Italy, Latvia, Spain and Portugal. These activities received the input and endorsement from key players and market actors of the target regions. The signature of three Memoranda of Understanding between the Canary Island and Comptem (see the Spanish section) and between Magliano Alpi (Italy) and Latvian major stakeholders (see the Latvian and Italian sessions) as well as Thuringian main stakeholders and Dutch initiators of two large energy gardens (see the German Section) demonstrate the sustainability of the actions beyond lifetime of COME RES.

CONTENTS

ABOUT COME RES	3
ISSUES ADDRESSED AND MAJOR STEPS	3
ABSTRACT	4
1. INTRODUCTION.....	10
1.1. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE OF THE REPORT	10
1.2. NATIONAL COUNTRY DESKS AND TARGET REGIONS	11
1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT	12
2. OVERVIEW OF DESK ACTIVITIES	13
2.1. SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES HELD BY THE DESKS	13
2.2. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	14
2.3. TOPICS DISCUSSED.....	17
2.4. COUNTRY DESK ONLINE PAGES	18
2.5. PRIVACY AND ETHICS.....	20
3. DESK ACTIVITIES IN COME RES COUNTRIES	21
3.1. BELGIUM – NETHERLANDS.....	21
3.1.1. COUNTRY DEKS ACTIVITIES.....	22
3.1.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	34
3.1.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	35
3.2. GERMANY	37
3.2.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	38
3.2.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	53
3.2.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	55
3.3. ITALY.....	57
3.3.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	57
3.3.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	68
3.3.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	70
3.4. LATVIA	71
3.4.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	72
3.4.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	83
3.4.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	86
3.5. NORWAY	88
3.5.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	89
3.5.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	95
3.5.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	96
3.6. POLAND.....	98
3.6.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	98
3.6.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	106

3.6.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	108
3.7. PORTUGAL.....	109
3.7.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	109
3.7.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	116
3.7.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	118
3.8. SPAIN.....	119
3.8.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	119
3.8.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES.....	129
3.8.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED	130
4. CONCLUSIONS AND POSSIBILITIES TO MAINTAIN THE DESK INFRASTRUCTURE	132

FIGURES

Figure 1 - Examples of country desk websites	11
Figure 2 – Breakdown of the Participants (average) in the events organised by the country desks per stakeholder group	16
Figure 3 - Breakdown of participants in the kick-off meeting per stakeholder group	22
Figure 4 - Miro boards of barriers and drivers from the first group (Flanders)	23
Figure 5 - Miro boards of barriers and drivers from the second group (Flanders).....	24
Figure 6 - Miro boards of barriers and drivers from the third group (the Netherlands)	24
Figure 7 - Breakdown of participants in the first thematic workshop and policy lab per stakeholder group	25
Figure 8 - Miro boards from group 1 policy lab	26
Figure 9 - Miro boards from group 2 policy lab	26
Figure 10 - Breakdown of participants in the first follow-up meeting of the country desk and policy lab per stakeholder group.....	28
Figure 11 – Padlet break-out room 1 (Province of North Brabant) first follow-up meeting and policy lab.....	29
Figure 12 - Breakdown of participants in the second follow-up meeting of the country desk and policy lab per stakeholder group.....	31
Figure 13 - Breakdown of participants in the second thematic workshop per stakeholder group	33
Figure 14 - Breakdown of participants per stakeholder group in the KOM of the German Desk	39
Figure 15 – Interactive section: Analysis of the present barriers and future options	40
Figure 16 - Breakdown of participants per stakeholder group in the first Thematic Workshop	42
Figure 17 - Participant engagement in the First Thematic Workshop	44
Figure 18 - Breakdown of participants per stakeholder group in the Status Meeting	44
Figure 19 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group	47
Figure 20 - Breakdown of participants in the second status meeting of the German country desk per stakeholder group	49

Figure 21 – Results of a Slido poll among desk participants on the most important barriers for energy communities..... 50

Figure 22 – Results of a Slido poll among desk participants on the most important barriers for energy sharing..... 51

Figure 23 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick-off meeting of the Italian Desk per stakeholder group 58

Figure 24 - Breakdown of participants in the Thematic Workshop of the Italian Desk per stakeholder group 59

Figure 25 – Result from the interactive session held during the Thematic Workshop of the Italian Desk..... 60

Figure 26 - Breakdown of participants in the first country desk meeting and Policy Lab per stakeholder group 62

Figure 27 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop per stakeholder group 65

Figure 28 - Breakdown of participants in the second Country Desk Meeting per stakeholder group 66

Figure 29 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick off meeting of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group 73

Figure 30 - Breakdown of participants in the first thematic workshop and policy lab of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group..... 75

Figure 31 – Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group 76

Figure 32 - Breakdown of participants in the first follow-up meeting of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group 79

Figure 33 - Breakdown of participants in the second follow-up meeting of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group 80

Figure 34 - Image of the second follow-up meeting. Copyright: A. Zučika..... 83

Figure 35 - Breakdown of participants in the kick-off meeting of the Norwegian Desk per stakeholder group 89

Figure 36 - Breakdown of participants in the Thematic Workshop of the Norwegian Desk per stakeholder group 90

Figure 37 - Breakdown of participants in the first Country Desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group 91

Figure 38 - Breakdown of participants in the second thematic workshop and policy lab per stakeholder group 92

Figure 39 – Image of the hybrid meeting on 21.09.22. Copyright: Erik Tollefsen 93

Figure 40 - Breakdown of participants in the second Country Desk follow-up meeting per stakeholder group 94

Figure 41 - Examples of the Norwegian newsletter..... 96

Figure 42 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick-off Meeting of the Polish Desk per stakeholder group 99

Figure 43 – Breakdown n of participants in the first Country Desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group 103

Figure 44 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group 104

Figure 45 – Breakdown of participants in the second Country Desk Follow-up meeting and Policy Lab per stakeholder group..... 105

Figure 46 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick-off meeting of the Portuguese Desk per stakeholder group 110

Figure 47 - Breakdown of participants in the Thematic Workshop of the Portuguese Desk per stakeholder group 111

Figure 48 – Breakdown of participants in the first Portuguese country desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group..... 112

Figure 49 - Breakdown of participants in the second Portuguese country desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group..... 113

Figure 50 – Output of the brainstorming sessions dedicated to the development of a draft version of the Action Plan 114

Figure 51 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop of the Portuguese Desk per stakeholder group 115

Figure 52 – Breakdown of participants in the kick-off meeting per stakeholder group..... 120

Figure 53 – Breakdown of participants in the first Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group 121

Figure 54 – Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group 124

Figure 55 – Breakdown of participants in the first Spanish country desk follow-up meeting per stakeholder group..... 127

Figure 56 - Breakdown of participants in the second Spanish country desk follow-up meeting per stakeholder group..... 128

TABLES

Table 1 - COME RES Desks, corresponding leaders and target and model regions 12

Table 2 - Summary of stakeholder engagement in the COME RES desk activities 14

Table 3 – Overview of country desk online pages and the resources available for COME RES countries..... 18

Table 4 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Belgian/Dutch Country Desk 21

Table 5 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the German Desk during months 4-27 ... 37

Table 6 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Italian Country Desk 57

Table 7 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Latvian Country Desk 71

Table 8 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Norwegian Country Desk..... 88

Table 9 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Polish Country Desk..... 98

Table 10 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Portuguese Country Desk..... 109

Table 11 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Spanish Country Desk..... 119

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE OF THE REPORT

This report is part of the COME RES Work Package (WP) 3 “*Country Desks and stakeholder dialogues*”. This WP aims at the establishment and maintenance of eight stakeholder desks, and at the organisation of a wide set of activities at the country and/or regional level. The desks are an important vehicle to ensure wide engagement of market actors and stakeholders throughout the project duration and to create networks that can continue after the end of the project. The WP comprises the organisation of dialogues with major stakeholders and thematic workshops, policy labs and dedicated stakeholder consultations, feeding outcomes into other WPs of the project. The activities with the stakeholders addressed critical barriers and drivers for renewable energy communities (RECs) in each target region (feedback loops with WP2), identified and disseminated good/best practices (feedback loops with WP4 and WP5) discussed transfer activities (feedback loops with WP6), discussed steps for four action plans (Task 3.5) and derived policy recommendations (feedback loops with WP7). Moreover, this WP also tried to synchronise its desk activities with the transposition of RED II and the respective implementation of enabling frameworks for RECs in the various COME RES countries. This implied an adaptation of the activities organised by the different desks to the local context, both in terms of timing, topics covered as well as the groups of stakeholders involved.

According to the Grant Agreement, each desk must organise and implement at least the following activities:

- **Three regular country desk meetings**, including the kick-off meeting and two follow up meetings;
- **Two thematic workshops**, which aim to provide non-biased information to stakeholders and market actors, critically assess good/best practice community energy solutions, identify options to improve legal and policy frameworks in the target regions, and assess best practice transfer opportunities/restrictions;
- **Two policy labs**¹, serving as an interface between the COME RES project and actual policy formulation and implementation processes in the COME RES countries and facilitating a policy dialogue with policy makers.

The desks were also expected to **document** the performed activities **and make them visible on the COME RES website**. A dedicated section on the website illustrates the activities and output of the stakeholders desks. Each country had a dedicated country desk website. A great number of country desks published summary reports with the workshops’ results in both original language and in English, as well as announcements, events and other relevant documents produced in the country desk webpage.

¹ Policy labs are designed as policy roundtables addressing actual and relevant legal and policy developments related to the transposition and implementation of RED II (e.g., the assessment of potential and barriers for RECs, enabling frameworks for RECs, consideration of RECs in support schemes). They should also inform policy makers about (interim) project findings and policy developments in the other COME RES partner countries.

The German Stakeholder Desk

The German desk concentrates on community energy and community integrated solutions. It involves a core group of experts, 40 stakeholders and a wider group of roughly 90 stakeholders for operational reports, regular desk meetings and working addressing the core group, whereas the 'Stakeholder Desk and Policy Roundtable' are open to a larger group of stakeholders. The stakeholders come mainly from target regions (Thuringe and Baden-Wuerttemberg) but also from other German federal states (e.g. North-Rhine Westphalia) and organisations at the national level.

The name Renewable Energy Community has not yet been officially defined in German law. However, there are community-based organisations and initiatives active operating fully the corresponding criteria (see Renewable Energy Directive (RED) country being implemented). As of the end of 2020, the number of energy communities in Germany reached 85, involving 250,000 members and investments in RED installations of 1.8 billion EUR. Roughly one quarter of all energy communities are engaged with the generation of electricity from solar energy, while most (80%) that with electricity production from PV. Between 2008 and 2020, the total number of energy communities rose an increase from 26 to 79. Since 2017 however, the annual increase has continuously declined. In 2020, only 14 new energy communities were founded (RED/2018).

The desk is designed as an informal forum to discuss current topics related to the development of RED. It seeks to accompany and inform the transmission and implementation of the latest Renewable Energy and the Integrated Electricity Market Directives and their provisions for energy communities. For this purpose, the desk organises thematic, technical and policy workshops, public decision makers. It provides input to the analysis of activities, barriers, good practices and lessons learned and supports implementation. The stakeholders involved can provide feedback on project results (e.g. on the action plan for the target region, Thuringe) and help to test and validate approaches and support their development.

Figure 1 - Examples of country desk websites

Moreover, WP3 launched **targeted stakeholder consultations**, which were conducted in all the COME RES countries with the support of the country desks. Finally, **action plans** for four target regions (Apulia, Italy; Latvia; Norte Region, Portugal; Canary Islands, Spain) were elaborated in close collaboration with a core group of desk members.

This deliverable provides the consolidated report for all desk activities whose **main purpose is to summarise and document stakeholder engagement in the eight country desks** throughout the project's lifetime. These activities include the regular country desk meetings, thematic workshops and policy labs, as well as other relevant activities performed by the desks (e.g., communication and dissemination activities). This report collects all desk activities implemented during the project's lifetime – between September 2020 and December 2022. It builds upon Deliverable D3.1 “*Stakeholder involvement and engagement plans*” and updates Deliverable D3.2 “*First Consolidated Report of Desk Activities in the Target Regions*” with new contributions of the consortium partners responsible for the different country desks.

1.2. NATIONAL COUNTRY DESKS AND TARGET REGIONS

Eight country desks, representing nine European countries², were established as part of the project, following the methodological framework defined within Task 3.1. By the end of January 2021, all the desks had been officially launched with a kick-off meeting, where a core group of stakeholders was invited to participate.

The eight country desks, the national consortium partners and the target and model regions are presented in Table 1. Hereafter, this report will refer to these national stakeholder desks when referring to the COME RES desks.

² Stakeholders from Belgium and The Netherlands cooperated in a cross-border desk.

Table 1 - COME RES Desks, corresponding leaders and target and model regions

Country	Desk Leaders	Target Region(s)	Model Region(s)
Belgium/ Netherlands	VITO, REScoop.eu, TU/e	Province of Limburg Province of West-Flanders	Provinces Antwerp and East-Flanders, Flemish Brabant (Leuven)
		Utrecht, North Brabant	Zeeland, Rijsenhout, Etten-Leur, Woerden
Germany	FUB-FFU	Thuringia	Schleswig-Holstein
Italy	ENEA, Ecoazioni	Apulia	Piedmont
Latvia	LEIF/FEI	Whole country	Municipality of Marupe
Norway	CICERO	Whole country	Islands and farming communities
Poland	KAPE	Mazovia Province, Lesser Poland Province	Lower Silesia, Pomerania, Virtual Green Power Plant Ochotnica
Portugal	INEGI	Norte Region	Municipality of Lisbon
Spain	ECORYS, ACER	Balearic and Canary Islands	Cataluña, C. Valenciana

1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

This report is composed by four main sections. This **first section** provides a brief introduction with the background and purpose of the report and the identification of the eight country desks, which will be referred throughout the document. **Section 2** is dedicated to the overview of the desk activities from all the country desks, providing an overall perspective of what has been accomplished in terms of activities organised, stakeholders' involvement, main topics discussed and obtained results, and an overview of the online presence of the desks. **Section 3** provides a more detailed description of the activities organised by the country desks, with a subsection dedicated to each desk. Finally, **section 4** comprises the main conclusions deriving from the assessment of the activities performed by the country desks and respective results.

2. OVERVIEW OF DESK ACTIVITIES

2.1. SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES HELD BY THE DESKS

The eight country desks held several events during the COME RES project lifetime, including regular desk meetings, thematic workshops and policy labs. Table 2 presents a summary of all events organised by each of the desks. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, most of these meetings were held online, ensuring the compliance with the sanitary restrictions established in the different countries.

All desks held a **kick-off meeting**, marking the establishment of the national desks. These meetings, taking place in December 2020 and January 2021, focused mostly on the presentation of the project to the invited core stakeholders, including its objectives and expected results, as well as the desks' objectives and modes of operation. Preliminary discussions on the status quo of RECs in the different countries and the main barriers and drivers for their implementation were also conducted.

Moreover, as envisaged by the Grant Agreement, all desks held two **thematic workshops**, fostering a dialogue between the different groups of stakeholders. Even though the workshops' topics were defined according to the desks' specific contexts, there was a clear focus on the current regulatory and legal framework for community energy initiatives and on the main barriers and drivers for RECs implementation. The Spanish desk organised one thematic workshop in each of the insular target regions.

All desks combined the thematic workshops with **policy labs**, in the form of policy roundtables, gathering policy makers and other stakeholders to discuss the transposition processes in the different countries (and target regions). These events proved to be key for the accomplishment of the project's objective of accompanying (and contributing to) the establishment of a favourable framework for the implementation of RECs, in line with the provisions of RED II. The Belgian/Dutch, German, Latvian and Spanish country desks held one additional policy lab, aiding an even stronger exchange between policy makers, public authorities and stakeholders.

Apart from the thematic workshops and policy labs, all desks updated on a regular basis the key stakeholders about the project's development either through mails or in **country desk meetings** (sometimes called status meetings). As envisaged in the Grant Agreement, all desks held two of these country desk meetings that involved a larger number of stakeholders.

Furthermore, the country desks have also been involved in other activities, including the regular interaction with relevant national and regional stakeholders, who may or may not be part of the country desks, ensuring the continuous interaction with different stakeholder groups. Desks have also been liaising with other related projects and initiatives at national and European level, which has been accomplished through the participation in events organised by those initiatives.

Finally, the desks have also contributed to make the project results visible in the respective countries and regions, e.g. through the presentation of project's results in different national and regional events, additionally to the events organised within the scope of the desks. Furthermore, amongst the additional activities should also be mentioned the feeding of the national desk webpages with several resources

including articles in technical journals and the regional press in the respective language of the desks as well as the translation of the project communication materials into the respective national language.

2.2. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

As envisaged in the Deliverable D3.1 “Stakeholder engagement plans”, the country desks have been involving a diverse set of stakeholders in their activities, covering the different relevant groups identified in D3.1. A summary of the stakeholder engagement in the activities organised by the desks in the scope of the COME RES activities is presented in Table 2 and the respective breakdown per stakeholder group is to be found in Figure 2.

Concerning the **number of active participants**, the country desks’ regular meetings had a participation rate which ranges from 5 to 191 participants. The highest majority of meetings fully complied with the minimum of 15 participants per country as defined in the Grant Agreement. Overall, the desks have been successfully engaging a large number of relevant stakeholders to participate in their activities. Because of the novelty of the energy community issue in Poland and the still lacking definition of RECs in the national legislation, it was more difficult to gain momentum. For this reason, it was decided to keep the number of participants limited in the Polish country desk meetings and some other country desk events. Hence participation reached less than 15 – in order to enable a more focused discussion on specific topics. This exception is also justified by the high specificity of the workshop, which focused on the technical and economic viability of PV installations as part of energy community initiatives. The other exceptions refer to the second country desk meetings of Italy and of Portugal. In both cases, the number of stakeholders was kept low in order to ensure higher engagement and participation from the attendees in the discussion of the action plans. In general, the workshops’ level of participation in the desk activities largely exceeded the proposed KPI of at least 20 stakeholders per country, having reached 52 participants on average.

The activities organised by the desks have also been characterised by a relatively **balanced participation of male and female attendees**, with an average share of 37% female participants and a minimum of 22% of female participants in single meeting (except for one event in Portugal with only 5 participants of which all were male). This ratio is not entirely satisfactory, yet should be adequate to promote the incorporation of gender issues in the project results, by providing a gendered perspective on the topics discussed in the several activities organised by the desks.

Table 2 - Summary of stakeholder engagement in the COME RES desk activities

Country	Meetings	Date	Total Participants	Policy Makers*
Belgium/ Netherlands	Kick-off Meeting	19.01.2021	41	2
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	25.05.2021	35	3
	First Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	30.11.2021	36	9

	Second Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	18.10.2022	21	1
	Second Thematic Workshop	18.10.2022	21	1
Germany	Kick-off Meeting	11.12.2020	37	3
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	30.03.2021	70	8
	First Country Desk Status Meeting	21.09.2021	54	5
	Second Thematic Workshop and second Policy Lab	31.03.2022	63	6
	Second Country Desk Status Meeting and third Policy Lab	23.11.2022	45	5
Italy	Kick-off Meeting	21.01.2021	89	6
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	06.05.2021	180	11
	First Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	28.04.2022	165	6
	Second Thematic Workshop	30.11.2022	191	12
	Second Country Desk Meeting	01.12.2022	14	4
Latvia	Kick-off Meeting	27.01.2021	19	3
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	17.06.2021	33	7
	Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	16.02.2022	37	5
	First Country Desk Meeting	06.10.2022	28	4
	Second Country Desk Meeting	24.11.2022	23	3
Norway	Kick-off Meeting	14.01.21	30	-
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	02.06.21	80	7
	First Country Desk Meeting	26.01.22	32	-
	Second Thematic Workshop	21.09.22	44	-
	Second Country Desk Meeting	16.11.22	15	-
Poland	Kick-off Meeting	27.01.2021	85	6
	First Thematic Workshop	28.10.2021	13	-
	First Country Desk Meeting	25.05.2022	12	1
	Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	10.11.2022	8	-
	Second Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	02.12.2022	14	1

Portugal	Kick-off Meeting	29.01.2021	35	4
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	22.06.2021	132	4
	First Country Desk Meeting	15.02.2022	29	4
	Second Country Desk Meeting	17.11.2022	5	-
	Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	22.11.2022	95	15
Spain	Kick-off Meeting	26.01.2021	37	10
	First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	25.05.2021	75	17
	Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	30.06.2021	51	19
	First Country Desk Meeting	08.03.2022	55	5
	Second Country Desk Meeting	10.11.2022	21	3

* Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials

Regarding the breakdown of participants in the events organised by the eight desks per stakeholder group, Figure 2 illustrates the diversity of stakeholders engaged in activities of all the desks. Even though not all stakeholder groups were represented in all the activities, the groups involved ensured a diversity of perspectives and interests on the implementation of renewable energy community initiatives.

All desks have successfully engaged policy makers and other public authorities to actively participate in their activities, ensuring the involvement of politicians, administrations and policy advisory organisations in country desks. A good level of participation of community energy initiatives and cooperatives, as well as associations and groups of interest, has also been accomplished. Financing institutions and mass media seem to be the groups least engaged in the desks' activities.

Figure 2 – Breakdown of the Participants (average) in the events organised by the country desks per stakeholder group

Concerning the policy labs, as shown in Table 2, nearly all desks have been able to involve at least 2 policy makers, as envisaged in the project KPIs. Only the Norwegian and Polish desk did not manage to involve a policy maker in some of the country desk events due to insufficient interest at political level for the REC issue.

2.3. TOPICS DISCUSSED

As referred in section 2.1, the topics discussed in the activities held by the country desks were defined on the basis of local context specificities as well as on the national progress in the RED II transposition process. A more detailed summary of the topics discussed in the different activities and main conclusions is presented in section 3. This section highlights the main topics discussed and the potential feedback loops with the remaining activities of the COME RES project, including specific contributions to the project expected outputs.

The characterisation of the **status quo of RECs** in the COME RES countries was one of the main topics discussed within the desks' meetings. All desks used their events to both gather and disseminate information on the current implementation of energy community initiatives at national and regional level. Obtained outcomes were relevant for the conception of the Deliverable D2.1, and for the estimation of the potential for RECs in the COME RES target regions (Deliverable D2.2). On the other hand, preliminary project outputs associated with these deliverables were also presented to different stakeholders in some of the desk activities.

Moreover, all desks dedicated part of their activities' agendas to the discussion of the **transposition of RED II** in the different countries, providing an assessment of the current legal and regulatory framework applicable to RECs. These discussions allowed project partners to accompany recent developments in the provisions applicable to energy community initiatives and gather the perspective of the different stakeholders on the ongoing transposition process. Within the policy roundtables, the project could also provide inputs to the transposition process, by bringing policy makers to the discussion. This was particularly successful in Latvia and in Spain.

As part of the discussion on the transposition process, the country desks dedicated special attention to the development of an adequate **enabling framework for RECs**, as most of the countries still are considerably behind schedule on this issue. Here, the contributions from the activities were two-fold. On the one hand, they were useful to collect suggestions from several stakeholders on how to build an adequate enabling framework which could create a level playing field for the establishment of RECs. On the other hand, these activities were relevant to provide advice to policy makers responsible for the development of the RECs enabling framework and to understand the future steps in each of the target regions.

Barriers and drivers for the implementation of RECs was also one of the topics thoroughly addressed in the desk events. Along with the discussion on the legal, regulatory and policy framework applicable to RECs in the COME RES countries, stakeholders participating in the different activities provided their perspective on the current barriers and drivers for enhancing community energy initiatives. Stakeholders identified technical, financial and legal barriers which hamper the development of these initiatives. The

lack of information/low level of awareness on the REC concept was identified as an additional relevant barrier to be overcome.

Other topics, such as the identification of good and best-practices and the most suitable business models, were discussed in dedicated sessions of the desks, e.g. in the thematic workshops, but also in the policy labs. The outcome of this dialogue and feedback from stakeholders proved very important for the activities being performed as part of work packages 4, 5, 6 and 7 of the project.

2.4. COUNTRY DESK ONLINE PAGES

Besides the organisation of the events, the country desks have also contributed to make the project outputs visible at the national and regional level through the participation in national events and by feeding the project online page, and the dedicated national desks online pages.

The national desk websites correspond to nine online pages (one for each of the COME RES countries) and are available in English and in the national language. These pages contain resources and information specific to the different countries, including information on the desks planned events and on their respective outputs (Table 3). All national pages include the summary of the regular desk meetings and thematic workshops, mostly in English and also the respective language.

The project partners leading the country desks have also supported ICLEI with the translation of different communication and dissemination materials, including the project flyer and poster, policy briefs, and factsheets. Moreover, desk leaders have also aided in the collection of material to include in the periodic newsletters.

Table 3– Overview of country desk online pages and the resources available for COME RES countries

Desk	Language	Available Resources	Link to Desk Online Page
Belgium	Dutch / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Summary report of kick-off meeting; Presentations and summary report of the first Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Assessment report of potentials for RES community energy in Limburg en West-Vlaanderen; Summary report of the first and second country desk meeting	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/belgium
Germany	German / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Summary report of kick-off meeting; Summary report of the first and second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Summary report of the status meeting; Summary Report of the second status meeting; Two publications in <i>Energiewirtschaftliche Tagesfragen</i>	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/germany

Italy	Italian / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Agenda, presentations, session recording and summary report of kick-off meeting; Summary report of the first and second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/italy
Latvia	Latvian / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Summary report of kick-off meeting; Summary report of the first and second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Summary report of the first and second Country Desk Meeting	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/latvia
Netherlands	Dutch / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Summary report of kick-off meeting; Presentations and summary report of the first Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Assessment report of potentials for RES community energy in Noord-Brabant; Summary report of the first and second country desk meeting	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/the-netherlands
Norway	Norwegian / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Summary report of kick-off meeting; Summary report of the first and second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Summary report of the first and second country desk meeting	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/norway
Poland	Polish / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Agenda and summary report of kick-off meeting; Summary report of the first Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/poland
Portugal	Portuguese / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Project summary and objectives of the national desk; Agenda, presentations and summary report of kick-off meeting; Agenda, session recording and summary report of the first Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Agenda and summary of the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/portugal

Spain	Spanish / English	COME RES policy briefs, factsheets, flyer and poster; Agenda and summary report of kick-off meeting; Agenda and summary report of the first and second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab; Summary report of the second country desk meeting	https://come-res.eu/stakeholder-desks/spain
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2.5. PRIVACY AND ETHICS

Comprehensive steps have been taken throughout all the events and activities mentioned in this report to ensure due consideration of privacy and ethical issues. In particular, the consortium has given careful consideration to the provisions set out in the Deliverable 1.4. This deliverable contains guidelines and actions to be followed by the consortium when dealing with stakeholders, participants and other relevant members of the public engaged with the COME RES project. The deliverable provides templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets as well as information on the procedures to be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction, guaranteeing the compliance with national and EU legislation.

Before each event and activity, individuals were informed about the intentions of the relevant partners to take photographs and gather the information shared during the events. Participants were informed about the option to refuse should they not wish to be photographed, and any of these requests was fulfilled.

Furthermore, no specific data about the individual attendees of the events are going to be published in this public report. As a rule, only the name of the organisations the individual represents has been mentioned and aggregated data (such as share of male/female attendees). However, all organisations were informed about the fact that their presence in events and activities would be disclosed, and they were given the opportunity to request not to be included in any project publications. Additionally, the only names which have been included in the report and other public material are the names of persons who were officially involved as, e.g., invited speakers, moderators or panellists. or those who gave explicit permission for their names to be published because they acted as speakers, moderators or special guests, or due to having any other special function at an event or activity.

Concluding, due consideration has been given to ensure informed consent of attendees and participants to be photographed and mentioned in any subsequent description of the event.

3. DESK ACTIVITIES IN COME RES COUNTRIES

Section 3 provides a detailed description of the activities performed in the different COME RES countries and outlines the respective outcomes and lessons learned. Each section comprises one of the eight country desks: 3.1. Belgium – Netherlands; 3.2. Germany; 3.3. Italy; 3.4. Latvia; 3.5. Norway; 3.6. Poland; 3.7. Portugal; and 3.8. Spain.

3.1. BELGIUM – NETHERLANDS

The Belgium/Dutch country desk was coordinated by the Technical University of Eindhoven, in collaboration with VITO/EnergyVille and supported by REScoop.eu. The country desk brought together important stakeholders from the national, regional and local level in Flanders (Belgium) as well as the Netherlands.

Table 4 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Belgian/Dutch Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Makers
Kick-off meeting	19.01.2021	Online	Identify region-specific drivers and barriers for RECS	41	11
First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	25.05.2021	Online	Discuss interactions between local policies and RECS	35	11
First Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	30.11.2021	Online	Present the current status of the transposition and illustrate how the COME RES project contributes to practical implementation of these provisions in Flanders and the Netherlands. Discuss the priorities of the enabling framework for RECs in the Netherlands and Flanders.	36	9
Second Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	18.10.2022	Online	Present and discuss the comparative analysis of the regulatory and enabling framework for RECs in the 9 COME RES countries and the results of the stakeholder survey on RECs.	21	1

Second Thematic Workshop	18.10.2022	Online	Presentation of the Energy Community Platform	21	1
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* Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials

3.1.1. COUNTRY DEKS ACTIVITIES

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off Meeting of the Belgian/Dutch Desk

The first meeting of the joint Belgian/Dutch country desk took place online on 19 January 2021. The meeting was designed to bring together key stakeholders to identify opportunities and barriers for RECs in the selected COME RES target regions Limburg and West Flanders in Flanders and North Brabant in the Netherlands.

The meeting was attended by 41 stakeholders representing ministries, energy agencies, renewable energy associations, innovation agencies, energy cooperatives and their associations, municipal organizations, financing institutions, SMEs, environmental NGOs, and research organizations. Figure 3 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. Stakeholders from the transnational, national, provincial, and local levels were represented. Approximately 43% of the participants were female.

The event began with a presentation of the COME RES project by Erik Laes (TU/e) and Erika Meynaerts (VITO), including the main objectives of the desk. This was followed by presentations on the current and future policy frameworks for energy communities in Flanders (VITO) and the Netherlands (Ministry of Economic Affairs). The last part of the meeting consisted of breakout sessions to identify barriers and drivers for energy communities in the target regions and suggest important components of an enabling framework.

Figure 3 - Breakdown of participants in the kick-off meeting per stakeholder group

The main points raised by Flemish participants were:

- Policy makers should utilise the full potential for energy communities e.g., installation of PV on large roofs of companies, schools, public buildings, etc. Maps of potential solar and wind installations could help to visualise this.
- Accessibility of the energy market should be guaranteed for all actors, not just the large/commercial players. This has historically been a problem for wind energy in the region and should be proactively anticipated with regard to other renewable energy sources.
- There is a lack of knowledge and information about energy communities (added value, role of different actors). The regulatory and enabling framework must be transparent and unambiguous to promote energy communities and engage citizens.

The main points raised by Dutch participants were:

- Congestion problems in the distribution grid are an opportunity for energy communities (especially for integrated solutions with energy storage) that can offer flexibility to the grid.
- There is a lack of knowledge and information about energy communities. Participation in energy communities is limited to "front runners" or "early adopters". The regional energy strategies offer a "window of opportunity" for citizen participation.
- Start-up and management of energy communities is, to a large extent, based on volunteers. There is need for professionalisation and support to reach the ambitious targets.

Figure 4 - Miro boards of barriers and drivers from the first group (Flanders)

Barrières en drijfveren voor hernieuwbare energiegemeenschappen
 Vlaanderen groep 2- gemedereerd door Dirk Vansintjan

Barrières en drijfveren voor hernieuwbare energiegemeenschappen
 Vlaanderen groep 2- gemedereerd door Dirk Vansintjan

Figure 5 - Miro boards of barriers and drivers from the second group (Flanders)

Nederland groep 3 - gemedereerd door Erik Laas

Barrières en drijfveren voor hernieuwbare energiegemeenschappen
 Nederland groep 3 - gemedereerd door Erik Laas

Figure 6 - Miro boards of barriers and drivers from the third group (the Netherlands)

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The first thematic workshop and policy lab was held on 25 May 2021. The aim was to explore how local policies can stimulate the start-up and further growth of energy communities and how energy communities can contribute to the realisation of local policy objectives.

The meeting was attended by 35 stakeholders including local and national governments, inter-municipal organisations, energy cooperatives, transition experts, financing institutions, grid operators, and research institutions. Figure 7 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. Stakeholders from the transnational, national, provincial, and local levels were represented. Approximately 40% of the participants were female.

Figure 7 - Breakdown of participants in the first thematic workshop and policy lab per stakeholder group

The plenary session was chaired by Erika Meynaerts (VITO/Energyville). This was followed by a workshop in which four speakers discussed the interaction between local policies and energy communities based on their own context and perspective:

- Hilde Hacour (policy officer, Province of Vlaams-Brabant) explained the "LICHT Vlaams-Brabant" and "RHEDCOOP" projects.
- Leo D'haese (director, ECOoB) illustrated how citizen participation and public-private partnerships accelerated the climate transition in Oost-Brabant.
- Martijn Messing (project manager of the Social Innovation Program, Province of Brabant) discussed how energy communities can contribute to the energy transition and gave critical guidance on the role that authorities play in the development of local energy communities.
- Rien de Bont (Masters student, TU/e) presented the different views on the stimulation of energy communities in the Dutch context of multi-level governance based on his research.

The presentations were followed by a panel discussion, moderated by Erik Laes (TU/e). The topics addressed included: accelerating the renewables transition through professionalisation, linkages between energy communities and the broader communities in which they are situated, and the transparency of national policy on energy communities.

In the policy lab, the participants were divided into two groups. In each group, four propositions were discussed with the participants, using dot voting in Miro across a spectrum of positions as a basis for the discussion:

- To what extent should local governments facilitate energy communities?
- Assume that, as a local government, you can only support one energy community. Which criterion is decisive in making your choice?
- How can local governments ensure that energy communities have the broadest possible support?

- What type of energy community should local authorities stimulate in particular?

Figure 8 - Miro boards from group 1 policy lab

Figure 9 - Miro boards from group 2 policy lab

The session was closed by Erika Meynaerts (VITO/Energyville) with a look ahead to the next activities of the country desk. Finally, participants were asked to fill in a survey to assess their satisfaction with the content and organisation of the first thematic workshop and policy lab.

The thematic workshop and policy lab yielded a number of conclusions, including:

- Both professionalisation and voluntarism are important. When it comes to embedding energy communities in their localities, volunteerism is crucial. But professionalisation is also important to manage the complexity of energy projects.
- Energy communities have to operate profitable projects themselves, but local government can facilitate the construction of profitable projects, for example through an environment fund that provides the necessary resources that have to be paid back later in the operational phase.
- There is a lack of insight and knowledge about national legislation on energy communities among local governments and citizens.
- The facilitating role of local government should not jeopardise the independence of energy communities.
- The facilitating role of local authorities is necessary to guarantee equal access to (renewable) energy markets for both private investors and energy communities.
- Strong facilitation by local government is mainly helpful in cases where there is real danger of monopoly.
- Embedding energy communities in local needs makes the energy community 'future-proof'.
- Inclusiveness is an important principle for energy communities.

ACTIVITY 3: First Follow-Up Meeting of the Country Desk and Policy Lab

The first follow-up meeting of the Dutch/Flemish country desk took place on 30 November 2021. The aim of this meeting was to present the current status of the transposition of the provisions on renewable energy communities, as stipulated in the RED II, by the EU Member States and illustrate how the COME RES project contributes to practical implementation of these provisions in Flanders and the Netherlands. Back-to-back with the country desk meeting, an interactive policy lab was organised to discuss the priorities of the enabling framework for RECs in the Netherlands and Flanders.

The meeting was attended by 36 stakeholders with representation from local and national policy makers, energy and innovation agencies/competence centres, associations and groups of interest, energy system operators, SMEs, municipal utilities companies, community energy initiatives/energy cooperatives, NGOs and network organisations, financing institutions and research organisations. Figure 10 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. Stakeholders from the national and local level were equally represented. Approximately 33% of the participants were female.

Figure 10 - Breakdown of participants in the first follow-up meeting of the country desk and policy lab per stakeholder group

During the country desk meeting, Dirk Vansintjan (REScoop.eu) presented the transposition tracker of REScoop.eu which assesses the progress of the transposition of the Renewable Energy Community (REC) and Citizen Energy Community (CEC) definitions in the European Member States. Erika Meynaerts (VITO/Energyville) and Erik Laes (TU/e) illustrated how the COME RES project can contribute to the practical implementation of the provisions on renewable energy communities in the RED II in Flanders and the Netherlands. They presented the main conclusions from the assessment of the starting conditions for RECs and the assessment of the potential for RECs in the COME RES target regions.

Following the country desk meeting, an interactive policy lab was organised on the enabling framework for renewable energy communities in the Netherlands and Flanders. Padlet was used as a tool to support an interactive discussion between the participants. The participants were allocated to three break-out rooms which dealt with the following questions:

- Based on the requirements of the European Directive (RED II, art. 22 §4), what are the key priorities on which the enabling framework for RECs should focus on in Flanders/the Netherlands?
- How can these priorities be put into practice in Flanders/the Netherlands?

The policy lab resulted in a list of priorities with regard to the implementation of the enabling framework and specific actions/measures that national and local authorities in Flanders and the Netherlands can implement to support the development of renewable energy communities.

Figure 11 – Padlet break-out room 1 (Province of North Brabant) first follow-up meeting and policy lab

The country desk meeting and policy lab yielded a number of conclusions, including:

- The majority of the Member States did not reach the deadline for the transposition. Little efforts have been made by the Member States with regard to the implementation of an enabling framework and adapting existing support mechanisms for RES to the specific characteristics of RECs. Good examples of the transposition of definitions are Belgium, Ireland and Sweden.
- The target regions in Flanders and the Netherlands have a considerable potential for community energy based on PV and wind.
- The participants in the policy lab considered the majority of the requirements of the enabling framework, as stipulated in art. 22 § 4 of the RED II, a key priority for implementation.
- The participants in the policy lab provided some examples of actions/measures that national and local authorities can implement to enable the development of renewable energy communities:
 - Local authorities issue public tenders for RES projects with criteria on, e.g., citizen participation and creating added value for the local community.
 - Capacity building for local authorities on public tendering, citizen participation and RECs.
 - Transposition of national and regional goals on renewables to the local level.
 - Adaptation of regulation and financial support mechanisms to take into account the specific characteristics of RECs which often have small scale RES projects and a primary aim to share the energy produced amongst their members (and not to maximise the self-consumption of the owner of the roof). At the same time, tackle several societal

issues and creating (social, environmental, economic, ...) benefits for the local community.

- The national government should provide a stable and transparent framework to stimulate RES, not only making energy sharing technically feasible but also financially feasible. Regulation should not only be adopted to stimulate RES production to avoid investments in the distribution network (e.g., capacity tariff) but to maximise RES production. A tax shift from electricity towards natural gas can be an important measure to make investments in RES electricity production and district heating networks more attractive.
- As the distribution of heat is a very local issue and not regulated yet, the set-up of a local district heating network supplied with, e.g., residual or waste heat could be a great opportunity for RECs to collaborate with local authorities.
- Provide a loan for feasibility studies to energy communities, to be repaid later in case the project proves to be successful.
- Assessment of costs and benefits so that cost advantages can be allocated if and where energy communities can offer advantages to the grid.

ACTIVITY 4: Second Follow-Up Meeting of Country Desk and Policy Lab

The second follow-up meeting of the Dutch/Flemish country desk took place on 18 October 2022. The aim of this meeting was to present the current status of the COME RES project. Two project results were discussed in more detail, in particular the comparative analysis of the regulatory and enabling framework for renewable energy communities in the nine COME RES countries (D7.1) and the results of the stakeholder survey (D3.4). Back-to-back with the country desk meeting, a policy lab was organised that elaborated on some policy-relevant results from the comparative analysis and stakeholder survey.

The meeting was attended by 21 stakeholders, with representing national policy actors, energy and innovation agencies/competence centres, SMEs, community energy initiatives/energy cooperatives, NGOs and network organisations and research organisations. Figure 12 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. Stakeholders from the national and local level were equally represented. Approximately 33% of stakeholder participants were female.

Figure 12 - Breakdown of participants in the second follow-up meeting of the country desk and policy lab per stakeholder group

During the country desk meeting, Michael Krug (FUB) presented the results of the comparative analysis of the regulatory and enabling framework for renewable energy communities (RECs) in the nine COME RES countries. Erika Meynaerts (VITO) and Erik Laes (VITO, TU/e) illustrated the results of the stakeholder survey sent out in May/June 2022 to the members of country desks in the nine COME RES countries.

Following the country desk meeting, an interactive panel debate on the regulatory and enabling framework for renewable energy communities in the Netherlands and Flanders took place. The panellists (Jan de Pauw, REScoop Flanders, Maarten Tavernier, VVSG, Joep Mol, Platform Coöperatief Duurzaam Noordoost Brabant, Siward Zomer, Energie Samen) and members of the country desk provided their views on the following questions:

- What can Flanders/the Netherlands learn from RED II transposition in other EU countries?
- Our survey indicates that fair access for RECs to the energy system (based on cost-benefit analysis) is a priority. In what respect is current access not fair?
- What role can the (local) government play in the promotion and further development of RECs: passive (as a facilitator) or active (financier or participant)?

The country desk meeting and panel debate produced several conclusions, including:

- The participants agreed with the results of the comparative assessment for Flanders and the Netherlands, namely that Flanders scores well on the transposition of the legislative framework and the Netherlands scores well on the implementation of an enabling framework and specific support schemes for RECs.
- The 50% local ownership target for large-scale land-based renewable electricity generation in the Climate Agreement in the Netherlands is a non-binding target but needs to be further elaborated through spatial policy frameworks. Municipalities often settle for the commitment of

project developers to issue a bond and establish an environment fund to develop projects in the immediate vicinity. Depending on the confidence of the officials and councilors, different approaches are taken in different municipalities. It is unclear whether such arbitrariness can be quickly resolved through a national legislative process that will soon take five years. Through policy, communication and clear images, you often have more impact.

- In the Netherlands, a more pragmatic approach to policy on renewable energy communities is possible because the barriers for entering the electricity market are very low. The Dutch law on the liberalisation of the energy market is very well structured, regulating activities and not parties. As such, the cooperative movement did not have to be overly concerned with elaborating legislation and could focus on supporting the practice.
- At the local level, Flanders has some good examples of provincial and municipal decisions linking citizen participation to the development of renewable energy projects on their territory. However, these decisions are not legally enforceable, so citizen-led initiatives do not have equal access to renewable energy projects as commercial players.
- In Flanders, a general framework for energy suppliers on how to deal with customers that share energy would be useful. That way a renewable energy community can clearly explain to citizens what the advantage of energy sharing is. Today there are still too many variables that make energy sharing in a renewable energy community a bold financial undertaking. If no clear financial benefit can be communicated to participants of a renewable energy community, nobody is going to embark on this adventure.
- Citizen-led initiatives need to professionalise at some point if they want to increase scale and have a say in renewable energy development. If you want to upscale and establish renewable energy communities at urban or regional level, you need not only investors but also development money ('finance-to-develop'). To professionalise, you need funds to hire external staff or pay people in the initiative. Also, grant/funding streams should be aligned, e.g.: start-up grant, planning grant, development loan and then funding or guarantee for equity (heat). It is important that the funds also effectively go through the initiative so that there is professionalisation within the initiative.

The country desk meeting and policy lab was concluded with an overview of the next project steps.

ACTIVITY 5: Second Thematic Workshop

The second thematic workshop was organised on 18 October 2022, back-to-back with the second follow-up meeting of the country desk. The aim of the second thematic workshop was to present and promote the Energy Community Platform (<https://energycommunityplatform.eu/>). Feedback was gathered from the participants about the content and functionalities of the platform. The participants were also encouraged to upload relevant resources, energy communities and experts on the platform.

The meeting was attended by 21 stakeholders, with representation from national policy, energy and innovation agencies/competence centres, SMEs, community energy initiatives/energy cooperatives,

NGOs and network organisations and research organisations. Figure 13 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. Stakeholders from the national and local level were equally represented. Approximately 33% of stakeholder participants were female.

Figure 13 - Breakdown of participants in the second thematic workshop per stakeholder group

During the second thematic workshop, Sara Tachelet Energy (REScoop.eu) presented the Energy Community Platform. Launched recently (during EUSEW 2022), the platform aims to promote community energy projects and accelerate the transition to energy democracy. The platform was developed for citizens interested in community energy or involved in energy communities. The platform is managed by REScoop.eu but was funded through several EU projects (ECCO, Compile, COME RES) and the Tides Foundation (Patagonia).

The platform offers practical resources (e.g., tools, reports, good practices) tailored to start-up and already established energy communities and provides information on relevant experts (advice may be remunerated) and other energy communities (map and fact sheet). The "development stage test" allows an energy community to get an indication of the development stage it is in and provides tailor-made information (indicators, roadmap). The "sustainability scorecard" allows energy communities to evaluate themselves in terms of environmental, economic and social outcomes. The results are presented in a visually appealing scorecard. Recommendations are also given for further development, illustrated with good practices.

One can register for free on the platform. Upon registration, a profile is created. Based on the profile, customised search results are delivered. New resources as well as experts and energy communities can be notified on the platform, with validation and quality control by REScoop.eu.

Participants could try out the platform during the workshop and ask questions with regard to the content and functionalities of the platform. In general, the platform received very positive feedback from the participants.

3.1.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: The Online Survey

The online survey was distributed in May-June 2022 amongst the Flemish and Dutch members of the country desk (with 'snow-ball' effect through their networks). There were 72 respondents in total, of which approximately 80% completed the survey. In Flanders, 69% of the respondents were representatives of national and local authorities, NGOs and network organisations, research organisations, municipal utilities companies and energy community initiatives/energy cooperatives. 40% of the Flemish respondents indicated that they are involved in renewable energy communities. In the Netherlands, 57% of the respondents were energy cooperatives. 77% of the Dutch respondents indicated that they are involved in renewable energy communities.

Some of the key findings of the survey:

- The respondents consider the following activities as most relevant or promising for RECs: electricity generation, heating, storage, flexibility services, and transport. In Flanders, more than 75% of the respondents also consider the built environment an important activity for RECs. Agriculture is considered as the least important activity for RECs.
- The respondents consider following technologies as most important for RECs: PV, wind and storage. In the Netherlands, integrated and hybrid systems are also considered important technological solutions which can be explained by the capacity problems on the distribution grid and successful (pilot) projects of existing energy cooperatives.
- The majority of the barriers that are outlined in the survey are rated important to very important by more than 50% of the respondents. Regulations restricting the ability of RECs to share self-generated energy are considered as the most important barrier for REC development. Lack of network and knowledge and acceptance of the cooperative model are considered as the least important barriers for REC development.
- More than 50% of the respondents consider all aspects outlined in the survey important or very important for the development of RECs. Regulations enabling energy sharing within the energy community and national or regional government support for local authorities are considered the most important aspects for REC development. In Flanders, also the access to adequate information is considered an important aspect.
- In Flanders, it is (very) important that local authorities take an active role in facilitating collaboration between relevant stakeholders such as research institutions, industry, network companies, etc. In the Netherlands, it is (very) important to provide financial support to citizens, SMEs and civil society organisations initiating RECs and to allocate suitable areas to RECs.
- In the Netherlands, almost 75% of respondents are not familiar with the RED II and the provisions and opportunities for RECs. In Flanders, less than 25% of respondents are not familiar with the RED II and the provisions and opportunities for RECs.

- The majority of the respondents consider fair and equal participation of RECs in the electricity system (incl. transparent cost-benefit analysis and fair distribution of network costs among all consumers) as the most urgent measure of the enabling framework to be implemented. In the Netherlands, also the facilitation of access to financing for RECs is considered urgent.

OTHER ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

The Association for Flemish Cities and Municipalities (VVSG), which is a member of the country desk, published two articles on their website which are based on the results of the COME RES project. The articles were written in close collaboration with VITO. The first article was published in the online newsletter of 13 July, 2022 ([COME-RES: Potentieel hernieuwbare energiegemeenschappen in 2 provincies onderzocht \(vvsq.be\)](#)) and gives the main results of the assessment of the potential for REC development in the Flemish target regions, West Flanders and Limburg (based on D2.2). The second article was published in the online newsletter of 9 November 2022 ([Onderzoek naar energiegemeenschappen: Vlaanderen scoort goed voor wetgeving, slecht voor ondersteuning \(vvsq.be\)](#)) and gives an overview of the main conclusions of the assessment of the regulatory and enabling framework for RECs in Flanders (based on D7.1).

3.1.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

The country desk meetings have yielded a number of outcomes and lessons learned. One of the most significant lessons learned is the extent to which there is a lack of information and knowledge across actors at the local level about the regulatory and enabling framework for RECs. While the country desk has made progress in providing stakeholders with access to information and lines of communication, this should remain an important point for the attention of policy makers while further developing and implementing the enabling framework.

Beyond this, the desk meetings have identified several barriers and drivers for the establishment and further development of RECs in the target regions, suggesting critical components of an enabling framework, e.g., access to information and financing, equal/fair access to the energy market, tailor-made support mechanisms, capacity building of local authorities. In the thematic workshops and policy labs, we explored further how local policies and RECs interact and how they can mutually reinforce each other. Local governments can take an active role in the promotion and further development of RECs by, e.g., facilitating cooperation between relevant local stakeholders, providing financial support, allocating public roofs/land, taking into account citizen participation in public tendering.

One of the advantages that has emerged from the transnational character of the Belgian/Dutch country desk is the facilitation of communication between key actors and stakeholders in the development of renewable energy communities in Flanders and North Brabant, yielding a more encompassing set of tools to support the establishment and further development of renewable energy communities in both countries. In particular, Flanders and North Brabant proved to be complementary in the sense that Flanders has progressed further in the legal implementation of key stipulations of the RED II, whereas North Brabant (or the Netherlands in general) scores better on implementing an enabling framework for energy communities. Hence, mutual learning between the stakeholders from both regions could occur.

At the same time, it was at times difficult to get a deeper discussion of recent policy developments in both Belgium and the Netherlands, as there are marked different governance structures and debates in both these countries. For instance, in the Netherlands the distribution grid is faced with capacity problems when dealing with the demand to integrate more local renewable electricity productions, whereas this is not the case in Flanders. In addition, the Dutch national policy to move away from natural gas as a source for heating in the built environment opens up a great opportunity for energy communities to form around local heat distribution grids (even though heating grids are 'out of scope' in the COME RES project). Flanders has no comparable policy framework.

Even though the transnational character of the Belgian/Dutch country desk had its pros and cons, we in any case conclude that the Belgian/Dutch country desk facilitated connections between Dutch and Flemish stakeholders that would otherwise not have connected. The country desk offered for stakeholders from both countries a unique experience to get a better feeling of how things might be radically different 'across the border', whilst at the same time showing how both countries have to react to the same European legislation.

3.2. GERMANY

The German country desk has been organised by Freie Universität Berlin (FUB) in close collaboration with the Thuringian Energy and GreenTech Agency (ThEGA) and included important stakeholders such as community energy associations and initiatives, RES organisations, public authorities and policy makers from the model and target regions Schleswig-Holstein and Thuringia, as well as stakeholders from other German regions and organisations operating nationwide highlighting the interest in the project from all over Germany.

Table 5 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the German Desk during months 4-27

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Makers*
Kick-Off Meeting	11.12.2020	Online	Presentation of the project and the European legal framework, discussion of the legal framework, frame conditions in the model region Schleswig-Holstein and target region Thuringia, key obstacles for energy communities and possible problem solutions.	37 (core group)	3
First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab <i>"The future of citizen wind power - How should an enabling framework for RECs look like?"</i>	30.03.2021	Online	Presentation of the project's progress, issues concerning the RED II transposition process, potentials for RECs in Thuringia and Schleswig Holstein, possible (political) support measures (e.g., citizen energy funds). Low level of local acceptance even for community energy projects as a barrier.	70	8
First Status Meeting <i>"Energy communities – potentials, business models, good practice"</i>	21.09.2021	Online	Presentation of the project's progress, especially findings of Deliverable 2.2 (REC potential assessment), presentation and discussion of business models and good practices, discussion of a citizen energy fund in Thuringia and on the national level.	54	5
Second Thematic Workshop and second Policy Lab <i>"Renewable Energy"</i>	31.03.2022	online	The aim of this workshop was to present first findings of COME RES, discuss the transposition of RED II and its	63	6

<i>Communities: Perspectives in Europe and Germany”</i>	implications for RECs in Europe and Germany, and present current proposals to improve the enabling framework for community energy in Germany.
Second Country Desk Status Meeting	The final country desk meeting presented selected results of COME RES and the draft policy recommendations for Germany, discussed the role of RECs in times of energy crisis and how to implement energy sharing in Germany taking into account the experiences in Austria and Italy.
Third Policy Round Table "Renewable Energy Communities in Times of Multiple Crises“	23.11.2022 online 45 5

* Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials

3.2.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

The country desk activities gave important insights into the challenges and the current state of RECs in Germany in general and Thuringia more specifically and supported the further development of existing RECs. In the process of analysing barriers, potentials, and the transposition of the RED II with different national stakeholders, the country desk meetings provided a good opportunity for stakeholders to also exchange ideas and opinions and to network with other stakeholders and policy makers. The presentations of national and international good practices such as, e.g., *Grenzland-Pool* in Schleswig-Holstein or the community virtual power plant in Loenen (Netherlands) introduced new business models to the stakeholders and gave inspiration for the future development of RECs. Furthermore, policy makers from Thuringia, Schleswig-Holstein and from the national level informed the participants of current legal developments, including the transposition of RED II or the citizen energy fund (*Bürgerenergiefonds*) that is being developed in Thuringia following the example of Schleswig-Holstein. These presentations were embedded in dedicated policy labs/roundtables and followed by a dialogue with other policy makers, representatives from community energy associations and the other desk/workshop participants.

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-Off Meeting

The Kick-Off meeting was held online on 11 December 2020 and was attended by a core group of 37 stakeholders and markets actors, of which 38% female (including the organisation team). The main goal of this meeting was to launch the German Desk and to present the COME RES project to a core group of key stakeholders. Furthermore, the status quo and framework for (renewable) energy communities in Germany were discussed, including barriers and possible solutions. Participants included representatives from community energy initiatives, public authorities and policy makers from the national level, the target and model region, and other regions as well, highlighting the interest in the project from all over Germany.

Figure 14 - Breakdown of participants per stakeholder group in the KOM of the German Desk

The event started with the presentation of the COME RES project, its goals, tasks and the role of the country desk by the project coordinator Rosaria Di Nucci (FUB). Next, Michael Krug (FUB) and René Groß (DGRV, National Office for Energy Cooperatives) reported about the transposition of the RED II in Germany and the future development perspectives for energy cooperatives. In the following discussion, many participants shared their scepticism with regards to a full and timely transposition of the RED II and its provisions for collective self-consumption and energy communities in Germany.

Subsequently, the framework for community energy, obstacles, problem areas and examples of good practice in the model region Schleswig-Holstein and the target region Thuringia were discussed by Nicole Knudsen (BWE Schleswig-Holstein, Wind Energy Association), Ramona Rothe (ThEGA, Thuringian Energy and GreenTech Agency), Prof. Reinhard Guthke and Marcel Schwalbach (both BürgerEnergie Thüringen e.V., Regional association of Citizen Energy in Thuringia). The guaranteed feed-in tariffs provided through the Electricity Feed Act and later the Renewable Energy Sources Act as well as the high level of planning security for investors were considered as important success factors explaining the dynamic development of energy communities in Schleswig-Holstein, but also other regions. The specific model of community wind farms in Schleswig-Holstein is certainly not fully transferable to other regions, but there are definitely parallels and common challenges.

Various participants referred to existing forms of cooperation between municipal utilities and energy cooperatives in Thuringia as good practice cases. According to Marcel Schwalbach (Board of directors of energy cooperative Ilmtal eG), energy sharing makes energy cooperatives more interesting for project developers, adding to its overall attractiveness. Hence, Tom Janneck (VZSH, Consumer Advice Center Schleswig-Holstein) and Matthias Golle (Ilmtal eG) suggested exploring further cooperation possibilities between energy cooperatives and municipal utilities/energy supply companies.

An overview of different forms of cooperation between municipal utilities and energy cooperatives in Germany can be found here: <https://www.energiegenossenschaften-gruenden.de/kooperation-stadtwerke.html>.

In their joint presentation, Angelika Behlig and Milena Schulz-Gärtner (MELUND, Ministry for Energy Transition, Agriculture, Environment, Nature and Digitalisation of the State of Schleswig-Holstein) introduced the Citizens' Energy Fund in Schleswig-Holstein, which was established in 2018. Through this fund, citizen/community energy projects can be supported in the start-up phase, in which project financing via financing institutions is not yet available. Beneficiaries would have to repay the funding as soon as overall project financing would be secured. Marcel Schwalbach and Matthias Golle mentioned that Thuringia is going to follow the example of Schleswig-Holstein and that the regional government recently decided to set up a similar fund. René Groß (DGRV, National Office for Energy Cooperatives) reported that there were also plans to establish such a fund at the national level.

Figure 15– Interactive section: Analysis of the present barriers and future options

Finally, the participants discussed the opportunities and risks regarding energy communities in Germany and especially in Thuringia.

- Digitalisation and digital platforms may provide a chance for energy cooperatives, e.g., if used to sell electricity (see Bürgerwerke eG.), but are still in an early stage. A problem arises with new foreign players that could occupy the electricity market, especially in the field of on-site trading/energy sharing, and prevent individuals to join a more time-consuming and expensive energy community.

- Land availability and land securing is another problem that was addressed. Often, project planning companies secure land at an early stage and tend to not cooperate with energy communities. Participants underlined the importance of regional planning authorities/communities and a proactive approach of informing and sensitising local landowners about energy communities.
- Furthermore, the lack of local acceptance of (community) wind farms was mentioned several times. An increasing polarisation in many communities leads to a shift of focus of citizen energy movements towards more accepted systems, such as PV rooftop systems. Some participants proposed labelling and certification schemes (e.g., under the Economy of the Common Good initiative) as a tool to tackle the acceptance problems. Some promising examples exist already in Schleswig-Holstein and Thuringia.
- Finally, the inclusion of low-income households and people who have not been very interested in the energy transition so far was emphasised. Tom Janneck (VZSH) suggested to find solutions to realise collective self-consumption and tenant power concepts and on how to deal with financial shortfalls.

Rosaria Di Nucci summarised that whilst at a federal level, progress in the implementation of the RED II is not very encouraging, there are some promising signals at the level of the federal states. The kick-off event illustrated the role of social and local acceptance as a critical barrier to the energy transition. Citizen energy and renewable energy communities are considered an important instrument not only for decentralisation, but also for the democratisation of the energy system in Germany and elsewhere.

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The first thematic workshop was held on 30 March 2021 together with the policy lab entitled "The Future of Citizen Wind Power - What Should a Regulatory Framework for Renewable Energy Communities Look Like?" Its aim was to organise a stakeholder dialogue on the transposition and implementation of the recast Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) in Germany and in the different Länder, especially with regard to the regulations addressing specifically RECs. The joint online event was attended by 70 stakeholders and markets actors, of which 31% female, including a high share of elected politicians, policy makers and public authorities from the EU, as well from the national, regional and local level. Due to the high policy relevance, the combined event was intended to gather a broader spectrum of participants and also to enlarge and reinforce the core stakeholder group and offer a forum to exchange experiences. Participants from regions beyond the COME RES target and model regions joined the event (e.g., from Bavaria, Berlin, Brandenburg, Saxony, North Rhine-Westphalia, etc.).

The workshop first presented the COME RES project and dealt with selected issues of the transposition process in Germany. Prof. Dr. Dieter Sell (ThEGA), Dr. Rosaria Di Nucci and Michael Krug (FUB) representing the project and country desk coordination stressed that in Germany there is still a lack of a legal definition of RECs that fully complies with the requirements of the RED II. Further transposition gaps have been identified in the field of electricity sharing or regarding the required assessment of barriers and development potentials for RECs. Ana Maria Sanchez Infante of the European Commission DG Energy, provided insights into the European energy policy context, the policy objectives and the

legal framework for RECs and citizen energy communities (CECs) provided by the RED II and the Integrated Electricity Market Directive respectively.

Figure 16 - Breakdown of participants per stakeholder group in the first Thematic Workshop

Klaus Mindrup (Member of the Federal Parliament, SPD) and Malte Zieher (Bündnis Bürgerenergie, Alliance for Citizens' Energy) held presentations on the historical development of citizen energy and the concept of energy sharing, respectively. They however concluded that the pioneering role of Germany had changed, and that the former government hindered the transposition of the RED II: The existing definition of citizens' energy companies has not been adjusted and the concept of energy sharing has not been transposed in the German legislation. Dr. Phillipp Leander Wolfshohl (Bundesnetzagentur, Federal Network Agency) illustrated recent developments of the auction system. He also pointed out that one of the political goals linked to the auctions was to safeguard actor diversity. This political goal, however, has been neglected by the government. The auction system does not necessarily safeguard actor diversity. Furthermore, representatives of RECs underlined that frequent changes of the laws and the increasing complexity of the market rules would jeopardise the principle of non-discrimination. In a Slido survey the workshop participants were asked how the auction system should look like in the future in order to facilitate the development of energy communities in the area of wind energy. 61% of the 31 respondents were in favour to make use of the "de minimis clause"³ and to exempt community wind energy from the auctions and provide predictable support instead. 29% of respondents supported the proposal to create special segments/bidding rounds exclusively for community wind farms in the frame of the auction system. 10% of the respondents were in favour of providing additional privileges/incentives in the frame of the existing auction system. None of the respondents supported the proposal to keep the auction design as it is.

The thematic block was followed by an interactive dialogue session where the key issues were highlighted:

³ De minimis clause is a legal principle which allows for matters that are small scale or of insufficient importance to be exempted from a rule or requirement.

- Need for further action regarding the transposition and implementation of RED II: Clear definitions of RECs and CECs are needed because too vague legal definitions in combination with attractive privileges for citizen energy companies in the field of wind energy led to the misuse of the concept after the amendments to the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) in 2017 which marked the transition from feed in tariffs/premiums to auctions.
- Development potentials for RECs in the target and model region.
- Elements of an enabling framework for RECs: It was emphasised by several participants that (financial) participation of citizens and local communities is generally necessary to achieve a broader level of social acceptance. This should be accompanied by effective formal and informal procedural participation.
- Possibilities of the federal states, districts and municipalities to facilitate the development of energy communities including RECs. The participants discussed existing support instruments for RECs like community resp. citizen energy funds. Schleswig-Holstein was the first of the German Länder that has set up such a fund in 2018. Stakeholders from Thuringia appreciated that the Thuringian state government decided to follow this example.

Subsequently, a survey among the participants of the meeting showed that electricity and heat production (70%), energy sharing and collective self-consumption (59%), tenant electricity models (52%) and electricity sales (41%) are considered as the most promising business areas for energy communities in the future.

The policy lab was designed as a roundtable and involved: Ana Maria Sanchez Infante (European Commission, GD ENER), Tobias Goldschmidt (State Secretary, Ministry of Energy Transition, Schleswig-H.), Klaus Mindrup (Member of Federal Parliament, SPD, Representative for Cooperatives), Markus Gleichmann (Member of State Parliament, Thuringia, Die Linke, European Committee of the Regions), Laura Wahl (Member of State Parliament, Thuringia, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen), and Hans-Jürgen Weidt (Mayor of the Municipality of Werther, Thuringia). Initially, the policy roundtable addressed issues related to the transposition of RED II from both a European and a regional perspective. Furthermore, the contributions of energy communities or RECs to enhance social acceptance were highlighted. Further acceptance factors which have been identified include the involvement of all citizens, early fact-based information, and the generation of local value added. A problem in Thuringia is the negative perception of the energy transition - frames are crucial, e.g., in relation to public services and job creation, since there is severe local opposition against wind energy projects. It was proposed to introduce a spatial target for wind energy at federal level (2% of the total area to be reserved for wind energy) and to launch a nationwide citizen energy fund. In addition, the importance of cooperation between cooperatives and municipalities, as well as between urban and rural regions, was stressed together with an expansion of the leeway for financial participation offered to municipalities. It was suggested to check whether the possibility of voluntary payments by the operators of new wind farms to host municipalities which has been recently introduced with the amendments of the Renewable Energy Sources Act of 2020 might be extended to operators of existing wind energy plants.

As a summary, it was pointed out that the transposition and implementation of the RED II may face the risk of becoming a lost opportunity in Germany. The implementation process has multiple dimensions, but shows significant implementations deficits. In the workshop, important elements that should be included in a future enabling framework for RECs were mentioned (e.g., citizen energy funds). The presentations and reactions in the chat also illustrated the socio-political, economic and environmental challenges involved, in particular the need for concretisation of a number of vague and unspecified legal terms in relation to RECs (e.g., purpose, proximity, effective control, rights of RECs including energy sharing etc.).

Figure 17 shows a summary of the active engagement of the participating stakeholders on Slido during the workshop.

COMERES Zukunft der Bürgerwindkraft Online-Workshop 30.03.21

Figure 17 - Participant engagement in the First Thematic Workshop

ACTIVITY 3: First Status Meeting

A so-called status meeting was organised online on 30 September 2021 with the purpose to present outcomes and current activities of the COME RES project, to discuss business models and good practice cases and to reflect on actual policy developments in Germany. In particular, in view of the results of the Bundestag elections, the status meeting aimed to provide an opportunity for exchange and networking in a (virtual) space. The meeting was attended by 54 stakeholders and markets actors, of which 50% female, including all stakeholder groups except media representatives.

Figure 18 - Breakdown of participants per stakeholder group in the Status Meeting

The status meeting was structured into three sections: First, new project findings including the results of an analysis of REC potentials in Thuringia and current activities of the COME RES project were presented, followed by four good practice cases of energy communities in Germany. The third session was dedicated to the enabling framework for RECs. Participants discussed the future of the energy transition and the transposition of the RED II and its provisions for RECs in Germany after the federal parliament elections of 2021. The meeting was concluded by a discussion of the specifications of a citizen energy fund in Thuringia which soon will start operation.

Prof. Dieter Sell (ThEGA) opened the meeting with Dr. Rosaria Di Nucci (FFU). Moreover, Dr. Di Nucci (FUB) presented key activities and preliminary results of the COME RES project and illustrated some activities of other COME RES country desks, especially Italy and Portugal. Michael Krug (FUB) gave a brief review of the two previous country desk meetings in Germany which have been documented in detail on the project website. Further, he presented together with Vincenzo Gatta key assumptions and selected results of the assessment report of potentials for RECs in Thuringia that were recently compiled as a project report. Several participants questioned the assumption of 100% self-financing by citizens, and considered this not realistic at least for wind energy. Michael Krug specified that the condition of 100% self-financing does not exclude the possibility of taking up loans and that the assumptions had to reflect the different conditions in each country included in the study. However, the presenters conceded that in the case of wind energy, a 20% share of citizen-based financing is more realistic.

Johannes Vollmer (bbh) gave preliminary insights of an analysis of REC business models and provided examples from different COME RES countries, especially Italy. Here, the RED II with its provisions for RECs has been largely transposed to national law and an enabling framework for RECs is taking shape. A high public interest and various impulses from local public authorities helped to develop a large number of RECs, especially in small municipalities which aim to benefit from those RECs. In comparison to the Italian case, Horst Leithoff (BWE Schleswig-Holstein, Wind Energy Association) referred to the difficult framework conditions in Germany where energy sharing and self-consumption by members of a REC are practically impossible. The same would be true for combinations of energy production, energy storage and energy refinement which would be hampered by the restrictive system of taxes, fees and surcharges. Subsequently, a survey among the participants of the meeting showed that electricity and heat production (70%), energy sharing and collective self-consumption (59%), tenant electricity models (52%) and electricity sales (41%) are considered as the most promising business areas for energy communities in the future.

Next, four good practice cases were presented:

- Wind farm Uthleben: Co-operation between a developer, a municipal utility company and citizen energy cooperatives in Thuringia (presented by Thomas Mund, managing director of the municipal utility company Stadtwerke Nordhausen),
- Pool of five community wind energy projects in Schleswig-Holstein (“Grenzland-Pool”) with activities in the field of sector coupling and hydrogen production (presented by Horst Leithoff, Managing Director of several community wind farms including Bürgerwindpark Grenzstrom

Vindtved and Chairman of the regional section of the German Wind Energy Association in Schleswig-Holstein),

- Direct marketing of electricity from community energy projects in North Rhine-Westphalia (presented by Thomas Voss, Die Energielandwerker eG, a developer of renewable energy projects),
- Pilot project on energy sharing in Essen/North Rhine-Westphalia based on so called consumer stock ownership plans implemented in the frame of the Horizon 2020 project SCORE (presented by Prof. Jens Lowitzsch, Viadrina University Frankfurt (Oder)).

The cases illustrated that not only cooperation between citizens is important, but also between different market actors like cooperatives and other citizen-based organisations, municipal utility companies and project developers. It proved fruitful to join forces and pool different citizen energy projects in order to gain a stronger market position and to profit from value-added effects, e.g., when selling electricity while owning local substations. Furthermore, RECs can profit from the collaboration and know-how of project developers and municipal utilities. In this manner, RECs can reduce risks and counteract the consequences of the increasing complexity of the legal framework that discourage citizens to engage in citizen energy projects. All these synergies are best illustrated in the concept of energy sharing.

The final section was dedicated to the enabling framework for RECs. First, Dr. Julia Verlinden (Bündnis 90/Die Grünen), member of the previous and newly elected federal parliament and so far energy policy spokeswoman of the Green Party, gave a keynote presentation on the prospects of the energy transition in general and on the implementation of RED II after the Bundestag elections in particular. She argued in favour of a higher CO₂ pricing and also pleaded for a reform of the electricity market design. She said two trends could be observed, flexibilisation and digitalisation, which could contribute to a further decentralisation of electricity production. Further, she saw a need for action regarding the transposition and implementation of the relevant EU directives, especially in the area of collective self-consumption, energy sharing and energy communities. In the following discussion she emphasised the role of citizen and community energy in order to allocate new investments for the energy transition. However, the developments in Brussels should always be kept in mind (e.g., with regard to the “de minimis rule” and the new State Aid Guidelines). She supported the development of a citizen energy fund on the federal level as a useful tool measure to set uniform standards.

In the final presentation, Prof. Dieter Sell (ThEGA) illustrated cornerstones of the planned citizen energy fund in Thuringia, to be based on a funding guideline (*Förderrichtlinie*) and to largely follow the example of the citizen energy fund in Schleswig-Holstein. The participants emphasised the importance of a clear definition of citizen energy in order to prevent the misuse of state funds. In this regard, Ramona Rothe (ThEGA) explained that according to the funding guideline, the fund will offer financing of citizen energy projects in the planning and start-up phase. 500,000 EUR have been earmarked from the state budget. The aim is to strengthen citizen energy projects in the fields of renewable electricity and heat generation, energy efficiency, new mobility and digitalisation in the energy sector. As a rule, funding is awarded in the form of a conditionally repayable and interest-bearing grant to citizen collectives comprising at least seven natural persons who must have their primary residence in the municipality concerned. In addition

to that, and similar to the case in Schleswig-Holstein, planned projects would be examined very carefully for their feasibility.

In his conclusions, Michael Krug (FUB) stressed the importance and urgency of implementing the relevant EU directives and their provisions for energy communities. However, in the existing target architecture of the German energy transition, this is a blank spot, and it is worth considering the inclusion of quantitative and/or qualitative targets for citizen energy in general and energy communities in particular. In addition, the EU dimension should always be kept in mind, as important decisions are currently being made there, such as the revision of the State Aid Guidelines. Finally, the event and particularly the good practice cases illustrated how important cooperation between citizen energy actors and municipal utilities can be and how valuable networking and clustering among citizen energy actors is.

ACTIVITY 4: Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The second thematic workshop and policy lab of the German country desk was held online on 31 March 2022. Prominent stakeholders and policy makers, including members of the national and regional parliaments in Thuringia and Schleswig-Holstein, experts from ministries (e.g., Thuringian Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Energy Transition in Schleswig-Holstein) and other public authorities (6 in total) were among the 63 participants. Regional stakeholders - mostly from Thuringia and Schleswig-Holstein, partly from other federal states (*Länder*) - were slightly in the majority with a share of 55% compared to national, transnational (EU) and international stakeholders. 40% of the participants were women.

Figure 19 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group

During the event, the COME RES project and selected (interim) results for Germany were presented including an overview of the country desk activities in all partner countries. Furthermore, good practice examples of selected community energy initiatives and RECs from the other COME RES partner countries were presented and discussed. These raised interest among the German stakeholders, especially those cases which show a good collaboration of community energy initiatives with municipalities and where municipalities have initiated or are actively involved in REC activities, e.g., in

Magliano Alpi (Italy), Crevillent (Spain) or in the case of the multifunctional Energy Gardens (Netherlands). Cooperation between community energy initiatives and municipalities or municipal multi-utility companies (*Stadtwerke*) can help to overcome local acceptance barriers, particularly in the field of wind energy or ground-mounted PV.

The workshop included two guest presentations by the COME RES project partners Dr. Erik Laes and Dr. Kellan Anfinson from the Technical University of Eindhoven addressing the transposition of the RED II in the Netherlands and the good practice showcase of the community virtual power plant in the municipality of Loenen.

In the following session, the change of the federal government in Germany and its implications for RECs and RES in general were discussed. In this context, the energy reform launched by the new government (so called Easter Package- *Osterpaket*) was discussed by the participants. Dr. Antje Kießwetter from the Thuringian Ministry of Environment presented the planned support measures for citizen energy with a focus on the new citizen energy fund (*Bürgerenergiefonds*). The following discussion illustrated that the citizen energy fund is a good starting point but will not suffice for enhancing REC initiatives. Additional measures are needed to support the planning phase of new REC projects and support the members of RECs, mostly volunteers, on their way to professionalisation.

In an interactive workshop session, different topics were addressed. First, participants discussed how an enabling framework for RECs should be designed in Germany taking into account the respective provisions laid down in RED II, particularly in Article 22(4). One of the most important arguments was that planning and project approval procedures need to be streamlined. Complex and lengthy procedures represent a major barrier, particularly for new and small projects with only limited resources and know-how. Further, Malte Zieher (Alliance for Citizens' Energy - *Bündnis Bürgerenergie*) illustrated the barriers for energy sharing in Germany referring to the intersection of different laws. He also explained that the government prioritises the reform of the electricity market design and other aspects of the energy market. In the following, different options for vulnerable and low-income households to participate in RECs were discussed. As active financial participation is often missing, ways of passive participation, e.g., through reduced electricity tariffs should be considered.

The highlight of the workshop was a policy lab/roundtable involving policy makers, representatives from public authorities and renewable and community energy associations. The Russian aggression against Ukraine was one of the issues addressed and the participants underlined the need for decentralised renewable energy systems. The participants further discussed and assessed the planned amendments to the Renewable Energy Sources Act (*EEG*) and other legislative measures included in the so-called Easter Package (*Osterpaket*) and their respective drawbacks and advantages. Timon Gremmels (Member of the Federal Parliament, Social Democratic Party, SPD) provided important insights into the policy formulation process and anticipated that energy sharing will probably be possible soon, since the new government decided to remove one of the largest barriers, the so-called Renewable Energy Levy (*EEG-Umlage*). But still, several shortcomings remain related to the transposition of RED II. Referring to the planned amendments of the definition of “citizen energy companies” (the German equivalent for REC), it was recommended to increase the “radius of participation” and the remuneration of RES based

electricity fed into the grid. Furthermore, landlord-to-tenant electricity models and collective self-consumption schemes were characterised as being economically not attractive and facing manifold legal/administrative barriers.

In her conclusion Rosaria Di Nucci remarked that since the last country desk meeting in September 2021, there has been some progress in developing an enabling framework for RECs, also in terms of transposing the provisions of RED II and that the commitment of the new government gives some reason for optimism. Yet, important barriers remain for the development of RECs. These are:

- Lengthy and complex planning and permitting procedures, administrative barriers
- Lack of a regulatory and enabling framework for energy sharing
- Insufficient participation of low-income households in RECs.

ACTIVITY 5: Second Status Meeting and Policy Round Table

The final country desk meeting was held on 23 November 2022. The purpose of this meeting was to present selected results and final activities of the COME RES project, to inform about the good practice transfer activities, to discuss current policy developments and to present draft policy recommendations for Germany. The status meeting provided an opportunity for exchange and networking for the 45 participants, of which 47% women, in a (virtual) space.

Figure 20 - Breakdown of participants in the second status meeting of the German country desk per stakeholder group

Ramona Rothe (ThEGA) opened the meeting together with Dr Rosaria Di Nucci (FUB) and highlighted the challenges for RECs in the current energy crisis. Dr Di Nucci then presented main results of the COME RES project including the energy community platform and the good practice transfer processes initiated by the COME RES consortium, including a Dutch-German transfer initiative. The latter was further explained by Prof. Reinhard Guthke (BürgerEnergie Thüringen e.V.). The purpose of the Dutch-German transfer activities was to initiate a transfer of the Dutch best practice case of 'Multifunctional Energy Gardens' to Thuringia. Concluding the first section, Michael Krug (FUB) presented the results of a comparative analysis of the RED II implementation in the nine COME RES countries. This was

followed by a discussion of the still existing key barriers for RECs in Germany, although it was remarked that some progress has been made since the change of government one year ago. As the results of a Slido survey among the participants highlight (see Figure 21), main barriers include the amount and complexity of regulations RECs have to cope with, the missing enabling framework for energy sharing, but also the low political attention towards RECs in the current discourse focused on short-term political measures to mitigate the present energy crisis as well as the planned levy for excess profits of energy companies which will likely also apply for energy cooperatives and other community energy initiatives.

Multiple-choice poll (Multiple answers)

Figure 21 – Results of a Slido poll among desk participants on the most important barriers for energy communities

The next session was dedicated to the implementation of energy sharing in other EU countries and introduced by two guest presentations: Eva Dvorak representing the Austrian Coordination Centre for Energy Communities (*Österreichische Koordinationsstelle für Energiegemeinschaften*) and Dr. Riccardo Novo (Kelso Institute Europe) illustrated the Austrian and Italian examples for a successful implementation of RECs and Energy Sharing. The foreign perspective gave valuable insights for the German stakeholders on concrete steps that are necessary to support the development of RECs. Subsequently, Malte Zieher (*Bündnis Bürgerenergie*) compared the three presented cases Austria, Italy

and Germany and presented the recommendations of his organisation for a successful implementation of energy sharing in Germany. These envisage, inter alia, to introduce a premium for electricity shared within a REC (similarly to the case of Italy where a premium of 11 ct/kWh applies). Electricity fed into the grid will continue to receive a market premium. In the following discussion, it became clear that energy sharing is key to enhance the mainstreaming of RECs in Germany. The participants appreciated the establishment of support services for RECs in other COME RES countries and in particular in Austria. In another Slido survey (see Figure 22), participants were asked to identify the most important barriers for energy sharing in Germany. 82% of the respondents consider the missing enabling framework as the highest barrier. However, the low level of digitalisation and poor endowment of consumers with smart meters is a hindrance as well.

Multiple-choice poll (Multiple answers)

Welches sind die größten Hemmnisse für Energy Sharing in Deutschland? 0 1 6

(1/2)

Figure 22 – Results of a Slido poll among desk participants on the most important barriers for energy sharing

The concluding session was introduced by a joint presentation of Dr Di Nucci, Michael Krug, and Lucas Schwarz (FUB) who illustrated the draft policy recommendations for Germany based on the overall project’s findings, addressing national, regional and municipal policy makers. This was followed by a policy lab resp. roundtable moderated by Dr Dörte Fouquet (bbh and European Federation of Renewable Energies) involving elected politicians, ministerial officials, community energy associations and energy cooperatives. First of all, the roundtable participants discussed current policy processes at EU level including the development of the RED III and IV. Furthermore, they addressed the plans of the

Federal government to skim off the windfall profits of energy companies including operators of wind and solar farms due to the high gas prices in combination with the merit order effect. There is a large risk that these plans will lead to a loss of trust among energy communities and SMEs. In addition, the auctions were criticised (again) for not being effective in cutting costs, but also for discriminating energy communities. There are currently too few projects which have been granted approval, which means that competition in the auctions is low, and a reduction of electricity prices is hardly achieved. It is true that the Federal government has launched several measures to speed up planning and permitting procedures in cooperation with the state (*Länder*) governments, but these measures will likely have only long-term effects. Most of the participants agreed that the temporary suspension of the auctions would be helpful to increase private investments and thus encourage the development of RECs in Germany in this energy crisis. From a political perspective, Markus Gleichmann (Member of the Parliament of Thuringia, the Left Party) added that funds for RECs are in principle available in Thuringia, but the policy process is too slow and impeding the distribution of the funds. He also pointed out to the difficult political situation in Thuringia with a minority government, a powerful opposition including the populist AfD party on the far right of the political spectrum.

The meeting highlighted the potential of RECs to solve some of the problems related to the current energy crisis. But the lengthy administrative procedures and complex regulations in Germany are impeding their development and so is the missing enabling framework for energy sharing. Furthermore, the poor consideration of RECs in the current government efforts to manage the energy crisis may potentially lead to detrimental effects for RECs in Germany. Finally, the auctions represent still a major barrier for RES projects in general and at least partly for projects of RECs, although the Federal government decided to exempt projects of RECs falling under the *de minimis*' thresholds from the participation in auctions.

Concluding the meeting, Dr Di Nucci pointed out that in the EU, governments take short-term measures to reduce energy costs for households and SMEs. While these are necessary, they only provide temporary relief and are not sustainable in the long run. To counter the return of fossil fuels or nuclear power, it is necessary to focus on a new energy model based on renewables, storage and smart grids in which consumers and prosumers take an active role in the energy system. Regarding RECs, progress has been made in terms of transposing the provisions of the RED II, but there are still too many regulatory and other barriers hampering a swift implementation of an enabling framework. Energy sharing with the associated digitalisation remains a key issue in Germany. Michael Krug added that RECs provide multiple answers to the current multiple crises Germany and the other EU countries are currently facing and should become a cornerstone in any political strategy to cope with those crises. They make a significant contribution to protecting European citizens against the volatility of the energy market, contribute to local security of supply, may reduce the need for grid expansion and are a suitable means to promote socially acceptable regional integrative solutions for 100% renewable energy.

Dr. Di Nucci and Michael Krug closed the meeting and thanked all participants for the fruitful cooperation within the Desk over the last two years and for the many suggestions which are going to be taken into account in the revision of the lessons learned and formulation of the policy recommendations. They

flagged up the final COME RES Conference in Brussels on 31 January 2023 and invited all participants to join the event.

3.2.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: THE ONLINE SURVEY

A dedicated stakeholder consultation was carried out in all nine COME RES partner countries in the form of an online survey. This covered, inter alia, perceptions of the role of RECs in the energy transition, relevant legal forms and actors of RECs, promising technologies and fields of REC activities, and measures needed for scaling up REC development. The online survey was open for German stakeholders during May and June 2022. In total, 52 stakeholders participated (of which 15 from Thuringia and 37 from other regions in Germany). The spectrum of institutions represented by the respondents was rather balanced with a certain preponderance of energy and innovation agencies/competence centers, energy cooperatives, associations/groups of interests and NGOs, which was the case in most country desk activities.

In Germany, respondents considered that RECs will play a very important role in the energy transition, especially to ensure sufficient renewable energy production and enhance public acceptance. A large majority of the German stakeholders considered energy cooperatives as the most relevant legal form for RECs. This is only broadly in line with the results in other COME RES countries that consider more a variety of legal forms. Furthermore, respondents in Germany considered electricity and heat generation as the most promising fields of activity for RECs. The online survey also revealed that 87% of the respondents consider the reduction of administrative burdens as highly important to promote development of RECs. Removal of unjustified legal and administrative barriers for RECs represents the most important element of an enabling framework, followed by cooperation with DSOs, and access to funding. Taking a look into the survey findings of all nine COME RES countries, PV was generally considered the most relevant technology for RECs. Only in Germany, the relevance for onshore wind energy comes close to PV, underlining the pioneering role of Germany in citizen wind energy.

In general, the results of the survey support the findings of the German country desk activities and make them comparable to the other COME RES countries, highlighting some important differences.

INPUT TO GOOD/BEST PRACTICE TRANSFERS

During the first and second thematic workshop of the German country desk, the participants discussed good/best practice cases from Germany and other COME RES partner countries. They also assessed the possibilities to transfer good practices from other COME RES countries or from other regions in Germany to the COME RES target region of Thuringia. Inspired by the outcomes of those workshops, FUB in consultation with two core stakeholders of the country desk from Thuringia (Thuringian Energy and GreenTech Agency, BürgerEnergie Thüringen e.V.) decided to initiate a transfer of good practices. The COME RES good practice showcases from the Netherlands, particularly the innovative concept of the 'Multi-functional Energy Gardens', appeared to be particularly promising. In order to carry out the transfer activities, a transfer team was set up involving German and Dutch COME RES project partners,

committed stakeholders from Thuringia and other regions participating in the German country desk and Dutch mentoring experts.

The Dutch-German transfer activities started in June 2022 with a transfer visit and capacity development workshops held in the Netherlands, when experts from Thuringia and other regions in Germany travelled to Noord-Brabant and Gelderland, to visit and learn from three good practice energy communities. These included the so called 'Multifunctional Energy Gardens', the citizen wind farm *de Spinder* and the community virtual power plant in Loenen. After the transfer visit, the transfer team agreed to focus on "transferring" the Energy Garden concept, because the group considered it as having the most realistic potential to be implemented in Thuringia in a short to medium term.

The transfer activities continued on 14 October 2022, when FUB organised a follow-up workshop entitled 'Which elements of the Multifunctional Energy Gardens can be transferred from the Netherlands to Thuringia?' together with the Thuringian Energy and GreenTech Agency (ThEGA) in Erfurt (Thuringia). Participants included the members of the transfer team as well as policy makers and other stakeholders from Thuringia participating in the COME RES country desk including representatives from the Thuringian Ministry of Environment, Energy and Nature Conservation, local energy cooperatives, environmental NGOs, the climate protection foundation Jena-Thüringen and the foundation *Stiftung Landschaftspark Nohra*.

Based on the workshop outcomes, the transfer team co-created a 'transfer roadmap' outlining concrete steps to transfer the concept and defining concrete responsibilities. The transfer team agreed that targeted awareness-raising activities are essential to make the concept of Energy Gardens known to the public, energy cooperatives, municipalities, municipal utility companies and other relevant stakeholders. Moreover, several members of the transfer team decided to sign a Memorandum of Understanding indicating their commitment to continue the dialogue and cooperation also after the lifetime of COME RES. More information on the transfer process, the transfer visits and transfer workshops can be found on the COME RES website and the corresponding project reports.⁴

JOINT BROCHURE ON BEST PRACTICE TRANSFER WITH CONTRIBUTIONS FROM KEY STAKEHOLDERS

As one of the key outcomes of the good/best practice transfer activities, the German desk, led by the Thuringian Energy and GreenTech Agency, decided to publish a brochure informing about the Dutch concept of Energy Gardens and related multi-use approaches in the Netherlands and Thuringia. The brochure contains contributions from Dutch and Thuringian experts that belonged to the core stakeholder group of the German country desk. The brochure is going to be presented during the final COME RES conference in Brussels on 31 January 2023.

⁴ See Bastiani, M. et al. (2022). D6.2 Four capacity development and transfer workshops report, and de Bont, R. et al. (2022). D6.3 Four Best Practice Transfer Roadmaps for Learning Regions.

3.2.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

The majority of desk participants considers that Germany is still lagging behind in terms of transposing the provisions of RED II and that there are still implementation gaps, although certain improvements have been achieved after the change of the Federal government. Collective self-consumption and energy sharing represent particularly important transposition gaps.

Collective self-consumption and neighbourhood concepts (*Quartierskonzepte*) are considered by many stakeholders as important elements of any future energy strategy, also and especially with regards to their potential contributions to price stabilisation, system resilience and security of supply. However, even if self-consumption of electricity has become more attractive from a purely economic perspective after the abolition of the renewable energy surcharge on 1 July 2022, there are still several legal and administrative barriers hampering the collective use of RES based energy in the same building, multi-apartment block and neighbourhoods, including numerous obligations jointly acting self-consumers have to fulfil in their role as energy suppliers. Such regulations should be simplified. In order to facilitate collective self-consumption schemes, the current principle of personal identity (which envisages that the operator and the user of the electricity have to be the same person) should be abolished.

Moreover, desk participants see a need to reduce the administrative burden for landlord-to-tenant electricity projects (*Mieterstromprojekte*). There are many burdensome and costly energy management obligations (e.g., obligations of energy suppliers, documentation, accounting obligations) which the operators of such schemes have to fulfil, although the EEG levy has been recently removed which makes such projects financially more attractive.

Many actors represented in the German country desk see energy sharing as a key to reduce energy costs for the members of a REC and to enhance local acceptance of RE projects. For the Federal government, however, the introduction of energy sharing is apparently linked to a fundamental overhaul of the existing market design (including a reform of the levy/ surcharge system). A key concern of the government is to reach a fair allocation of system costs and avoid social imbalances. A recent study⁵ commissioned by Bündnis Bürgerenergie and carried out by the Institute for Ecological Economy Research (IÖW) concluded that energy sharing has an enormous potential. Over 90% of all households could be supplied with electricity via Energy Sharing based on RES plants (such as PV rooftop installations). IÖW estimates that private investments of about 6.5-12.8 billion EUR can be made, corresponding to 100-200 EUR per member).

The debates in the frame of the German country desk also showed that in addition to financial support there is apparently a need for accompanying measures, including the dissemination of good practices, support in the development of networks as well as assistance in the professionalisation of energy cooperatives. Intermediaries seem to be necessary providing advisory services as well as institutional

⁵ Wiesenthal et al. [IÖW] (2022) Energy Sharing: Eine Potenzialanalyse. Gemeinschaftlich Strom im Verteilnetz erzeugen und nutzen: Eine Studie zum Umsetzungsvorschlag im Rahmen von Artikel 22 der Erneuerbare-Energien-Richtlinie der EU. Gutachten im Auftrag des Bündnisses für Bürgerenergie e.V.; https://www.buendnis-buergerenergie.de/fileadmin/user_upload/downloads/Studien/Energy_Sharing_Eine_Potenzialanalyse_02052022.pdf

and technical support for citizens, local communities and municipalities. In several federal states, regional energy agencies are already assuming or may assume such functions. It would be desirable if they were equipped with more staff and resources.

There are still many bottlenecks in the area of planning and permitting procedures in the federal states for RES in general which are commonly considered lengthy and overly complex. It has been pointed out repeatedly that simplification/ streamlining of planning and permitting procedures is urgently needed, otherwise the achievement of the ambitious federal targets will become very difficult. However, there is a certain risk that simplifications and streamlining of administrative procedures might be implemented at the expense of nature conservation rules.

The poor equipment of electricity consumers with smart meters represents another bottleneck for energy communities in general and energy sharing in particular. Besides the slow smart meter rollout, digitalisation of the energy transition is generally underdeveloped (see for example the poor digitalisation of administrative procedures including permitting of projects).

Municipalities are seen as key enablers of RECs. They may provide suitable space for RES facilities operated by RECs (e.g., rooftops on municipal buildings, municipal land) or link the lease-out of municipal land/rooftops to the compliance of the respective developers with certain social criteria (e.g., financial participation of local community, orientation towards the “Common Good”). Municipalities in Thuringia and several other federal states face legal barriers if they want to engage in certain independent economic activities like energy production. This hampers their participation in renewable energy communities. There are several inspiring cases of cooperation between energy community initiatives and municipal utility companies. Such models should be promoted.

3.3. ITALY

The Italian country desk was organised by ENEA in close collaboration with Ecoazioni. It reached a large and well-balanced group of stakeholders ranging from the energy industry and services, public authorities, community energy initiatives, NGOs, environmental and RES associations as well as R&D organisations. Also, several experts for legal framework, organisational and business models or technical and IT developers were involved in the country desk events.

Table 6 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Italian Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of policy makers*
Kick-off Meeting	21.01.2021	online	Kick-off Meeting of the country desk	80	4
First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	06.05.2021	online	Sectorial analysis and Piedmont and Apulia regional cases	170	10
First Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab	28.04.2022	online	Presentation of first COME RES results; discussion of instruments for the development of RECs; presentation of good practices	165	6
Second Thematic Workshop	30.11.2022	Bergamo and online	Presentation of interim COME RES results including the stakeholder consultation; Action plan for the target region Apulia;	191	12
Second Country Desk Meeting	01.12.2022	Bergamo and online	Presentation and Validation of the Action Plan for the Apulia region.	14	4

* Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials

3.3.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off Meeting of the Italian Desk

The kick off meeting (KOM) of the Italian country desk was held on 21 January 2021. The event was organised by ENEA and ECOAZIONI. About 180 stakeholders attended the meeting. In addition to the 47 participants who committed in advance, 42 actors expressed their interest during the meeting to participate in the desk activities on a more permanent basis, reaching 89 in total. Stakeholder groups represented included: decision-makers and public administrators, electricity companies, research institutes, financial institutions, professional trade associations, and environmental and consumer associations. The number of participants shows the large interest paid to this new form of collective action for energy that can offer an opportunity of development that strengthens the involvement and cohesion of the communities involved.

Figure 23 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick-off meeting of the Italian Desk per stakeholder group

Following the welcome address of Giorgio Graditi, Director of ENEA’s Department Energy Technology and Renewable Energy Sources, the COME RES project coordinator Rosaria Di Nucci (FUB), introduced the objectives and main steps of the project followed by Elena De Luca (ENEA) that illustrated the role and functions of the country desks. The state of the art and the methods of implementation of the RECs was extensively described by the representatives of the Ministry of Economic Development (MiSE), GSE (the managing organisation of the electricity market) and the research Centre RSE. Italy is comparatively advanced in transposing the European legislation on RECs. In fact, thanks to a strong attention at the parliamentary level, an incentive system has already been established.

Elena De Luca (ENEA) explained that some interesting aspects emerged from the dialogue, such as the need for more information on the possibility of combining the incentives for RECs with the others provided for energy efficiency. In addition, some critical issues were reported at the legal level for the constitution of the RECs on the territorial dimension of the enabled subjects.

In the session dedicated to the nationwide dissemination of RECs, the processes initiated by the Piedmont and Apulia Regions were highlighted. Piedmont was the first region to implement its own legislation related to RECs while the Apulia Region is committed to encouraging the growth of this type of initiative. Furthermore, Massimo Bastiani from ECOAZIONI pointed out how this form of self-production and collective consumption can have beneficial effects on consumer awareness about environmental, economic and social repercussions that can contribute to improving the quality of life in particular in the marginal and more internal areas of the country.

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The first thematic workshop took place on 6 May 2021 and was organised in the form of an exchange of experiences between Piedmont Region (model region) and Apulia Region (target region) on common issues. The policy lab, which took place in the second part of the day, was dedicated to the transposition

and implementation of RED II at the national level.

Figure 24 - Breakdown of participants in the Thematic Workshop of the Italian Desk per stakeholder group

The first thematic workshop, entitled " Energy communities: Forms, legal models and business plans", took place on 6 May 2021, organised and coordinated by ENEA and ECOAZIONI. Its aim was to promote a stakeholder dialogue on the transposition and implementation of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) in Italy and in the different regions, and an exchange of experiences with different application models for RECs. A total of 26 speakers and in total more than 170 participants (25% female and 75% male) joined the meeting. In compliance with COVID-pandemic regulations the activities were carried out online.

The workshop was structured into three sections: the presentations about COME RES and the update on the transposition process in Italy of the RED II, a specific focus on **forms, legal models** and **business plans** developed in Piedmont and Apulia and the last part in the form of an interactive session. The workshop was moderated by Massimo Bastiani for ECOAZIONI and opened by Elena De Luca from ENEA that presented activities and preliminary results of the COME RES project. Romano Borchiellini, Energy Center Lab - Politecnico di Torino, presented the initiative "Manifesto delle Comunità Energetiche". The Manifesto proposes itself as a catalyst for the ability of different public and private stakeholders (municipalities, universities, companies, citizens) to build an integrated capacity for dialogue with national standardisation and regulatory authorities, in order to give a unified voice to the efforts to transpose European directives and to make them more attentive to the needs of public and private energy users. Matteo Caldera, Laboratorio Smart Cities and Communities of ENEA, presented the tool RECON, developed by ENEA to encourage the establishment of energy communities and which allows an initial technical and economic assessment to support the start-up of a REC. Alexia Boulanger for Envipark, illustrated the history and the state of the art of the Piedmont' experience in the RECs, explaining why it is a model for the implementation of RECs Italy. This Region is already active for a long time, with planning and institutional organisation, regional laws and regulations issued even before a national directive. At the regional level, Piedmont has set the goal of covering 10% of the territory with energy communities.

Marco Bailo, Mayor of Magliano d’Alpi, and Sergio Olivero, President of REC Scientific Committee, described their REC pilot experience in Piedmont. In particular, Olivero illustrated the business model that has been developed in Magliano d’Alpi, to enable participatory development of RECs. The case of the Apulia Region, the Italian’ target region for COME RES, was introduced by Salvatore Tomaselli, DiTNE, who described the regional legislative framework and the initiatives that are currently being implemented. Lucilla Parisi, Mayor of Roseto Valfortore, and Michele Raffa, Friendly Power S.r.l. described the path that is being pursued in the creation of the first energy community in Apulia. The energy community of Roseto Valfortore, participated by citizens, businesses and local authorities, was created with the aim of enhancing all the resources of the territory and, through targeted investments, to retain locally the benefits created by Renewable Energy Sources (RES). Creation of RECs is closely connected with the concept of energy poverty and in Italy this experience is spreading mainly in the contexts of small municipalities and inland areas of the country, as well as in large urban peripheries. For Elena Torii, UNIPOL, this type of initiative has a great potential to bring attention to consumption, for the redevelopment and conversion of public and private buildings in the marginal areas of the country.

The third part of the workshop was focused on the application of an online participatory SWOT analysis, coordinated by Virna Venerucci from ECOAZIONI. Through the SWOT, strengths and weaknesses of the REC models treated in the workshop were highlighted with the aim of revealing the similarities, deviations and elements of success between Piedmont and Apulia, which may be useful on a regional and national scale.

Figure 25– Result from the interactive session held during the Thematic Workshop of the Italian Desk

The policy lab "Scenarios for renewable energy communities" was held in the second part of the day, moderated by Elena De Luca from ENEA and introduced by Massimo Bastiani from ECOAZIONI. The introduction presented preliminary results of the COME RES project, including the findings of a legal gap assessment referring to the transposition of the RED II in the different COME RES partner countries. The work session was opened by Senator Giovanni Giroto updating the participants on the progress of the process of development of RECs in Italy, pointing out that 10 days before the law transposing the relevant European directives including RED II was approved. This enables the overcoming of the limit of 200kW and constitutes an important step for the promotion of renewable energy communities since the capacity limit represented a significant criticality for their diffusion. Davide Valenzano, Head of Regulatory Affairs Unit GSE (the so-called electricity market managing organisation), introduced the progress and the results of the consultation on collective self-consumption and community renewable energy potential in Italy. GSE places the citizen at the centre of this great energy transition to RES based systems; the role of participation and consultation is seen as fundamental. Tools and some models of specifications are available to support those communities that want to start to establish RECs.

Eleonora Riva Sanseverino, National Representative of Partnership Driving Urban Transition, highlighted the role of smart cities in the new community research programmes. Maurizio Sasso, Department of Engineering of the University of Sannio, emphasised the role of sharing economy, energy communities, internal areas and training. On the role of the small and medium enterprises as actors in energy communities, intervened Claudio G. Ferrari, President of FEDERESCO. Small and medium enterprises, represented in the event by FEDERESCO, reported the difficulty in using the financial resources made available. Indeed, less than one third of the budget available for 2020 was spent. Although existing planning tools are adequate, there are still some barriers that need to be overcome by the central government in order to establish effective rules and to streamline regulations that allow stakeholders to realise their investments in due time. There is also a lack of specific skills that should be trained. The point of view of the environmental associations was represented by Luca Iacoboni, Head of the Climate and Energy Campaign of Greenpeace Italy. This was followed by the interventions of: Mauro Annunziato, Director of ENEA Smart Energy Division on the digital platforms for the development of local economies - Perspectives for geographically marginal communities; Marco Bussone, President of National Union of Mountain Communities (UNCENM), who recalled the importance of the role of local communities in the development of initiatives; Jens Lowitzsch, European University Viadrina (Frankfurt/Oder), who illustrated the role of international cooperation in the development of RECs in Piedmont; Daniela Patrucco, Consultant for the activation of Energy Communities - Freelance Journalist Qualenergia, who underlined the role of good practices for the promotion of more conscious RECs.

A number of interventions highlighted the need for better governance that allows the fruitful use of funds available to public bodies, and that promotes the development of territories and local communities also involving small and medium-sized enterprises.

The role of science and technology was highlighted as well: concrete examples were presented on digitalisation and the use of tools that allow citizens to monitor energy exchanges and have a positive effect on reducing consumption. These tools, based on advanced technological solutions, can promote

the emergence of new forms of economy with positive social impacts, activating a network of exchange of services, in addition to the “good” energy. As pointed out by environmental and third sector associations, RECs are perceived as a democratic and "truly green" instrument.

During the debate it was emphasised that RECs represent the great change underway in the energy system, which is moving from a centralised model to a form of greater decentralisation of energy production and consumption, where the citizen becomes a responsible protagonist. The delay in the achievement of the RES-E production objectives in the NECP (gap of 40GW to reach the target for PV installed capacity) was also pointed as an opportunity for an active participation of individual citizens. In this regard, the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) will provide new resources to support RECs implementation. Indeed, it is expected a 2.2 billion EUR funding to support PV generation, corresponding to around 2.500 GWh of electricity generation per year, and a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions of about 1.5 million tons of CO₂ per year.

ACTIVITY 3: First Country Desk Meeting and Policy Lab

The event that took place on 28 April 2022, focused on the transfer of best practices. The activities to assess best practice transfer between participants, based on the experience of other COME RES partner countries, involved 165 stakeholders.

Figure 26 - Breakdown of participants in the first country desk meeting and Policy Lab per stakeholder group

The event provided an update on the progress of the project and the results achieved in the first period at an overall level, but also had a focus on the country desk. The experience of the Belgian energy cooperative EcoPower was also presented, which had been selected as a best-practice and mentoring region for Italy. The starting scenario and business model found great interest among the participants.

The event showed that Italy is progressing very well compared to the other countries involved in the COME RES project. The Italian experiences and future prospects were illustrated.

Subsequently, a discussion followed on the GECO project, whose objective is to create a large energy community by exploiting the opportunities of the area and to put together a housing area, a council housing area with an industrial area that could provide a space for photovoltaic installations. The

implication of the COVID pandemic and all the various changes in the regulations negatively affected the realisation of the GECO project. There were a series of difficulties, from the technical point of view but also from the administrative and management point of view. In this way a whole series of experiences were gathered and lessons drawn, with both local and regional institutional decision-makers.

Mr. Altobelli of Falck Renewables presented how crowdfunding can promote inclusiveness and shared a financing tool also focusing on RECs and illustrated an example of a project realised in the UK with a cooperative of citizens. The cooperative collects the contributions of its members and transfers the funding to Falck. In return, for the lifetime of the wind farm the cooperative receives a fixed portion and a share proportionate to the performance of the wind farm itself sharing part of the risk.

The second event is the co-ownership scheme where the company offered those who live near the plant, organised as a social enterprise, to become co-owners of a wind turbine. This move allows the community to participate in the revenue of the plant and to reinvest the profits in initiatives in the area in particular for energy sustainability projects. There is nothing to prevent the revenues from being used for RECs.

Further, the REC being set up in Roseto Valfortore, Apulia, the target and “learning” region of the COME RES project, was presented. The discussion focused on the first critical issues that emerged in the diagnostic phase and in the authorisation process-, but also on the objective that the Municipality of Roseto intends to pursue was presented. It is assumed that of the 4 million kWh of electricity consumed in the Municipality of Roseto Valfortore, 35% will be covered by renewable energy sources in 2023. Roseto also plans, as a mountain community, to utilise thermal energy to support its needs in winter periods. In general, there is an increasing awareness towards using the territory’s own resources and a growing wish to be sustainable.

The latest case discussed was a REC in the project phase of the Unione Montana Monti Azzurri in the Marche region. The project is aimed at finding and testing innovative solutions to address a whole series of problems that affect, above all, inland rural areas, trying also through energy communities to create new development models for the respective territories. For many years now, these inland areas have experienced negative demographic and economic trends, so the energy community can be an engine, a tool to reverse or at least slow down these processes.

Moreover, the tools that ENEA will deploy to support the strategic choices of energy communities were also presented.

During the concluding part it was highlighted that in Italy the creation of energy communities should not forget the prospects on the territory. An energy community is primarily a “Local Energy Community” that enhances the potential of the territory, which is not only energy potential but also the social potential of aggregation and management of the territory. The European legislation refers to the concept of ‘empowerment’ of citizens, thus giving them the opportunity to manage their own energy, making them aware that energy has an environmental cost more than an economic one, and making them independent and able to satisfy their own needs. This approach is particularly important and is also linked to the historical reality we are experiencing, and therefore to the scarcity of energy resources. In

the next few years, we will have to change our energy market and, above all, our energy sources, so all these actions will be crucial at the European level to drive Europe, towards a carbon-neutral economy. Projects such as COME RES are particularly interesting because the exchange of information and the circulation of models are, particularly in the start-up period, a fundamental element in ensuring that RECs exploit their potential to the fullest.

Crowdfunding has emerged as a very useful tool because it can engage and empower local communities to become key agents of change in the transition. The other important issue is that the energy community scenario is constantly growing. Over time it will be necessary to assess the capacity for integration with all the other tools available (e.g. IT) and also to understand how to manage the issue of partnerships, which is an increasingly important aspect; then there is the legal framework underlying the organisational form of communities.

The following Policy Lab was dedicated to the implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan – (NRRP) and focused on how to transpose the provisions of the RED II. The national production of renewable energy amounted to 114TW in 2018 and is expected, thanks to photovoltaics, to reach 30GW in 2030. There are clearly several measures that can be applied to reach these targets. First of all, incentives must be appropriately diversified, depending on the technology to promote or the mechanisms that one wants to incentivise. The transition is a path in the making, many technologies still need development and research to be marketable, and so it is right that these technologies should still be invested in with ad hoc instruments precisely to improve their efficiency and effectiveness and thus make them competitive. A simplification of all authorisation procedures is necessary, especially for those plants that have to undergo revamping and repowering. Fundamental are the policies that must, among other things, make available and identify areas of the territory suitable for installations.

Italy is moving quickly and after a test phase, RED II has been transposed with Law 199 of 2021. The test phase allowed to define the most suitable criteria for a correct transposition of RED II and a model of RECs suited to the configuration of the national grid. In addition to the regulatory framework, the financing instruments dedicated to RECs were presented, in particular the PNRR, which provides 2.2 million EUR for municipalities under 5.000 inhabitants as a priority. The regions will also play a role with additional instruments and priorities.

Several energy communities were presented: the case of San Giovanni, presented by Legambiente, where the REC was born to respond to a demand for mitigating energy poverty, thus a REC established by citizens with 40 families involved, with a 53KW photovoltaic plant installed on buildings and financed by the Foundation for the South.

The REC of Magliano Alpi was the first in Italy and evolved during the regulatory transition phase into a model that was replicated throughout Italy. Through collaboration agreements based on the Magliano model, RECs are being set up in Friuli Venezia Giulia (RECOCER), in municipalities in the Alpine areas, in Liguria and in Tuscany. The objectives of the agreements between these municipalities are to foster knowledge, enabling communication based on concrete experiences, i.e. the mayors talking to each

other, and it is much easier to get certain concepts across. Also fundamental is the dialogue between the administrative actors.

The event also highlighted that it is necessary to understand what the optimal technological mix is to introduce in specific territories through so called heritage and resource surveys, starting from the pilot activity that the research center RSE carried out to create the "territorial heritage map". This document takes into account geological formations, ecological networks as well as the settlement structure, i.e. how the territories changed over the years. Fundamental are also the models for activating RECs through a public driver, namely the pluralistic models that respond to social needs and arise from below, such as the San Giovanni model, and the Industry model where the promoters are industries and subjects that provide services connected to the energy system.

ACTIVITY 4: Second Thematic Workshop

The second thematic workshop was linked to a public event on Urban Transition held in Bergamo. All stakeholders from the Italian country desk were involved and the meeting reached an audience of around 200 stakeholders on urban issues and on renewables and cooperation networks. Different project presentations took place and the discussion focused on results and future synergies to improve the results at national and international level.

Figure 27 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop per stakeholder group

The thematic workshop took place in a hybrid mode, remote and in-person. Among the participants were the Mayor of Roseto Valfortore, representatives of the mayors of the inland Apulia area, representatives of Italian funding agencies working on urban issues, civil servants from different Italian and foreign cities working on the creation of energy sustainable cities with different projects. The COME RES project partners ENEA and ECOAZIONI highlighted the strategic role that the establishment of energy communities can play in advancing the share of renewables. The preliminary results achieved by COME RES were presented.

It was stressed that one of the core activities of COME RES is to facilitate cross-country and domestic transfers of at least four best practices identified within a portfolio of 21 best practices through the

creation of dedicated Transfer Teams. The key twinning/mentoring activities include the joint development of transfer roadmaps and Memoranda of Understanding, involving learning and mentoring regions.

Gilda Massa presented the Italian country desk and the meetings held, starting with the kick-off meeting in January 2021 until the final event on project results and a virtual policy roundtable.

ENEA gave a detailed presentation of the Roseto Valfortore experience, the training process, the lessons learnt from the Belgian EcoPower, and the possible insights that led to the roadmap and action plan for the Apulia Region.

ACTIVITY 5: Second Country Desk Meeting

A final country desk meeting which was restricted to a low number of stakeholders took place on 1 December 2022 to present and validate the action plan for the Apulia region starting from the experience of Roseto and continuing with the discussion of the lessons learnt. Including the COME RES partners, 14 people participated in the event.

Figure 28 - Breakdown of participants in the second Country Desk Meeting per stakeholder group

Gilda Massa opened the meeting by introducing the participants, presented the highlights of the COME RES project and delivered a presentation on the experience in Roseto Valfortore. In a past meeting, a REC Transfer Roadmap and Action Plan had been drafted with a group of core stakeholders based on the lessons learnt from Roseto Valfortore, aiming at transferring the REC Roseto Valfortore model to suitable sites in the Apulia Region. The action plan includes a regional workshop for dissemination and engagement of stakeholders, a regional workshop on a REC business model (based on the experience of ECOPOWER), a MoU and a strategic action plan among RECs and involvement in a multiservice ENEA platform for RECs (to open in 2024).

Vincenzo Raffa presented the experience of FriendlyPower, partner of the project, introduced the concept of Renewable Energy Community (REC), aimed at promoting local economic development through the valorisation of the existing resources in the territory. He highlighted the environmental, social

and economic benefits of RECs. The local authorities and founding members collected adhesions by actively promoting the REC in the area.

The REC pursues the following objectives:

- Environmental protection;
- Energy saving;
- Promoting the use of renewable energy sources;
- Local production and use of energy;
- Energy self-sufficiency;
- Fight against energy poverty.

He also described the modalities of users' participation. The revenues need to cover all the costs of the REC (i.e. start-up costs, costs of management and maintenance of the plants, rental costs, return of investment, etc.); 40% of the remaining amount is shared among all the participants, while 60% of it is assigned to members with higher consumption to facilitate the "responsible consumption". He illustrated the application to Roseto Valfortore and its characteristics: two solar plants, 90 kW total power, for a total annual energy produced of 112,500 kWh, 15 residential users, 22 municipal users, 3 commercial users. Looking at the hourly energy generation, between 11 a.m. and 3 p.m. the energy produced exceeds the energy withdrawn. Therefore, energy sharing and community benefits may increase if the consumptions are concentrated in those hours. Looking at the REC revenues, the benefits for the energy community increase according to the amount of energy shared.

Virna Venerucci (ECOAZIONI) focused her presentation on the task of identification of "Good Practice" and the Best Practice Transfer Roadmap, with the aim of transferring the good practices from other countries to the target resp. "learning" regions.

She recalled the experience of EcoPower, founded in 1991 in Flanders (Belgium) as a citizen cooperative, aimed at producing electric energy at low cost and revenue sharing, later becoming an energy supplier. The main objective of EcoPower has always been to put people together to invest in production of renewable energy and promote energy efficiency. Nowadays, EcoPower supplies green energy to Flanders and has plants installed in the whole country (Belgium). EcoPower has 60.000 members.

The transfer process is focused on: governance, legal form, activity In the energy market and business models, models of cooperation and possibilities for financial participation by local authorities.

The Mayor of Roseto Valfortore underlined the importance of the COME RES project and its positive effects in the Roseto Valfortore territory and also the great opportunity of joining the transfer workshop in Flanders (Belgium). She thanked ENEA and Friendly Power for launching the REC in Roseto, which will start soon, after some bureaucratic issues, with the installation of the solar plants. The citizen community is very much interested in the initiative. The final goal remains to become energy suppliers, starting form a citizen-based model and she confirmed the REC of Roseto has been inspired by EcoPower and they hope to reach in the future a business model aligned with EcoPower. The

representative of the mayors in Apulia inland area, expressed interest in the project and in its replicability in the territories under his administration and asked for the statutes of both Roseto and EcoPower and all the presentations.

3.3.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: The online survey

In Italy, 187 stakeholders responded to the survey and, while 33% of the respondents came from the renewable energy field, the target region Apulia was poorly represented. Over 75% of the respondents believe that RECs can play a strategic role for a sustainable urban transition. The organisational form considered most suitable by the interviewees is the energy cooperative (about 70% consider it very relevant and relevant), followed by citizen association and public-private partnership. Public authorities are considered the key actors for the creation of a REC, followed by citizens' association. The main field in which RECs are expected to have the greatest impact is for over 90% of the respondents, local power generation. Solar PV is the main technology for renewable energy production followed by storage solutions, whilst integrated and hybrid systems are in third position. The main barriers identified are lack of knowledge of the REC model and the lack of a clear / adequate legislation to enhance RECs' opportunities to sell surplus energy to the grid. Reducing administrative/ bureaucratic processes is indicated as a necessary condition, whilst specific funding for REC implementation is requested from 90% of the respondents.

INPUT TO REGIONAL ENERGY ACTION PLANS

On 10 October 2022, a first meeting with a core group of stakeholders took place in the municipality of Roseto Valfortore, located in the Apulia Region. The meeting was organised back-to-back with the second transfer workshop (in frame of Task 6.3) that focused on the REC of Roseto Valfortore, a pilot case in the Apulia learning region. During the meeting, a first discussion on the barriers and enablers for development of RECs and possible actions to overcome these barriers took place. The core group of stakeholders also discussed the organisation of a regional event (policy lab) involving both the mayors of the inland area of the Apulia Region and the Regional Councillors working on energy and environmental issues. During the meeting it became clear that municipalities and the Apulia Region need to work together to revise spatial planning documents and the constraints placed on the installation of photovoltaic panels on the territory. The participants emphasised that the concept of RECs and the benefits for the region should be presented in a concrete manner to the regional government, with real energy data to provide evidence of tangible results and benefits of RECs. The draft proposal for an action plan that resulted from this first meeting aimed at transferring the successful REC-model of Roseto Valfortore to other, suitable sites in the Apulia Region, by stimulating and promoting the REC model across the municipalities in the Apulia Region, by showcasing the good practice and sharing lessons learned, by engaging municipalities in the Apulia Region to cooperate on the development of RECs and by enabling the development of RECs through multi-service platforms and guidelines.

Later on, the action plan was presented during the second thematic workshop (see activity 4) and then further discussed and approved by a limited group of regional core stakeholders during the second country desk meeting (see activity 5).

INPUT TO GOOD/BEST PRACTICE TRANSFER

The transfer workshop focused on the enabling framework for RECs at the national and regional levels, on tools mechanisms and incentives and was carried out with a smaller group of ten people (three from the discussion municipality, four from RECs, two from an energy utility and two COME RES project partners).

The discussion addressed following issues:

- administrative processes involving RECs and the energy providers;
- EcoPower's initial business model and its improvement;
- citizen engagement on environmental issues;
- national/regional legal framework.

The workshop focused on the Apulia scenario. A discussion on challenges for RECs and for the municipality of Roseto was carried out. In particular, the participants addressed how the regional legal framework is aligned to national scenario and what, from the point of view of the Mayor and technical experts of the municipality, is needed to speed up the process of the REC development.

The utility service presented its own experience on RECs, starting from wind turbine and going through the PV installations in the Apulia region, how these technologies impact on citizens and on the social acceptance in the area.

The engagement of the citizens is needed and a first analysis starting from the project data of EcoPower was taken as a rough starting point.

MEETING WITH MAYORS OF THE SONDRIO VALTELLINA MOUNTAIN COMMUNITY

The meeting was held in Sondrio on 16 March 2022, with the participation of administrators of the Mountain Community. ENEA and ECOAZIONI presented the COME RES project results and the possibilities related to the implementation of a REC in this territory of the Region Lombardy.

Following the meeting, the Mountain Community of Valtellina di Sondrio, decided to submit a project of REC within the PNRR "Activities": Green Communities. The project has been funded recently.

PERUGIA (IT) CONFERENCE "ARCHITETTI IN MOVIMENTO DALL'UMBRIA ALL'EUROPA VERSO UN NUOVO BAUHAUS"

The meeting represented an opportunity for discussion with architects from the Umbria region and all over Italy on the subject of Energy Transition and RECs. Architects and engineers are the privileged technicians for the implementation of RECs and represent the points of connection with the municipalities. This discussion took place within an Erasmus+ project dedicated to the higher education of professionals. The work agenda rich and full of content has made it possible to open new frontiers for

the creation of RECs, starting from the COME RES experience. The COME RES Coordinator Maria Rosaria Di Nucci reported on the comparative analysis of the implementation of the RED II in the EU and the open challenges.

The event was organised by the Order of Architects of Perugia, Ecoazioni, National Council of the Architect, and the Umbra Foundation for Architecture. The event was held face-to-face and disseminated online, with over 200 views.

3.3.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

In Italy, RED II has played a catalyst role for the development of community energy initiatives. According to the Renewable Energy Report 2022 by the Milan Polytechnic, presented on 17 May 2022, there are currently 26 active communities in Italy, all based on PV systems with an average power between 15 and 40 kW. As of 2 May 2022, the Energy Service Manager (GSE) received 37 applications to access incentives (updated data), including 13 Renewable Energy Communities and 24 Self-Consumption Groups. More than half of the applications come from Lombardy (6), Piedmont (7) and Veneto (9). The transposition of REC definition, rights, obligations and activities can be regarded as relatively advanced. Italy has implemented several measures for collective self-consumption and energy communities. Nonetheless, there are still transposition gaps and shortcomings. The establishment of RECs faces several barriers and restrictions and fights against red tape.

Regions have played a fundamental role to spread RECs; to date 13 regions have already established a normative framework.

The transfer initiated by COME RES between the learning region Apulia and the mentors of ECOPOWER in Belgium has represented an important impulse for the establishment of the REC of Roseto Valfortore. This fact has been acknowledged on several occasions by the mayor of the small town who manifested Roseto's aim of becoming an energy supplier, starting from a business model aligned with ECOPOWER.

3.4. LATVIA

The Latvian country desk was coordinated by LEIF in cooperation with IPE and did not limit its focus on selected target regions but considered the whole of Latvia. Latvia's country desk has been established accordingly with a core group of 15 national and local stakeholders, which has been widened up to 30-40 stakeholders invited to the thematic workshops and policy labs. The core partners of the country desk were ministries (Ministry of Economics; Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development), planning regions, energy agencies, municipalities, the Latvian Association of Local Governments, as well as local partnerships and NGOs.

The country desk supported the transposition and implementation of the provisions of the RED II and IEMD with input to the drafts of the national regulations and policy recommendations. The RED II and IEMD provisions regarding energy communities are included in the Amendments to the Energy Law and Amendments to the Electricity Market Law respectively, both adopted by the Saeima (Parliament) on 14 July, 2022, coming into force on 01.01.2023. However, the governmental regulations detailing the general framework were under elaboration for most of the time the country desk was active. Thus, the Latvian country desk activities were in due time and the desk had an excellent possibility to provide input for the draft governmental regulations and for the development of financial support instruments promoting the recognition of RECs in national renewable energy investment co-financing programmes.

Table 7 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Latvian Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Makers*
Kick-off meeting	27.01.2021	Online	RECs in Latvia: Introduction of the project	19	3
First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	17.06.2021	Online	Transposition of RED II and IEMD Directives and challenges of legal framework development in Latvia Development perspectives of RECs in Latvia Status quo of the COME RES project	33	7
Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	16.02.2022	Online	COME RES Good Practices Portfolio. (Pilot) practices in Latvia and Italy (Thematic Workshop). Drivers and barriers for RECs in Latvia, particularly the role of municipalities (Policy Lab)	37	5
Latvia Country Desk First follow-up meeting	06.10.2022	Riga, in presence	Key aspects of building RECs in Latvia, on-going support activities. Overall approach and lesson-drawing based on	28	4

			the Italian best practice case (Magliano Alpi)		
Latvia Country Desk second follow-up meeting and Policy Lab	24.11.2022	Riga, in presence	<p>Key results and outcomes of COME RES (overall)</p> <p>Energy Community Platform: How can it support RECs?</p> <p>Discussion on how to apply energy sharing in Latvia.</p> <p>Comparative assessment of enabling frameworks for RECs in COME RES partner countries.</p> <p>Discussion of interim country-specific policy lessons and recommendations.</p>	23	3

** Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials*

3.4.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

To provide valuable input for an enabling framework for RECs and viable REC models, the Latvian country desk organised solution-oriented stakeholder dialogues, disseminated the COME RES results and promoted their adaptation in Latvia. The meetings of the desk served as informal dialogue forums where, in addition to the presentation of the COME RES project results, Latvia’s topical issues such as barriers and drivers, policies and opportunities for the development of RECs have been regularly discussed.

The high interest in the desk activities by the officials of the Ministry of Economics has been a key prerequisite for the country desk’s success. But the high interest of other stakeholders in desk meetings and project results has to be highlighted as well. The largest share of the stakeholders attended all desk events and actively participated in discussions. Furthermore, the country desk meetings helped establishing informal cooperation between stakeholders, resulting in the planning of common activities. For example, Riga’s Energy Agency (REA), as the national contact point of the EU Energy Communities Repository invited the Latvian COME RES partners to a meeting about energy communities. In its turn, the Latvian Rural Forum invited the IPE representative to participate and disseminate COME RES results in the events of the Latvian LEADER groups.

The desk events including the policy labs provided valuable input to the creation of a national legislative framework. The responsible ministerial official in the Ministry of Economics has regularly presented the latest draft legal documents referring to RECs and invited the desk participants to comment them and submit their opinions.

Also, COME RES partners from other countries were regularly invited to join the desk activities, particularly INEGI, ENEA, FUB and REScoop.eu provided presentations within different desk activities during the whole course of the COME RES project.

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off Meeting of the Latvian Desk

The kick-off meeting was organised by LEIF and IPE on January 27, 2021. The purpose of the kick-off meeting was multi-fold:

- to present the COME RES project – objectives, work packages and tasks, planned key deliverables and results achieved so far;
- to initiate the first discussion regarding provisions of the renewable energy community’s legal framework, based on the Draft of the Amendments to the Law on Energy;
- to initiate the first discussion regarding definition and interpretation of key criteria defined by RED II for REC in Latvia;
- to present the citizens (flat owners of apartment buildings) co-operation examples for common solar PV technologies at Mārupe municipality, and, based on this experience, to draw and conclude on the lessons and challenges relevant for the RECs development in Latvia;
- to elicit possible topics of the thematic workshops for 2021 and to plan further steps.

The core group of stakeholders was invited to participate in the event. In total, the meeting gathered 19 stakeholders and markets actors, including representatives from the municipalities, regional planning regions and different ministries. 45% of the attendees were female.

The date of the kick-of meeting coincided with the open public discussion on the Draft Amendments to the Latvian Law on Energy. Thus, the responsible person of the Ministry of Economics could use the kick-off meeting also as a platform to activate the discussion among stakeholders interested in REC development.

Figure 29 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick off meeting of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group

The kick-off meeting was opened by Aija Zučika from LEIF, who introduced the COME RES project objectives, work packages, tasks and expected results, and the implementation time frame. Ivars Kudreņickis from IPE presented “The European legal framework for energy communities” and the

representative of the Ministry of Economics, E. Cilinskis, continued with a presentation titled “Transposition of the provisions of the RED II Directive in Latvia: planned changes in the legal framework and the planned timetable for transposition”. I. Francis from the Riga planning region presented the project “Co-creation and co-financing of Community renewable energy projects: Experience and lessons in Mārupe municipality”. Afterwards, an active discussion followed on the legal forms of REC. The discussion was preceded by the presentation of the representative of IPE on the options for legal forms for REC.

The main findings can be summarised as follows:

- The kick-off meeting revealed the critical challenges for REC development in Latvia and, at the same time, marked a range of important suggestions how to meet them.
- The participants noted other energy communities’ projects in which they participate. COME RES partners from Latvia will look for mutually beneficial cooperation. For instance, the Zemgale Region Energy Agency currently participates in the project strengthening energy communities as an instrument to reduce energy poverty (H2020 project POWERPOOR). The Zemgale Planning Region envisages the implementation of renewable energy communities in the wider frame of citizens’ cooperation and community’s development in the region.
- On behalf of the COME RES team, Aija Zučika (LEIF) thanked the participants for their active participation, especially the representatives of the Ministry of Economics and Riga Planning Region and Mārupe municipality, and expressed her strong conviction about a future fruitful cooperation in the frame of COME RES and about the participants’ contribution to the success of the project.
- The representative of the Ministry of Economics encouraged all participants to provide comments and proposals for the Draft Amendments to the Law on Energy.

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The first thematic workshop and policy lab of the Latvian desk was organised by LEIF and IPE on 17 June 2021.

The purpose of the combined event was manifold:

- In the first part (policy lab) the event took a closer look at the on-going transposition of RED II and IEMD in Latvia and the challenges of developing a proper legal framework for RECs. The policy lab served as an interface between COME RES and the actual policy formulation process in Latvia and facilitated a policy dialogue with policy makers.
- The second part of the event dealt with the REC potential in Latvia and the challenges on how to unlock this potential to contribute in meeting the national renewable energy targets.

An extended group of stakeholders was invited to participate in the event. In total, 33 participants joined the event, including representatives from municipalities, regional planning regions and different ministries. 40% of the attendees were female.

Figure 30 - Breakdown of participants in the first thematic workshop and policy lab of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group

Aija Zučika (LEIF) opened the meeting and presented the COME RES project’s advancements.

The first part of the event was dedicated to the policy lab. E. Cilinskis, from the Ministry of Economics, presented “Renewable Energy Communities: Draft Amendments to Energy Law (Transposition of RED II), current state and expected implementation“. This was followed by a guest presentation by COME RES project partner Isabel Azevedo (INEGI) entitled “Legal framework for REC in Portugal and first practices of RECs implementation“. L. Rozentale, Ministry of Economics, presented “Planned Amendments to Electricity Market Law concerning energy communities (transposition of RED II and IEMD)“. Afterwards, an interactive discussion moderated by COME RES project partners took place.

The second part focused on the development perspectives for RECs in Latvia. Energy expert J. Ozoliņš presented “Step-by-step development practice of solar PV project: lessons and challenges relevant for RECs” and Ivars Kudreņickis (IPE) outlined the REC potential in Latvia and their prospective contribution in meeting the national renewable energy targets, as a result of the respective assessment performed in the context of the COME RES project. A moderated discussion took place to conclude this part of the event.

The main highlights of the event can be summarised as follows:

- The exchange of experiences with INEGI provided a basis of comparison of the legal implementation process and allowed to learn more on the pilot projects. This was a fruitful addition to the Latvian experience. The focused online comments by Michael Krug (Freie Universität Berlin) allowed to link the workshop discussions with the ongoing tasks of the COME RES project.
- The event revealed and discussed several critical challenges for RECs development in Latvia and, at the same time, marked a range of important suggestions to meet them.
- The responsible official in the Ministry of Economics showed interest in the COME RES REC potential assessments and encouraged the participants to provide proposals for the Draft Amendments to the Law on Energy and to the Electricity Market Law.

- It was planned for the autumn event of the Latvian desk to discuss the role of municipalities in organising RECs and their perspectives on the participation in RECs. Also, the results of COME RES Work Package 4 – organisational and legal forms and business models – will be presented and discussed, as far as possible.
- Currently, the use of PV by RECs looks more promising compared to other RES technologies due to various factors (easier installation, lower available installation capacity, etc.). Additionally, there is a solar PV support programme envisaged by the National Development Programme 2021-2027 whose beneficiaries might be RECs as well. On the basis of these two factors, the official of the Ministry of Economics noted that RECs based on solar PV are the most probable choice.

ACTIVITY 3: Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The combined second thematic workshop and policy lab was held online on 16 February 2022. In total, 34 participants registered for the online event with 15 (40.5%) female and 22 (59.5%) male participants. There were 12 (32.4%) national level stakeholders, and 25 (67.6%) regional and local stakeholders. In addition, three representatives of the COME RES partners (IPE and LEIF) participated.

Among the stakeholders, officials of the Ministry of Economics and the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development, advisers of the Latvian Association of Local Governments, and a member of the national Parliament were present. The regional level was represented by the Riga Planning Region, the Zemgale Planning Region, and the Zemgale Regional Energy Agency. Representatives of the Riga Energy Agency, two other cities and eight local municipalities (*novadi*), several local initiatives and LEADER groups, as well as a range of other stakeholders participated in the event.

Figure 31 – Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group

Starting the meeting, Aija Zučika (LEIF) introduced the COME RES project, its structure, overall results achieved so far and its objectives. Its main goal was to support the transposition of the RED II provisions related to RECs and to promote the establishment of an enabling framework for RECs. Due to the

ongoing policy process, the Latvian COME RES activities were in due time and had a good possibility to provide input for the ongoing transposition of the RED II, particularly regarding an operational definition of RECs and proper implementation.

The thematic workshop included three presentations followed by an interactive discussion.

The first presentation by Ivars Kudreņickis (IPE) introduced the Good Practice Portfolio of RECs (COME RES Deliverable 5.2) and emphasised the diversity of the models. The six most relevant practices for Latvia had been selected for a more detailed insight, taking into account the following considerations: (1) contextual aspects, (2) REC technological and business aspects, (3) stakeholders cooperation aspects, (4) membership/geographical coverage. Furthermore, the potential of the good practice cases for the adaptation and transfer to Latvia was discussed shortly.

The second presentation by I. Francis (Riga Planning Region) provided insights in the implementation of the first two pilot projects of apartment building scale energy communities (rooftop solar technologies) in Latvia (in Jaunmārupe, Mārupe local municipality, 2018-2020). Particularly, it dealt with the role of co-operation between the planning region, the local government and the homeowners' associations. The implementation of the pilot projects had been strengthened by both the local government of Mārupe, organising the collaboration of all parties, and the involvement of highly qualified energy sector experts and professional NGOs as advisers. These pilot projects also highlighted the role of local leaders of the homeowners' associations. The concept of an energy community is now actively disseminated during the annual Green Energy Week of the Mārupe municipality.

As an example for the development of RECs in other COME-RES countries, G. D'Agosta (ENEA) shared the Italian experience in the third presentation. This presentation demonstrated in a detailed manner the process of developing a legislative framework for RECs in Italy and drew important conclusions. Especially the essential role of energy sharing for RECs was highlighted. The presentation also addressed the transition from the previous legal framework (experimental phase) which brought a number of restrictions for RECs (e.g., a capacity limit of 200 kW and certain technical restrictions requiring connection of REC members to the same building or medium to low voltage cabin) which only allowed the creation of very small, localised RECs, to the new and more flexible legal framework which allowed the option for larger scale RECs where the members have to be connected to the same high/medium voltage cabin.

The policy lab which was held back-to-back to the thematic workshop aimed to provide non-biased information to stakeholders and critically assess the perspectives of the development of RECs in Latvia. In particular, it dealt with drivers and barriers for REC-development in Latvia and the possible role of local municipalities through support of and participation in local RECs. Among others, the draft results of COME RES Deliverable 2.3 on barriers and drivers for RECs were presented for Latvia.

To lead the policy related discussion, the senior advisor, M. Pūkis, of the Latvian Association of Local Governments was invited. During the session, it was underlined that the legal framework for municipalities (municipal law) allows for enough flexibility for municipalities to participate in RECs, taking into account the variety of REC legal forms and business models.

The policy lab included also a discussion on the general system for REC-specific financial support. Particularly, the following aspects of this discussion should be highlighted: the upfront cost of REC projects, ways to ensure long-term economic viability of REC, and dedicated financial support instruments for the development of REC.

There is need to develop an effective and targeted advice system for REC establishment and development. Advisory services should be tailored to the needs of particular groups of stakeholders – potential participants of REC (landowners, SMEs, etc.).

As the general willingness of citizens to engage in collective energy actions is rather low in Latvia, a focused communication is crucial. But at the same time, there are active people and several initiatives of citizens who would like to take part in joint energy projects. Thus, especially examples of foreign good practices are needed – there are still too few success stories in Latvia. For example, multi-apartment buildings have a significant potential to become important sites for REC projects. Participation of the municipality can serve as a consolidating force for RECs - the event revealed that the involvement and leadership of local government is one of the critical challenges for RECs development in Latvia and, at the same time, marked a range of important clues to meet this. In this sense, coordinated co-operation between national, regional and local authorities and the compatibility of municipal law with the variety of different REC models are of key importance.

ACTIVITY 4: First Country Desk Follow-up Meeting

The first follow-up meeting of the Latvian country desk was held in Riga, on 6 October 2022. 28 participants attended the event (including COME RES partners - LEIF and IPE representatives). There were 16 (57%) national level stakeholders, and 12 (43%) regional and local stakeholders. 12 (43%) of them were female and 16 (57%) male participants.

Among the participants were high level policy makers, e.g., officials of the Ministry of Economics and the State Construction Control Bureau of Latvia (authority responsible for the registration of energy communities). Other important stakeholders include the adviser of the Latvian Association of Local and Regional Governments, Distribution System Operator (DSO), Latvian Rural Forum, Riga City Energy Agency, experts of the Riga Technical University, representatives of different municipalities and others.

Figure 32 - Breakdown of participants in the first follow-up meeting of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group

The event discussed a large range of key aspects of REC establishment and development in Latvia. Three presentations were held, each followed by an interactive discussion. The meeting was concluded by a non-formal exchange for networking.

One of the objectives of the meeting was to serve to connect the lessons learned from the COME RES best practice transfer activities (here: transfer of the concept of the Energy City Hall REC-1 in the municipality of Magliano Alpi, Piedmont region, Italy) with the practical activities that still need to be carried out to promote RECs in Latvia. Finally, the goal was to validate the corresponding short-term action plan.

In the first presentation, S. Olivero, President of the Scientific Committee of the REC of Magliano Alpi and L. Barbero, the coordinator of GoCER⁶ introduced the first municipality-driven REC example of Magliano Alpi. They explained the theoretical phases of REC development, as envisaged by the „Manifesto of the REC” promoted by the Energy Center, Politecnico di Torino, on this practical example and gave an outlook of the process of spreading the practice over Italy. The presentation demonstrated the important role of municipalities and the need for multiple partnerships for the development of the REC, based on which the local sustainable development and synergies with the local socio-economic system and combating energy poverty are catalysed.

In the second presentation by V. Ratniks (Riga City Energy Agency), the agency’s point of view regarding the role of RECs in Latvia was presented: the promotion of society involvement, providing wider utilisation of renewable energy sources, cheaper, green and secure energy, support for vulnerable households, possibility to widen social tasks performed by the municipalities. REA serves as Latvia’s contact point for the EU Energy Communities Repository and provides informative support for interested parties.

⁶ “Gruppo Operativo Comunita Energetische Rinnovabili” (Community Operational Group).

The third presentation, by R.Lagzdiņš (IPE/RTU), dealt with an economic performance evaluation model, currently designed for small-scale RECs, which includes active and passive renewables self-consumers. The audience was introduced to the algorithm of the model and its modelling results, which show the impact of different rates of the distribution system services tariff's reduction on the economic indicators of RECs operation.

Short-term actions to be taken to promote RECs in Latvia were presented by IPE/LEIF, the Latvian Rural Forum, Riga City Energy Agency and the Ministry of Economics. They will focus on five directions:

- input for the finalisation of the REC legislative framework (Cabinet of Ministers regulations),
- promoting RECs' interest in solar PV investment co-financing programme by ERDF (Latvia's EU Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027),
- continuation of the development of the presented Economic performance evaluation model to demonstrate the necessary pre-requisites for the economic viability of the REC,
- promoting development of RECs in rural areas by the activities of Latvia's Rural Forum and
- Riga City Energy Agency assists interested parties to submit a Technical Assistance Application under the EU Energy Communities Repository.

ACTIVITY 5: Second Country Desk Follow-up Meeting and Policy Lab

The second follow-up meeting of Latvia's country desk including a policy lab was held in Riga on 24 November 2022. This was the final meeting of the desk with 23 participants, of which 9 (39%) female and 14 (61%) male, in addition to the moderator. There were 11 national level stakeholders, and 12 regional and local stakeholders.

Among the participating stakeholders were officials of the Ministry of Economics, the adviser of the Latvian Association of Local and Regional Governments, experts from the DSO, the Latvian Rural Forum, Riga City Energy Agency, Zemgale Region Energy Agency, several municipalities and others.

Figure 33 - Breakdown of participants in the second follow-up meeting of the Latvian Country Desk per stakeholder group

The COME RES project was presented by LEIF and IPE, with participation of the COME RES coordinator/partner FUB (in presence) and COME RES partner REScoop.eu (online).

The objective of the event was to present the main results and outcomes of the COME RES project, such as key outcomes and results of the Comparative assessment of enabling frameworks and support scheme designs for RECs, and to discuss how to apply energy sharing in Latvia, taking into account the experience of other countries and the existing legal framework for RECs in Latvia. In the policy lab, participants then discussed policy lessons and recommendations on a national level.

As the COME RES project entered its final phase, the first part of the meeting underlined the main achievements of the COME RES. Aija Zučika (LEIF) summarised the COME RES key deliverables and related Policy briefs and Fact Sheets with their objectives and main contents. She also referred to the Italian-Latvian transfer activities carried out in 2022. Ivars Kudreņickis (IPE) gave a short presentation regarding the key results of the dedicated stakeholder online consultation⁷. He also presented the findings of the COME RES REC potential assessment in Latvia⁸, underlining its key assumptions and results. Finally, Aija Zučika gave an outlook of the project's final stage with the upcoming policy recommendations and COME RES' final event in Brussels, 31 January 2023.

The second part included six presentations, each followed by an interactive discussion: four presentations were provided by Latvian stakeholders and two presentations by COME RES partners FUB and REScoop.eu (see above).

The first presentation by E. Cilinskis (Ministry of Economics) informed about the current state of the draft governmental regulation regarding the requirements for energy communities and their registration. The ministerial official invited all participants to submit their opinions/proposals for this draft. He underlined that the Ministry had started to develop the governmental regulations in accordance with the Electricity Market Law, which will regulate the REC operation in the electricity sector including issues regarding electricity sharing. He also presented the current state of the envisaged REC support programmes and participants of the meeting were invited to submit their proposals regarding the formulation of the particular priority direction of the Modernisation Fund to advocate the interests of RECs.

The second presentation, by E. Matulis from the DSO SJ „Sadales tīkls”, covered the main steps to be taken by active consumers, including RECs, in the installation of micro-generation equipment, the requirements for connecting this equipment to the grid and their operation in parallel with the grid. The audience was introduced to the current procedure for the accounting for the renewable electricity produced by active users.

To learn from other projects promoting energy communities in Latvia, two further presentations were included:

⁷ COME RES Deliverable 3.4 “Consultation Series of the Eight country desks. Summary Report”.

⁸ COME RES Deliverable 2.2 “Assessment Report of Potentials for RES Community Energy in the Target Regions”

- PowerPoor⁹ project activities and lessons in Latvia (third presentation, by E. Ērmanis, Zemgale Regional Energy Agency);
- Latvian Rural Forum project activities (fourth presentation by I. Ašmane).

Power Poor develops support schemes for energy poor citizens and encourages the use of alternative collective financing instruments, such as energy communities, energy cooperatives etc., as well as crowd funding. The project also provides advising systems. Project implementation in Latvia shows the necessity for education about the concept of energy communities and operational principles.

In its turn, in Q4 2022, Latvia's Rural Forum performed a feasibility study, financed by the Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt (DBU), to identify at least two pilot areas for the first rural RECs in Latvia through dialogues with parties interested in RECs – such as municipalities, local communities (particularly LEADER groups), homeowners/homeowners' associations, local residents, etc. Thus, the feasibility study serves as a basis for preparing a future full-scale project of the REC.

After a break, the meeting was continued by the COME RES partner presentations. Michael Krug (FUB), illustrated key outcomes and main conclusions of the comparative assessment of the enabling frameworks and support scheme designs for RECs¹⁰. He also shortly illustrated the lessons learned from the Dutch-German transfer activities, which aim to initiate a transfer of the best practice case of "Multi-functional Energy Gardens" from the Netherlands to Thuringia (Germany). This is a particularly important topic, as the interest for large scale ground mounted solar PV parks is constantly growing in Latvia as well.

Subsequently, Stavroula Pappa (REScoop.eu) presented the key features of the new energy community platform (<https://energycommunityplatform.eu/>) developed by REScoop.eu together with COME RES and other projects. She underlined that the Sustainability Scoreboard for RECs, developed by COME RES, will be integrated in the platform in the final phase of the project.

The meeting was followed by the policy lab. First, the participants discussed policy lessons and recommendations for Latvia resulting both from of the event's presentations and the overall COME RES results. The discussion provided the input for the final recommendations within the Deliverable 7.3, to be developed in the COME RES final stage.

Moreover, a governmental official invited the audience to provide input for drafting the governmental regulations on energy communities. Best practices from COME RES countries could be a relevant source illustrating how to provide an enabling framework and develop and manage energy communities in the most effective way. Concrete (quantitative) national goals of the establishment of energy community should be set.

⁹ PowerPoor ("Empowering Energy Poor Citizens through Joint Energy Initiatives") is the CSA (coordination and support action) project of Horizon 2020 programme, ongoing in September 2020 – August 2023. Latvian partner – Zemgale Region Energy Agency.

¹⁰ COME RES Deliverable 7.1 "Comparative Assessment of Enabling Framework for RECs and Support Scheme Designs"

Figure 34 - Image of the second follow-up meeting. Copyright: A. Zučika

3.4.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: The Online Survey

The invitation to participate in the online survey was sent by LEIF and IPE to a list of 105 Latvian stakeholders, of which 45 stakeholders responded. The spectrum of respondents was rather balanced with a certain preponderance of local public authorities, NGOs and networks, and national and regional public authorities.

The survey covered, inter alia, perceptions of the role of RECs in the energy transition, relevant legal forms, promising technologies and fields of REC activities, measures needed for scaling up REC development. At the time of the survey the general legal framework for energy communities in Latvia had not been finally adopted¹¹, interpreting the results of the survey this aspect has been taken into account as well.

In Latvia, respondents highlighted that RECs will play a highly important role in the energy transition towards a low-carbon society. Three answers regarding the positive contribution of REC dominate: (i) ensuring public acceptance for energy transition, (ii) ensuring a smart and flexible energy system, (iii) ensuring sufficient renewable energy production. If summing up the answer's options – “agree” and “highly agree”, the share of positive answers for each of the noted above REC contribution is rather similar, i.e. more than 80%.

Regarding the most relevant legal form for RECs, the Latvian stakeholders do not assign a dominating preference to any of the forms. Latvian stakeholders consider a variety of legal forms. The highest

¹¹ Amendments to Energy Law and Amendments to Electricity Market Law have been adopted by Saeima (Parliament) on 14 July 2022.

preference (if summing answers “agree” and “highly agree”) is given to the associations, housing associations and energy cooperatives.

Further, respondents in Latvia considered electricity generation as the most promising field of activity for RECs (more than 90% of respondents, if summing answers “high important” and “important”). In accordance with this, solar PV is considered as the most relevant technology. In its turn, onshore wind has been considered as relevant by around a half of respondents. Such fields of REC activities as heat generation and activities in commercial and residential buildings significantly lag behind, by receiving around 60% positive answers.

Regarding the aspects which are most need to facilitate the development of REC, the four most important aspects, selected by Latvian stakeholders, are: (i) regulation that allow electricity sharing, (ii) access to adequate information for REC interested stakeholders, (iii) support to local authorities concerning regulatory issues and opportunities for direct participation in RECs, (iv) national financial support schemes for RECs.

In general, the results of the survey support the findings of the Latvian country desk activities.

INPUT TO GOOD/BEST PRACTICE TRANSFER

The good practice cases elaborated within Deliverable 5.2 were discussed during the thematic workshop on the 6 February 2022. The Latvian transfer case was selected based on the respective workshop discussions.

The Latvian Transfer Team has been composed of eight stakeholders and the two Latvian COME RES partners – IPE and LEIF. The Transfer Visit took place from 27-30 June 2022. The transfer team included national, regional and municipal policy makers and the citizens’ community initiatives in order to include all perspectives that are needed for a successful transfer of the best-practice.

The national policy level was represented by the Ministry of Economics and the Regulator (the Public Utilities Commission), the regional level by the Riga Planning Region and the municipal level by the Riga City Energy Agency and a municipality (*novads*). Civil society and the local level were represented by two NGOs/citizen initiatives, namely Zaļā Brīvība (“Green Liberty”) as well as the Latvian Rural Forum as the national-wide umbrella organisation of local initiatives (such as LEADER groups), actively promoting the concept of RECs in Latvia and studying the potential impact of RECs on the power grid.

Before the transfer visit, the in-depth assessment of the respective showcase of the REC of Magliano Alpi (as provided by Deliverable 5.3) had been translated into Latvian and distributed to the transfer team. After the visit, specific information obtained during the transfer visit was added to the case description and made publicly available on the LEIF-website.

From Italy, Sergio Olivero, President of the Scientific Committee of the REC of Magliano Alpi; Luca Barbero, Coordinator of GoCER and Gilda Massa from ENEA participated (virtually) in the transfer workshop which was held back-to-back with the Latvian country desk meeting on 6 October 2022. They presented the development of RECs in Italy and their contribution for sustainable local development.

The Transfer Workshop followed the ‘dynamic learning lab methodology’. Prior to the Transfer Workshop, LEIF and IPE had carried out several online meetings to develop a list of questions for the workshop. In particular, one online meeting with the group moderators was held to explain in detail the overall methodology and procedures to be performed within the Transfer Workshop. During the Transfer Workshop, the Italian experts gave an online presentation, followed by a brief Q&A session. Afterwards the meeting continued in presence, where key issues have been discussed by the participants in two separate moderated groups. At the end of the Transfer Workshop, the group work results were presented. During the workshop the general motivating factors and the (pre)conditions for the development of municipality-driven RECs in Latvia were identified and discussed. Based on the fruitful discussions, a roadmap in the form of the short-term plan of actions was developed. In general, the example of the “Energy City Hall REC-1” was regarded as transferable in principle especially because of the transferability of important elements of the given Italian best-practice.

INPUT FOR LEGISLATIVE DEVELOPMENT

The legislative framework for energy communities has been adopted on 14 July 2022 by the respective amendments to the Energy Law. Selected results of COME RES are explicitly referred to in the annotations of the amendments to the Energy Law:

- Energy communities’ potential in Latvia – selected material in Latvian has been prepared based on COME RES Deliverable 2.2 (methodology and Latvian evaluation),
- Synthesis report of drivers and barriers for RECs (COME RES Deliverable 2.3) with focus on the results in Latvia.

During the public consultation phase, IPE has submitted a proposal for the amendments to Energy Law. During the parliamentary process, IPE experts were regularly invited and participated in the meetings of the responsible parliamentary commission (Economics, Agrarian, Environmental and Regional Policy Commission).

There is on-going communication with the Ministry of Economics within the process of the elaboration of the governmental regulation specifying the legislative framework for RECs.

ACTIVE COMMUNICATION OF THE TRANSFER CASE EXPERIENCE

The article: “Best Practice in Italy. Renewable Energy Community - Energy City Hall 1” was published in Latvian both in the national newspaper – Latvijas vīze (37.000 subscribers for hard copies) and three regional newspapers – Bauskas dzīve, Kurzemnieks and Brīvā Daugava (total of 36.000 subscribers for hard copies).

ACTIVE DISSEMINATION OF COME RES GOOD PRACTICES

Presentations on the good practices of RECs gathered by the COME RES project were given by Ivars Kudrenickis (IPE) at the:

- Vidzeme Region Innovation Week “SYMBIOSIS for development and innovation”, 21 February 2022 (liaising with the EU Interreg Estonia-Latvia cross-border cooperation programme’s project SMART LIVING),
- Annual event (workshop) on Territorial and Spatial Development Planning, joining leading Latvian professionals in the field and organised by the Faculty of Geography and Earth Sciences, University of Latvia, 18 March 2022,
- Publication of short communications, in Latvian, on COME RES good practices in the Materials of the Faculty, submitted 11 March, 2022¹²,
- Three presentations for the M.Sc. students of the Faculty of Geography and Earth Sciences, University of Latvia, 2022,
- Presentation at the Latvian Rural Forum - Autumn Event 2022 - of Latvia’s LEADER groups in Ape parish, Smiltene Municipality, 10 November 2022 in presence, as well as at the online webinar for Latvia’s LEADER groups, organised by Latvian Rural Forum, 14 December 2022.

3.4.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

Latvia’s country desk has proved itself as the informal meeting place for stakeholders interested in REC development in Latvia. The country desk activities stimulated an exchange of ideas on how energy communities should look like in Latvia, which primary stakeholders should be involved, and how their creation and development can be successfully supported.

The desk events promoted a common perspective on REC development and helped to better understand barriers and driving factors.

Stakeholders from all levels – national, regional, local - were represented in the country desk events. Especially through active involvement of the officials of the Ministry of Economy, participants of the desk events had the opportunity to regularly discuss draft legal documents and prepare proposals for their improvement. Thus, desk activities provided valuable input for national legislative developments.

One of the most important topics discussed during the desk events was how to ensure economic viability of RECs. A financial support scheme should be created as an instrument to encourage the establishment and management of energy communities. The financial support should be elaborated and launched together with an information campaign and provide the necessary technical expertise. Hence, not only financial support is needed, but also support in all stages of REC creation and operation.

The role of municipalities in RECs was regularly discussed during the desk events and raised particular interest among the local authorities joining the events.

A significant part of national desk meetings was dedicated to the information exchange on best practices in COME RES countries and served as a source of inspiration to promote REC development in Latvia.

¹² Available at <https://conferences.lu.lv/event/58/attachments/20/406/Kopsavilkumi%20Abstracts%202022%20LU%20TAP.pdf>, pages 28-29.

The importance of good practices for Latvia is also shown by the above-mentioned invitations to give presentations at important events in Latvia, such as the Vidzeme Innovation Week and meetings of representatives of Latvian LEADER groups. Based on the Transfer Team for the Italian best practice transfer, a WhatsApp-group was created to enable an ongoing discussion for Latvian stakeholders.

The cooperation with the Riga City Energy Agency and the Latvian Rural Forum - both national contact points for the EU Energy Communities Repository and Rural Energy Communities Advisory Hub respectively - established during the country desk meetings, deserves special emphasis.

3.5. NORWAY

The Norwegian desk consists of a wide variety of institutions and sectors and spans over a variety geographical area in Norway, including Svalbard. The Norwegian country desk was organised by CICERO – Centre for International Climate Research in close collaboration with the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE) and included important stakeholders from the energy sector (grid and power companies, energy related tech companies), local authorities, civil society and interest organisations and small and medium enterprises within different sectors across Norway.

Table 8 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Norwegian Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Maker
Kick-off meeting	14.01.21	Online	Information about COME RES + CICEROs and NVEs role in the project.	33	-
First Thematic Workshop and first Policy Lab	02.06.21	Online	REC in Norway: Opportunities and challenges	74	7
First Country Desk Meeting	26.01.22	Online	Input to proposed regulatory changes	32	-
Second Thematic Workshop	21.09.22	Hybrid	Local energy communities: Opportunities in the age of the energy crisis	44	-
Second Policy roundtable	24.10.2022	NVE/online	Dissemination of research findings on drivers and barriers for RECs in Norway and dialogue concerning the role renewable energy communities can play in today's Norwegian energy context	7	-
Second Country Desk Meeting	16.11.22	Hybrid	Summary of COME RES project findings and discussions on the role of RECs in the Norwegian context	15	-

** Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials*

3.5.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off Meeting of the Norwegian Desk

The kick-off meeting of the Norwegian desk was held on 14 January 2021, online. The main goal was to present the COME RES project to the group of stakeholders joining the Norwegian desk and to kick-off the discussion on how to promote the implementation of Renewable Energy Communities in Norway.

The meeting was attended by 33 people, among stakeholders and markets actors, including small scale energy associations, research organisations and energy cooperatives.

Figure 35 - Breakdown of participants in the kick-off meeting of the Norwegian Desk per stakeholder group

The meeting started with an introduction of the COME RES project and the purpose of the Norwegian country desk, by Karina Standal, CICERO.

The Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE), by Anton Eliston also talked about their role in the project, and the current Norwegian regulation for renewable energy communities.

Then some of the participants brought forward about challenges related to the development of renewable energy communities in Norway today and possible business concepts. Particularly challenges related to rooftop solar PV in housing cooperatives and limitations in the current legal framework was taken up.

The meeting participants were given the chance to ask questions after each of the presentations. When all the presentations were over, they were followed by group discussions, where the meeting participants were divided into three groups that each discussed one specific topic:

Group 1: In the Norwegian context, how/what would a renewable energy community be? And how does this compare with the EU's definition of a renewable energy community?

Group 2: What kind of business models are possible, which both involve open participation for local citizens and where no single actor would have effective control in decision-making processes?

Group 3: What kind of local competencies would be required for enabling the establishment of renewable energy communities and ensuring good and inclusive processes?

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The first thematic workshop and policy lab was held online on 2 June 2021, with 74 participants. The purpose of the day was to identify current framework conditions in the Norwegian context with relevant stakeholders from local governance, energy sector institutions, research institutions and civil society.

Figure 36 - Breakdown of participants in the Thematic Workshop of the Norwegian Desk per stakeholder group

The event had three sessions: An introductory section, where Karina Standal (CICERO) presented the COME RES project, including coming activities and the latest research findings. This was followed by a roundtable organised in two thematic sessions, where stakeholders had the opportunity to discuss selected topics in further detail, including what measures could help facilitate the development of renewable energy communities in a Norwegian context.

Part 1: Framework conditions and opportunities for renewable energy communities in Norway

Senior researcher from Fridtjof Nansens Institutt; Marie Byskov Lindberg, presented findings from a study on solar energy production (prosuming) in apartment residential buildings. Tore Meinert from Utsira municipality (both an island and Norway's most isolated municipality) gave a presentation on how municipalities can take the role as facilitators for renewable energy communities.

Part 2: Local energy communities and the effect on the electricity system in Norway

Kjell Rune Verlo, Advisor with the regulator RME/NVE, gave a presentation on the establishment of local energy communities in Norway, with a focus on current regulation of grids and energy communities. Researchers Henning Taxt and Andrei Morch from Sintef Energy presented the research projects FINE (funded by Norwegian Research Council) and eNeuron (H2020). The projects research flexible integration of local renewable energy communities into the Norwegian electricity distribution system and tools for optimal design and operation of energy communities in Norway.

The participants in the roundtable discussion and panel discussion were – apart from the above-mentioned presenters - representatives of The Norwegian Solar Energy Cluster Association, The Association of Small-scale Hydropower, The Norwegian residential building country association, Gaia Architects and NELFO (trade association for electro, it, ecom). Additionally, the audience also included

grid and power companies, Statkraft, civil society organisations, representatives from political parties, municipalities, technology companies, branch associations, researchers and students in the field.

ACTIVITY 3: First Country Desk Follow-up meeting

The first country desk follow-up meeting was held online the 26 January 2022 with 32 participants. The main focus in the meeting was to discuss the proposed regulatory changes on sharing self-produced electricity within properties (e.g., condominiums) that are highly relevant for local energy communities. Three participants held presentations related to their consultancy input: Energy Norway (Jon Erling Fonneløp), the Solar Energy Cluster (Ola Rostad) and NBBL (Norwegian residential building country association) (Ketil Krogstad). It was followed by questions and discussion.

Figure 37 - Breakdown of participants in the first Country Desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

Karina Standal (CICERO) presented the preliminary results from the study of barriers and drivers for renewable energy communities.

In the second part of the meeting Kverneland Energi (Aksel Kverneland) held a presentation about solutions and business models for renewable energy communities. Kverneland Energi develops technology and solutions for local energy production and storage.

Afterwards Energigården AS (Erik Eid Hohle) talked about drivers and barriers for renewable energy communities when it comes to bioenergy, and his experience from managing the foundation at Hadeland, outside Oslo. They engage in knowledge exchange and education concerning bio-energy models for local electricity and heating production.

ACTIVITY 4: Second Thematic Workshop

On 21 September 2022, the Norwegian country desk held its second (hybrid) thematic workshop with 44 participants of which nearly half were from a research organisation. The topic of this workshop was: “Renewable Energy Communities: Opportunities in the age of the energy crisis”. Toril Ringholm from the Nordic Artic University held a presentation about the Drivkraft-project, led by the Senja municipality,

which engage the population, especially young people and business, to take part in the transition towards a renewable society.

Figure 38 - Breakdown of participants in the second thematic workshop and policy lab per stakeholder group

Then Jan Bråten, (Statnett) held a presentation about the role of local energy resources in the major energy transition. He gave an overview of the energy situation in Norway and Europe and future energy needs to reach the climate goals in Norway.

The presentations were followed by a panel discussion to discuss the presentations (led by Karina Standal) with Toril Ringholm, Jan Bråten, Maren Aschehoug Esmark (Head of Section, NVE) and Oddvin Breiteig (senior advisor, NELFO). In the dialogue, it was discussed what kind of role municipalities and local authorities can play in facilitating and benefiting from local energy communities and what resources they then need.

Wilfried Piementa de Miranda (Managing Director, Alpha Venturi) presented the HOLONI project which is a collaboration with the City of Copenhagen. Through the project, they have prepared and delivered technology services that show the potential for implementing roof-based solar systems in given areas.

This was followed by a summary of research findings on drivers and barriers (D2.3) and stakeholder consultation survey (D3.4) in the COME RES project. Nora Ytreberg (scholar CICERO) and Karina Standal presented the findings from qualitative interviews and a survey among stakeholders in Norway and the COME RES countries in Europe.

Finally, the presentations were followed by a panel discussion (led by Karina Standal) with Wilfried Piementa de Miranda, Maren Aschehoug Esmark, Jan Bråten and Ketil Krogstad (special advisor, Norges Boligbyggelags Landsforbund SA (NBBL)). It was discussed whether it is important to expand the local solutions in order to increase acceptance of energy conversion.

Figure 39– Image of the hybrid meeting on 21.09.22. Copyright: Erik Tollefsen

ACTIVITY 5: Second Policy Lab

The second policy roundtable was organised by CICERO Center for Climate Research, in close collaboration with NVE on 24 October 2022. The event was arranged as a closed dialogue meeting with representatives from NVE, The Norwegian Energy Regulatory Authority (RME), Enova and CICERO. The Ministry of Energy and Petroleum was also invited but had to cancel their participation shortly before the meeting took place.

The purpose of the event was to disseminate research findings on drivers and barriers for renewable energy communities in Norway and to prompt discussion on the opportunities and the role renewable energy communities can play in today's Norwegian energy context with high energy costs due to climate change, the phasing out of fossil energy in Europe and Russia's invasion of the Ukraine. Particular emphasis was placed on the dialogue around: 1) sharing of self-produced electricity, 2) the current model with exemption from electricity tax and network rental for self-produced electricity, 3) government support schemes and 4) narratives around Norwegian energy and the power system concerning what is understood as beneficial to society and cost-effective at national and local level. Four presentations were held: The EU green contribution, focus on renewable energy communities and advantages of such models (Merethe Dotterud Leiren); Summary of research findings on drivers and barriers for renewable energy communities in Norway (Karina Standal); Energy communities and their implementation under the Clean Energy Package (Stavroula Pappa REScoop.eu); Regulations concerning grid distribution and renewable energy communities in Norway (Ingvild Grøtterud Birkeland RME, Martin Windju NVE).

ACTIVITY 6: Second Country Desk Follow-up meeting

The second and final Norwegian country desk meeting took place on 16 November at CICERO's Science Park in Oslo. In total, 15 participants, of which 2/3 were women, were present either online or physically.

During the meeting several presentations were given. Karina Standal illustrated the main activities and main findings of the COME RES project. Data from surveys and interviews show that there are clear expectations of how a renewable energy society can contribute to the energy transition in Norway, but there are still high transaction costs involved for grass-root actors. After Standal, researcher Hanne Sæle (CINELDI/SINTEF) presented a study of barriers and opportunities for grid companies to facilitate local solutions. Sæle's presentation was based on interviews with grid companies in Norway. She pointed out that there is a significant demand for increased power in the power system, which is linked to the green shift, but there are several barriers in terms of geography (flexibility needs to be produced locally), competence and barriers. Also, there is a lack of are business models and actors that can realise and activate flexibility in the value chain. Subsequently, Terje Holmen presented the renewable energy community Lohøgda housing cooperative. Holmen described the process and the experience of setting up local PV electricity production and storage in heat boilers. There are plans for extending the project to hydrogen for storage purposes.

In the second session of the meeting, Beatrice Rossebø Danielsen, architect and site developer Byantropologene, presented a mapping of people's perspectives on energy on Utsira Island where they have had local electricity production from two wind turbines since 2007. Danielsen addressed the complexity of social acceptance and the need for energy projects to be anchored within the needs and benefits for the local communities. Lastly, Erik Eid Hohle from the foundation Energigården presented the research project CLIMATE BEST and transfer of local energy models from Norway to Slovakia. The meeting ended with a discussion on the role of renewable energy communities in Norway.

Figure 40 - Breakdown of participants in the second Country Desk follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

3.5.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: THE ONLINE SURVEY

CICERO led the work of D3.4 Summary report of the consultation series of the eight country desks. The survey was anonymous, but the response rate was much higher than the country desk members. Several of the Norwegian country desk members were helpful in distributing information of the survey in their network channels and in their newsletters (e.g., the Solar Energy Cluster Association). CICERO also used its own research network to ensure that the survey was distributed to relevant researchers in the field and stakeholder actors within relevant sectors (e.g., research projects with a large number of grid companies involved).

The stakeholder consultation survey supplied a systematic overview of relevant stakeholders' perceptions and experiences concerning RECs role in the Norwegian energy transition and energy system, barriers for RECs and adequate measures to support the promotion of RECs in Norway. Thus in-depth information could be gained on the barriers and drivers experienced by potential REC owners in Norway. Here issues of regulations, lack of information and awareness were highlighted. Furthermore, the interviews provided valuable insights on the potential benefits of RECs for local communities and for the low-carbon transition in Norway. There was a clear consensus that RECs can play an important role in enabling a more flexible and smart energy system, more renewable energy production and reducing grid costs. The majority also stated that the government's focus should not be mainly on large scale solutions. Moreover, the main barriers noted were regulations that limit sharing and sale of self-produced electricity, as well as lack of political focus on national and local government level. Further details are discussed in section 3.5.3.

OTHER ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

The CICERO team has distributed regular news and information to the Norwegian country desk members through newsletters or invitations to the different events (see the images below). In these newsletters we have emphasised popular science articles produced from COME RES research findings, latest deliverables, policy briefs and important events on relevant topics arranged by CICERO. These newsletters were distributed at the start of the project, May 2021, December 2021, Mai 2022, September 2022 and one is planned for January/February 2023.

Siste nytt fra COME RES-prosjektet om lokale energisamfunn

Kjære medlem av referansegruppen til COME RES-prosjektet,
 Vi setter stor pris på deltakelsen deres og engasjementet i COME RES-prosjektet så langt. Prosjektet går imidlertid mot slutten (februar-23), og vi kaller derfor inn til siste møte i referansegruppen. Onsdag 16. november fra 12.30 til 15.00 samles vi hos CICERO i Forskningsparken. Hermere program kommer senere, men vi vil blant annet få høre Hanna Sævi fra CINELDI/SINTEF Energi presentere en studie av barrierer og muligheter for at nettselskap skal kunne legge til rette for mer lokale løsninger, og Tarje Holmen fortelle om Lohøgda borettslags solcelleprosjekt og hydrogenplaner.
 Dersom du har forslag til temaer for gruppediskusjonen under møtet, vennligst gi beskjed til [Hege Fantoft Andreassen](#) ved CICERO innen 1. november.

[Klikk her for å melde deg på!](#)

COME RES-innlegg på Arendalsuka
 CICERO deltok med åtte arrangementer under Arendalsuka. "Er lokale energiløsninger veien til klimamålstilling?" var ett av dem. Olov Solar, Elnova og OBOS var med i panelsamtale, etter innlegg fra flere forskere. [Se oppslaget her](#)

Referat fra workshop: Lokale energiløsninger - muligheter i energikrisens tid
 21. september arrangerer vi workshop i COME RES-prosjektet. Referatet kan leses her: [Tematisk workshop](#). Presentasjonene fra innleiderne ligger som vedlegg i mailen.

Ny rapport: De ti beste eksemplene på lokale energiløsninger i Europa
 Det er foretatt en analyse av hvilke suksessfaktorer som ligger til grunn i etableringen av lokale fornybare energisamfunn i Europa. Det har resultert i en liste av anbefalinger for beslutningstakere og utviklere av lokale energisamfunn. Les mer på COME RES egen nettside: [Synthesis Report](#)

Forskningsworkshop om lokale energisamfunn
 CICERO, FME CINELDI og Include inviterer til forskningsworkshop på lokale energisamfunn 18. november. Workshopen har til hensikt å samle og utveksle erfaringer mellom forskere som jobber med temaet. Det vil bli presentasjoner fra flere relevante forskningsstudier. Workshopen er hybrid og er åpen for alle interesserte. [Info@dev.uib.no](#)

Vennligst meld deg på ved å klikke på knappen under.

Dersom du har noen forslag til temaer for møtet, gi beskjed til [Hege](#) ved CICERO innen 20. desember.

Med vennlig hilsen
 det norske COME RES-teamet:
 Hege Fantoft Andreassen og Karina Standal ved CICERO
 Anton Eliston og Astrid Gunhild Stavsgang ved NVE

[Klikk her for å melde deg på!](#)

Fornybare lokale energisamfunn - muligheter og hindringer

Beboere med personlig engasjement og god kunnskap er et ekstra fortrinn for borettslag som vil etablere lokal energiproduksjon. Det viser nylige intervjuer med sivilsamfunn, bedrifter og kommuner. [Lenke til sak](#)

Nytt faktaark om prosjektet

Lær mer om COME RES, og se hva som er status i de andre medlemslandene:

[Faktaark #1](#)

Artikkel i Energy Monitor

CICERO-forskere har bidratt på artikkel i tidsskriftet Energy Monitor om Fornybare, lokale energisamfunn:

[The conditions for community energy](#)

Figure 41 - Examples of the Norwegian newsletter

3.5.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

The activities held by the Norwegian desk were successful in gathering different stakeholder groups involved in the implementation of RECs. As the discussions of the different activities have pointed out, Norway is a country that spans over different geographies, needs and preconditions regarding RECs: Energy transition in Arctic areas; energy security and supply in island communities, growth of local businesses in areas where expanding or upgrading transmission is costly as well as local energy production in cities where there is a rapid increase of electric vehicles that pose new challenges for supply and flexibility of the electricity system. Recent surges in electricity prices have also highlighted the need for new energy solutions concerning heating (most of heating in Norway is through electricity) through decentralised systems. Furthermore, the concept of RECs is rather new in the Norwegian context and is interpreted in other ways than the definition given in RED II. Further, since Norway is not an EU member (but part of the EEA) the process of implementing RED II is not following a predefined time schedule, and thus does not entail a high policy focus on RECs.

Therefore, there is much to learn from the large variation of perspectives and stakeholders that are relevant for renewable energy communities in Norway. The main measures to abate the existing barriers which were emphasised by the stakeholders in the consultation survey were: reduction of regulatory and bureaucratic procedures, lacking access to systematic learning from pilot projects, lacking support for capacity development from national or local government. Adequate support schemes were mentioned as a fourth important measure. The present energy crisis with unprecedented high electricity costs in Norway (Southern and Western part) have shown that local energy models are becoming increasingly relevant for local actors, but also that there is uncertainty in terms of framework conditions

and how to best integrate such models into the existing power system which is based on national cost-efficiency and public ownership. A change towards more decentralised supply will require that important institutions such as local authorities and grid companies take on new roles and need new resources in doing so. At present there is no formal process for providing resources, incentives or guidelines for this to happen. In general RECs are not the main driver of local models. These are rather encouraged by other actors such as grid companies, property developers, power and tech companies and the research sector.

The discussions during the country desk meetings, thematic workshops and policy roundtables have revealed that there is a high interest in decentralised energy solutions in Norway, but these are not mainly driven forward by potential REC members/owners or grassroots actors. Rather, the climatic conditions require integrated and hybrid decentralised systems that are complex and connected with high investment costs (PV alone will also have disruptive aspects for the system). Moreover, the concept of RECs is not in line with the definition given in RED II as there is little focus on these aspects in Norway. Decentralised and local energy systems are gaining interest rapidly in research, power and grid companies, tech companies and larger businesses, as well as in some municipalities, SMEs and housing cooperatives (a common living form in larger Norwegian cities).

Decentralised energy models are also on the government agenda and new regulations that will promote more opportunities for housing companies/condominiums to engage in energy production as prosumers is signalled. However, the proposed changes are moderate and there is a debate concerning how to ensure such models can be profitable and integrated in the energy system, without transferring grid costs to other consumers. Despite the proposed regulations the policy focus is low and the latest Energy White paper focuses mainly on Norway's opportunities for energy related employment from building industry within blue hydrogen and off-offshore wind and very little on consumer and community aspects. The profound impact of the energy crisis on Norwegian households and local communities has fixed the focus primarily towards subsidy schemes and not on promoting RECs.

In general, the discussions have brought out different stakeholder interests and at times conflicting views on RECs and local energy solutions in the Norwegian energy system. Local energy solutions (including RECs) are perceived both as a valuable and necessary element in the energy transition, but also a potential disruptive element as it challenges today's centralised power distribution system and distribution of grid costs. This linked to solar PV as the most relevant technology for RECs due to the resistance against onshore wind and small-scale hydropower already being quite developed in Norway. To ensure energy security throughout the year (most energy is consumed during winter) this technology needs to be integrated with other technologies to be optimal in the system. Simultaneously, solar PV will provide local actors (housing cooperatives, SMEs and municipal buildings) with important financial benefits, but will entail higher costs for grid companies (under regulated monopoly) that will be transferred to the consumers. To ensure adequate development there is a need for a dialogue between different actors and decision-makers in order to ensure supporting regulations and framework conditions that open up opportunities for grassroots actors (and thus community benefits) as well as ensure an optimal system for energy security and fair distribution of costs.

3.6. POLAND

In Poland, the country desk concentrates on community PV and community integrated solutions in the Warmian-Masurian target region. The desk involved a core group of 25 stakeholders, including policy makers, national and regional (renewable) energy organisations, energy clusters, academia, civil society, banks, regional funds for environmental protection and water management, the PV industry, public utilities as well as local authorities and members of the parliament.

Table 9 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Polish Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Makers
Kick-off meeting	27.01.2021	Online	Conditions for development of community energy in Poland	85	5
First Thematic Workshop	28.10.2021	Olsztyn	PV installations – a key element of energy communities in Poland	13	0
First Country Desk Follow-up Meeting	25.05.2022	Online	Draft RES law	12	1
Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	10.11.2022	Warsaw	Citizen energy	8	0
Third Country Desk Follow-up Meeting and Policy Lab	02.12.2022	Online	Action Plan for Małopolska Province	14	1

** Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials*

3.6.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off Meeting of the Polish Desk

The kick-off meeting of the Polish desk was held on 27 January 2021. The main aim of the event entitled “Conditions for development of community energy in Poland” was to present the COME RES project, its objectives, activities and approach, and to discuss the status quo of community energy in Poland in the context of the RED II provisions. The meeting was attended by 85 stakeholders, from the following groups:

- Policy makers (Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Technology, Ministry of Climate and Environment, and Ministry of National Defence);
- National renewable energy organisations (Alliance of Associations Polish Green Network, Polish Wind Energy Association, and Polish Green Building Council);
- Regional energy organisations (Baltic Energy Conservation Agency);
- Metropolitan areas (Agglomeration Opole Trust, and Gdansk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area);

- Energy clusters (Żywiecki Klaster Energii);
- Academia (Warsaw University of Life Sciences, and Silesia University);
- Scientific Institutes (Institute of Power Engineering, Interdisciplinary Division for Energy Analyses of National Centre (IDEA) for Nuclear Research);
- Civic and Social Organisation (Association “SPRING”);
- Banks (Bank of Environmental Protection);
- Regional Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management – energy advisers;
- PV industry (Bison Energy);
- Technical universities (Silesian University of Technology);
- Public utilities (GPEC Group – Leader of Thermal Industry in Pomerania);
- Local authorities (Municipality of Zalewo, Municipality of Gorlice, Municipality of Bytom, and Municipality of Kościelisko);
- Parliament representatives.

The group of participants was also diverse in terms of the geographical scope of action, embracing local and national actors. Figure 42 represents the breakdown of the event participants per stakeholder group.

Figure 42 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick-off Meeting of the Polish Desk per stakeholder group

During the discussion, several RES community energy research projects and initiatives were presented. One of them, KlastER (Development of distributed energy within energy clusters), is being realised by the consortium composed of the Ministry of Development, the University of Science and Technology (AGH) and the Interdisciplinary Division for Energy Analyses of National Centre (IDEA) in the framework of the GOSPOSTRATEG programme from 2019 to 2021. One of the project’s objectives is to develop viable business models for community energy. It was emphasised that a current problem for developing business models is the lack of regulations that would enable any business models for community energy, which would ensure competitiveness in the energy market.

Three key factors that influence the development of energy communities were underlined:

- Enabling a regulatory framework;
- Support schemes;
- Awareness and social acceptance.

The network of energy advisors that operates in every voivodeship in Poland, under the Regional Funds for Environmental Protection and Water Management, acts to promote the use of RES and energy efficiency on a local level. This network is an effective tool to raise awareness of local actors and facilitate the development of community energy. The energy advisors are doing so by consulting, advising and participating in conferences, workshops and training for municipal energy managers. The services of energy advisors are free of charge because they are funded by the European Operational Programme Infrastructure and Environment.

It is worth noting that the cooperation of KAPE with the Regional Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Olsztyn had already started within the project “WinWind - Winning social acceptance for wind energy in wind energy scarce regions” (2017-2020), and this lively cooperation has been continued under the COME RES project. This regional fund is located in Olsztyn, the target region of the Polish desk.

One of the most valuable inputs was provided by the Director of the Low-Emission Economy Department of the Ministry of Development, Labour and Technology, Mr. Przemysław Hofman. He presented the current status of the regulatory work in detail. He also mentioned that the work on a proposal for a framework for collective prosumers is almost finished. The Ministry is currently in the stage of receiving confirmation from the Energy Regulatory Office (ERO) and the Ministry of Climate and Environment regarding this legislative project.

There are two models for collective prosumers that are intended to be introduced:

- Virtual prosumption – dedicated to installations that are not physically connected with the owners (energy consumers). A similar model was introduced in Lithuania. In this model, prosumers will have access to some of the privileges that regular prosumers have (e.g., net-metering scheme);
- Collective prosumption – dedicated to multifamily buildings. This model will operate on the same basis as individual prosumers (with the same rights and obligations).

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop

The first thematic workshop was organised by The Polish National Energy Conservation Agency (KAPE) in cooperation with The Regional Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Olsztyn. The event was held on 21 October 2021, as a physical meeting in Olsztyn. The workshop targeted the regional energy advisors working for The Regional Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in the Warmian-Masurian Province and gathered 13 participants.

The workshop entitled “PV installations – a key element of energy communities in Poland” began with an introduction given by Dr. Ryszard Wnuk, Senior Expert for Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and

[COME RES 953040 – Deliverable 3.3: Final Consolidated Summary Report of Desk Activities in the Target Regions](#)

Energy Efficiency (EE) at KAPE, who introduced the participants to the issues of RES utilisation through different technologies. He presented a variety of RES technologies that could be utilised in order to create self-sustainable energy communities. Furthermore, he presented the synergies resulting from combination of selected technologies. He also illustrated the European PV market in terms of total capacities installed, new capacities and energy produced in selected countries.

Piotr Nowakowski, Expert for RES at KAPE, described the origin of COME RES project, underlying the importance of the activities and outcomes that resulted from the previous initiative (WinWind project). He presented an overview of the COME RES project, its objectives, and methodology, explaining the links between the different activities. Piotr Nowakowski also presented the results of the analysis on potential assessment of RECs in target regions. Afterwards he held a presentation on the topic: “Economic profitability of PV installations – investments being realised by individuals, public entities, small and medium enterprises”. He emphasised the key aspects having impact on economic performance of the investment, i.e.:

- Annual electricity demand;
- Profile of energy consumption;
- Electricity cost;
- Escalation of electricity prices.

Nowakowski also presented and described business models that are utilised by different entities. These business models include:

- Net-metering scheme;
- Energy auctions;
- Full self-consumption;
- Self-consumption combined with electricity sales.

Afterwards, he illustrated a model PV installation – prosumer PV installation integrated within a passive building. The results of the technical – economic analysis, carried out with the use of a number of technical indicators, calculated on the basis of measurement data from the on-site monitoring system were also presented. The discussion on the economic profitability of the investment was based on static (Simple Payback Time) and dynamic economic indicators (Net Present Value, Internal Rate of Return).

The remaining part of the workshop was devoted to a broad discussion on the topic of the future of the energy communities in Poland.

The first topic addressed the provisions for energy cooperatives and energy clusters stipulated by the RES Act. It was pointed out that at the beginning of the year, the Ministry of Development was responsible for the roll-out of the enabling framework for energy cooperatives, virtual and collective prosumers. The head of the department at the Ministry of Development responsible for this task was actively involved in the Polish country desk activities. However, in the meantime, this responsibility was handed over to the Ministry of Climate and Environment. The new ministry started working on a rather

new approach, namely the further development of energy clusters, and the previous quite advanced solutions were stopped or postponed.

During the discussion with the participants following topics were extensively discussed:

- Energy clusters and community-driven initiatives in the region;
- RES technologies often utilised within energy communities;
- Key drivers for creation of energy community;
- Key actors involved in energy communities;
- Business models available;
- Impact of grants and other incentives on market and prices of RES technologies.

The participants also gave details of several biogas installations which initiated the cooperation of many entities at a local level and became a starting point for the creation of energy clusters. These examples were based on the model where electricity is produced jointly with heat in a CHP unit (fuelled with biogas). In such a model, electricity produced is fed to the grid (sold for fixed price – Feed-in Tariff scheme) and heat is utilised in many cases for heating purposes of public buildings or by private buildings. Such utilisation of heat from biogas installations decreases public opposition and creates favourable conditions for further cooperation.

Furthermore, the discussion focused on the Investment Programme within the framework of the National Recovery Plan dedicated to RES investments being realised by energy communities. The programme was recently revealed and presented by the Ministry of Development and Technology.

The programme foresees:

- Pre-investment support;
- Horizontal support;
- Investment support.

The estimated number of energy communities benefiting from pre-investment stage support is 139 and from investment stage support is 10.

During the discussion, the assumptions of the programme were also discussed, especially with regard to the: type of beneficiaries; time horizon; scope of support (eligible activities).

ACTIVITY 3: First Country Desk Follow-up Meeting

The first country desk status meeting was held on 25 May 2022 and brought together national, regional and local stakeholders, including policy makers, research organisations, the regional environmental fund, a RES company and other stakeholders. Figure 43 shows the breakdown of the participants per stakeholder group. The meeting was attended by 12 participants with a preponderance of actors from the national level over local ones. Approximately 50% of stakeholder participants were female.

Figure 43– Breakdown n of participants in the first Country Desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

The event focused on “Prosumership and collective consumption and draft RES law containing elements of the transposition of the RED II directive in Poland”.

The country desk discussed the concept of power system balancing introduced in Poland. One can talk about the collective prosumership in the Polish law with the entry into force of the amendment to the Law on Renewable Energy Sources, which introduced the possibility of using a new procedure of billing micro and small installations of renewable energy sources. This is a solution that allows direct production and consumption of energy from renewable sources by owners of installations in multi-apartment buildings. In this case, both the electricity consumption points and the renewable energy installation are connected to the electricity distribution network via the building's internal electrical system.

The country desk meeting yielded three main conclusions:

- Collective prosumership provides an opportunity for residents of multi-unit buildings in cities - users who are excluded by Polish law from the energy cooperative - to produce and use renewable energy.
- The participants agreed that the transposition of the RED II and the IEMD directives is a too lengthy process. The draft laws have been awaiting adoption for more than a year and do not represent a complete transposition.
- The billing method for both collective prosumers and energy cooperatives is not yet determined.

ACTIVITY 4: Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The second thematic workshop and the first policy lab were held on 10 November 2022. The meeting was attended by seven stakeholders, with a representation from energy and innovation agencies/competence centres, SMEs, community energy initiatives/energy cooperatives, NGOs and network organisations and research organisations. Figure 44 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. Stakeholders from the national and local level were equally represented. Approximately 71% of the participants were female.

Figure 44 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group

The workshop discussed issues related to the development of citizens' energy initiatives such as:

- the current situation in the citizen energy sector against the background of the European developments (more than a dozen such initiatives were identified),
- activities/plans related to citizen energy in Poland,
- plans in the context of the election campaign and potential fields for joint action,
- grid connection by DSOs as potentially the biggest problem for emerging cooperatives plus possible actions by local governments in this area,
- lack of tested solutions for establishing cooperatives,
- planned first call for the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management applications addressing at energy communities,
- lack of initiatives in the area of collective prosumership and potential difficulties associated with its implementation,
- the so-called "RES grant" project, which offers subsidies of up to 50% of the cost of PV installations on multi-family houses.

After the analysis of the current problems and perspectives of citizen energy, the assumptions of the policy lab's operation and expectations for the creation of a regional action plan were presented. During this meeting, a target region was selected – Małopolska Province, for which an action plan is going to be elaborated.

ACTIVITY 5: Second Country Desk Follow-up Meeting and Policy Lab

A country desk and policy lab on the development of an action plan for the REC was held on 2 December 2022, bringing together regional and local stakeholders, including policy makers, energy agencies, regional fund and other representatives of the energy community. Figure 45 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. The meeting was attended by 14 participants with a

preponderance of actors from the national level over the local one. Approximately 43% of stakeholders participating were female.

Figure 45 – Breakdown of participants in the second Country Desk Follow-up meeting and Policy Lab per stakeholder group

The purpose of the meeting was to provide an update on the status of the COME RES project and co-create cornerstones of an action plan for Małopolska province within the policy lab. Particular attention was paid to a comparative analysis of the regulatory and enabling framework for renewable energy communities in the nine COME RES countries (D7.1), the results of the stakeholder survey (D3.4) and the presentation of business models for RECs (D4.3).

Based on the results of the policy lab, KAPE developed a synthesis of the main findings, presenting the proposed actions in a clear and concise manner. In the final stage, the draft action plan was circulated to a core group of stakeholders for their approval and feedback. The team offered participants the opportunity to make additional comments and suggestions.

During the meeting, stakeholders discussed the solutions for the following barriers:

- Lack of clear/appropriate legislation for renewable energy communities which causes stagnation and delays in the establishment of energy communities.
- Lack of economic incentives and financial support discourages (especially) local government officials from engaging in the conceptual process of establishing RECs.
- Regulations that limit the ability of renewable energy communities to sell surplus energy to the grid.
- Regulations that limit the ability of renewable energy communities to share self-generated electricity (e.g., between members, neighbouring properties).
- Problems with DSOs that block the connection of competing energy co-operatives to the electricity grid. DSOs also fail to disclose the grid's connectivity, causing stagnation in energy investments.

- For the Małopolska Region (in mountainous areas), a significant barrier is the lack of sufficient electricity grids capacity.

During the meeting, the stakeholders also discussed possible enabling measures at both the national and local government levels, which could accelerate the creation of energy communities in Poland.

Particular attention was paid to regulations defining the right of energy cooperatives to become suppliers or producers selling surplus electricity to the grid. In Poland, only energy clusters can sell energy (however, they are not a legal entity – disqualifying them formally as RECs defined under RED II). It was also called for the implementation of a full legal definition of renewable energy communities. Gaps in this regard limit, on the one hand, the full transposition of the directive, on the other hand, the nature of the users.

Another issue analysed by the participants was the plan to introduce pre-investment support instruments for energy clusters and energy cooperatives. These are due to be released in the first quarter of 2023.

Again (the first time the issue was addressed at the thematic workshop on 10 November 2022), a discussion ignited on facilitating access for low-income and vulnerable households to participation in energy communities.

The role of local governments in initiating a dialogue and facilitating cooperation among relevant stakeholders such as research institutions, the business sector, energy companies, etc., was emphasised.

The discussion of the Action Plan for the Małopolska region was preceded by an analysis of the recommendations that were presented by the Krakow Climate Panel. They included, among others:

- recommendation to create energy communities,
- development and implementation of a comprehensive education and information program on climate and environmental challenges, aimed at residents,
- creation of a one-stop energy advice center,
- taking steps to amend the law on the introduction of the collective prosumer.

The proposed action plan activities are described in detail in Deliverable 3.5.

3.6.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: The online survey

The online survey was distributed in May and June 2022 to the members of the national office of KAPE and those stakeholders affiliated with KAPE and/or participating in the Polish country desk. There were 64 respondents in total, of which about 72% completed the survey.

Those who responded had in many cases an interest in RECs or came from the RES industry. Approximately 25% of respondents were representatives of national and local governments, NGOs and networks, research organisations, municipal utilities and energy community/cooperative initiatives. 53% of respondents indicated that they were involved in renewable energy.

Some of the key findings from the survey are:

- Respondents consider the following activities to be most relevant or promising for RECs: electricity generation, heating, storage and flexibility services, and transportation.
- Respondents consider local governments and grid companies to be the most important actors for RECs (about 90%).
- Respondents consider the following technologies to be the most important for RECs: PV (about 95%), bioenergy (85%) and hybrid systems (85%).
- Most of the barriers presented in the survey are considered important or very important by more than 80% of respondents. Lack of REC regulations and lack of financial support were considered the most important barrier to REC development. Lack of networks and knowledge and acceptance of the cooperative model were considered the least important barriers to REC development.
- Nearly 100% of respondents believe that regulations for energy sharing are important/very important. Potential facilitators according to the respondents are: regulations for the sale of energy by RECs and transposition of the implementation of the definition of RECs.
- For respondents, the most important driver for RECs is financial support (about 95%) and the reduction of the administrative barriers (about 90%).
- It is apparently very important to provide financial support to citizens, SMEs and civil society organisations that initiate RECs, as well as to allocate adequate areas for RECs.
- Almost 50% of respondents are not familiar with RED II and respective REC regulations and opportunities.

INPUT TO REGIONAL ENERGY ACTION PLANS

During the second policy lab, the stakeholder team identified a set of activities for the Malopolska province that could enhance the creation of energy communities. The proposed activities are:

1. Action: The establishment of an energy community incubator.
2. Action: Elaboration and disclosure of public inventory of power grids as the basis for planning places where REC can be created.
3. Action: Strengthen the Municipalities by their request for more information relevant for REC from the DSO (e.g. about grid characteristics, consumer connections, grid connection points etc.)
4. Action: Create tax exemptions for the establishment of renewable energy communities.
5. Action: Promote the simplification of administrative procedures for collective self-consumption projects with power over 100kW.
6. Action: Promoting teaching in professions related to the energy transition

OTHER ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

On 5 December 2022 a national conference took place in Kraków on distributed energy, which was attended by Anna Dylağ and several stakeholders from the country desk as well as Marcin Jaczewski from the COME RES Advisory Board. The following issues were discussed:

- The role of distributed energy in Poland's energy transition
- The role of the regulator in the changing energy system
- Assumptions of the strategy for the development of distributed energy in Poland until 2040
 - legislative and regulatory aspects
 - technical-technological aspects
 - economic and financial aspects
 - socio-cultural aspects
- How to develop distributed generation? (Recommendations of the industry)
- What is the future of distributed energy?

According to the Director of the Department of Low Carbon Economy, the introduction of a legal definition of renewable energy communities fully compliant with RED II will not change the current low diffusion rate of energy communities.

3.6.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

The main lessons learned from the Country Desk meetings and thematic workshops can be summarised as follows:

- An enabling policy, regulatory and legal framework, clear ways of accounting for REC members, and the development of cooperation with DSOs are key in developing energy communities.
- As long as the Polish legislator does not properly take into account the role of all types of RECs in the creation of new energy legislation, and as long as it does not create transparent and fair procedures and ways of settlement between energy communities and the electricity grid operators, the development of energy communities will remain marginal.
- In addition, the establishment of long-term oriented support instruments such as pre-investment grants and tax credits would encourage various entities to engage in RECs.
- The essential element for the development of RECs in Poland is the co-operation of the DSOs with RECs. At present, DSOs are reluctant to cooperate with entities that aim to develop RES installations.

3.7. PORTUGAL

Up until the end of December 2022, the Portuguese desk organised five online events: the kick-off meeting, a thematic workshop combined with a policy roundtable, a country desk status meeting, a meeting for the development of a draft action plan, and a thematic workshop combined with a policy lab (see Table 10 below).

Overall, the Portuguese desk activities have had a significant level of participation, demonstrating the engagement of a large number of stakeholders, covering the different groups of stakeholders identified in the stakeholder engagement plan. Both policy makers and public authorities demonstrated great interest in the project and had a good level of participation in the different activities promoted by the desk. The least engaged groups are financing institutions and mass media.

Table 10 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Portuguese Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Makers
Kick-off meeting	29.01.2021	Online	RECs in Portugal: Status quo	35	4
First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	22.06.2021	Online	RECs in Portugal: current context and prospects for the future	132	4
First Country Desk Follow-up Meeting	15.02.2022	Online	RECs and their implementation in Portugal	29	4
Second Country Desk Follow-up Meeting	17.11.2022	Online	Drafting an Action Plan for the Norte Region	5	-
Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab	22.11.2022	Online	How to promote RECs in Portugal: Transfer of Good-Practices and Action Plan	95	15

** Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials*

3.7.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off meeting of the Portuguese Desk

The kick-off meeting of the Portuguese desk was held online on 29 January 2021. The main goal of this meeting was to present the COME RES project to the group of stakeholders that integrated the Portuguese desk and to kick-off the discussion on how to promote the implementation of Renewable Energy Communities in Portugal.

The meeting was attended by 35 people, among stakeholders and markets actors, with around 25% of female audience. The group of participants included energy cooperatives, local authorities and energy agencies, systems operators, energy suppliers, research organisations, policy makers and other. Figure 46 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. The group of participants was also diverse in terms of the geographical scope of action, having local and national actors.

Figure 46 - Breakdown of participants in the Kick-off meeting of the Portuguese Desk per stakeholder group

The event started with a presentation by Isabel Azevedo (INEGI), focusing on the COME RES project, its objectives and expected results. The intervention also covered the main objectives of the desk itself and the planned desk activities for the project duration. Then, all participants were invited to present themselves, their institution and a small statement on their interest/involvement with community energy initiatives. The meeting also had space for an intervention by Coopérnico, an energy cooperative, represented by Ana Rita Antunes, who launched an open discussion about the status quo of RECs in Portugal. The discussion between the participants focused mainly on the barriers and challenges to its implementation as well as identifying the potential contributions of the COME RES project.

Throughout the discussion, different participants identified **opportunities** for the promotion of RECs, as e.g., potential synergies with energy efficiency and energy poverty related policies. Combining the implementation of RECs with actions towards sustainable mobility, including electric mobility, was also seen as an opportunity to promote RES integration at the local level.

Regarding the main **challenges and barriers** to the implementation of RECs in Portugal, there were identified regulatory, technical, economic and capacity-related barriers as follows:

- **Regulatory barriers:** The lack of a clear definition of key concepts as proximity, energy sharing and the difference between collective self-consumption and REC was mentioned as one of the main regulatory challenges for the implementation and operation of RECs, along with the regulatory uncertainty regarding the rules for connection with the grid and the applicable tax rebates.
- **Technical barriers:** The mostly centralised management of the grid may prompt some challenges to the implementation of local energy initiatives, including RECs. The participants have also identified the delay in the roll-out of smart meters as a potential challenge to the deployment of energy community initiatives.
- **Economic and financing barriers:** The fact that RECs need to fulfil the same requirements as any other market agent to provide system services, including the payment of the global warranty, may be an obstacle to the participation of RECs in the market, even though this could

be overcome with the dissemination of the aggregators' role. Alongside, the financing of RECs may be challenging, due to the risks involved in this type of initiatives, centred on collective investments and active participation of individual citizens.

- Information gaps: The lack of clear and accessible information may constitute a barrier to massive uptake of citizens in setting up and/or participating in RECs. Information on criteria for establishing a REC, key points on internal contracting rules, available funds and support mechanisms, among others, was mentioned to be essential to democratise the creation and participation in this type of initiatives.

ACTIVITY 2: First thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The first thematic workshop and policy lab was held online on 22 June 2021. There were 132 registered participants, representing over 60 different entities. The audience was composed by a wide set of stakeholders and markets actors, from policy makers to local authorities, energy agencies, systems operators and other, consisting of 22% female and 78% male participants.

Figure 47 - Breakdown of participants in the Thematic Workshop of the Portuguese Desk per stakeholder group

The workshop started with a brief presentation of the COME RES project and intermediate results by Isabel Azevedo (INEGI). This was followed by a session dedicated to the topic "RECs in Portugal: from theory to practice", presenting research projects and pioneer initiatives that explore the concept of CER in Portugal. This sharing of experiences allowed for the identification and dissemination of different forms of implementation in the Portuguese context, respective opportunities and difficulties. The speakers included: (1) Inês Campos, Researcher at the cE3c of the University of Lisbon, who presented the main results of the European project PROSEU; (2) Ana Rita Antunes, Coordinator of Coopérnico, who presented the European project Compile, in which Coopérnico will implement a REC in a private condominium, where residents have jointly invested in the installation of PV solar panels; (3) Bruno Carvalho, Project Manager in AdEPorto, presented the Asprela+Sustentável project and the REC concept that will be implemented in the municipality of Porto within this project; and (4) Francisco Gonçalves, CEO of CSide, a software company investing in the development of solutions for the management of RECs. The workshop also included an interactive session where all participants were

invited to perform a SWOT analysis of the legal and policy framework applicable to RECs in Portugal. As a starting point for this interactive session, Filipe Pinto, Director of Electricity Services at DGEG, presented the current framework applicable to RECs and collective self-consumption, as well as what are the legal and regulatory actions planned for the near future.

The event ended with a policy roundtable, moderated by Jorge Vasconcelos, President of NEWES and former President of ERSE, focused on the transposition of the Directive EU 2018/2001 to Portuguese legislation. The panel was composed by: Filipe Pinto, Director of DGEG's Electricity Services; Margarida Ramires Ramos, pbbbr Consultant in Administrative Law; Manuel Casquiço, Director of ADENE's Programmes and Initiatives Department; and Susana Serôdio, Head of APREN's Technical Department. The debate led to the identification of barriers that persist to the implementation of RECs, as well as to the suggestion of incentives and measures which are necessary to ensure the large-scale deployment of community energy initiatives in the Portuguese context.

A more detailed summary of the event is available in the project official website and the full recording of the event can be accessed [here](#).

ACTIVITY 3: First Country Desk Follow-up meeting

The first country desk meeting was held on 15 February 2022, online. The event was limited to the core group of stakeholders from the Portuguese desk. There were 29 participants, including a wide set of stakeholders and markets actors, from policy makers to local authorities, energy agencies, systems operators and other, consisting of 33% female and 67% male participants. Figure 48 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group.

Figure 48 – Breakdown of participants in the first Portuguese country desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

The meeting started with update of the COME RES project, with the presentation of intermediate results by Isabel Azevedo (INEGI). The aim of the intervention was not only to disseminate the recent project results among the group of Portuguese stakeholders, but also to take the opportunity to validate part of those results. The preliminary results on the barriers and drivers for RECs implementation in Portugal, from the focus group interviews performed as part of Task 2.3, were presented, along with the

methodology used. Examples of legal and organisational forms, deriving from Deliverable 4.1, were also presented.

This intervention was followed by an intervention from Ivone Rocha, Partner at Telles de Abreu Advogados, responsible for the Department of Energy, Environment and Natural Resources, dedicated to the topic "DL 15/2022 – challenges and opportunities for RECs". The implications of the recently published Decree-Law for RECs and collective self-consumption were presented and discussed with the participating stakeholders. Ivone Rocha also presented some of the difficulties promoters of RECs have been facing, as well as some of the most common options in terms of legal forms.

ACTIVITY 4: Second Country Desk Follow-up meeting

The second country desk follow-up meeting was held on 17 November 2022, online. The event had as main objective identifying key actions for the promotion of RECs in Portugal, with a focus on the Norte region. The meeting participation was limited to a very small number of people in order to foster a highly interactive and dynamic brainstorming session. The participants, selected based on the deep knowledge on the main barriers for RECs and the good understanding of local context, included a local energy agency, an energy cooperative, a consumers’ association and a citizen willing to create a REC initiative. The participants were all male.

Figure 49 - Breakdown of participants in the second Portuguese country desk Follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

The meeting started with an intervention from Isabel Azevedo (INEGI), who stated the aim and agenda of the meeting. Isabel also presented the COME RES results on the main barriers and drivers associated with the implementation of RECs, including results from the focus group interviews from Task 2.3 and the ones from public consultation from Task 3.4. This presentation was followed by a brainstorming session, where all participants were asked to identify actions they considered necessary to accelerate the implementation of RECs in Portugal, and in the Norte region. Throughout the discussion, Isabel Azevedo (INEGI), who acted as moderator of the session, filled a digital board with all the ideas, disaggregating the actions by level of implementation (national, regional, and local). The event ended

with a systematisation of the proposed actions and who could be responsible for their implementation. Shows the digital whiteboard used to keep track of the proposed actions, by the end of the session.

1a FASE					
Brainwriting					
<p>Linhas de ações chave para a promoção de CER em Portugal, com foco na Região Norte</p> <p>O que tem de ser feito para que as CER se tornem uma realidade?</p> <p>Quem deverá ser envolvido na sua implementação e de que forma?</p> <p style="text-align: right;">20 min</p>					
NACIONAL	REGIONAL	CIM	LOCAL	COMUNIDADE	...
<p>Ação: Clareza relativamente à distância</p> <p>Atores</p> <p>Prioridade</p>	<p>Capacitação das entidades regionais e locais</p> <p>ADENE / DGEG</p> <p>Formadores certificados (DE)</p> <p>Universidades</p>	<p>OSS - Balcão de apoio</p>		<p>ID - software para gestão de energia open source</p>	
<p>Facilitar interação com entidades reguladoras</p> <p>DGEG / ERSE / DSOs</p>	<p>Promoção de CER através dos consumidores finais</p> <p>DECO</p> <p>Quando houver casos práticos</p>	<p>Lista de EGACs</p>		<p>Chegar às pessoas</p>	
<p>Criação de projetos piloto, como ponto de partida de regulação</p>	<p>Criação de agregadores com volume que permita gestão de risco</p>	<p>Gestores de processo - com ligação direta a entidades nacionais</p> <p>Agências de Energia / CIMs</p>	<p>Clarificar o conceito de EGACs</p>	<p>Projetos mais pequenos para dar o exemplo</p> <p>Membros ativos comunidade</p>	
<p>Relação com o DSO / sem restrições técnicas</p>			<p>Compromisso político para a criação de CER</p> <p>Municípios</p>	<p>Criação de confiança no conceito</p> <p>Cooperativas e iniciativas já existentes</p>	
<p>Lista de EGACs</p> <p>DGEG</p>			<p>Modelos estáveis para os consumidores - contratos bilaterais</p> <p>Quem:</p>		
<p>Sessão de esclarecimento / FAQs</p>			<p>Divulgação de resultados de pilotos - bons e maus</p> <p>Pilotos / ERSE / DGEG</p>	<p>Gua por fases de processo - Manual Passo a Passo</p> <p>Agências de Energia</p>	

Figure 50 – Output of the brainstorming sessions dedicated to the development of a draft version of the Action Plan

ACTIVITY 5: Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab

The second thematic workshop and policy lab was held on 22 November 2022, online. There attended 95 participants, representing over 50 different entities. The audience was composed by a wide set of stakeholders and markets actors, from policy makers to local authorities, energy agencies, systems operators and other, consisting of 32% female and 68% male participants. Figure 51 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group.

Figure 51 - Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop of the Portuguese Desk per stakeholder group

The workshop started with a policy lab focusing on policy actions and measures to promote the implementation of RECs in Portugal. The aim of the first session was to provide to the participants insights on what is being done and/or planned by different policy makers regarding the promotion of RECs and promote the discussion on what is still missing, as a starting point for the definition of priorities for the Norte region. The speakers included: (1) Filipe Araújo, Vice-President of the Municipality of Porto, who presented the perspective of the municipality of Porto on RECs and their actions towards the acceleration of RECs implementation at the local level; (2) Bruna Tavares, Member of Future Energy Leaders Portugal (FELPT), who provided the FELPT perspective on the role of RECs for the future energy system; (3) Manuel Casquiço, Director of ADENE’s Programmes and Initiatives Department, who gave some insights on the most recent actions promoted by the national energy agency as well as foreseen initiatives; and (4) António José Baltazar, Head of DGEG’s Licensing Division, presenting the status quo in terms of ongoing licensing procedures for self-consumption and RECs, as well as some of the most recent actions promoted by DGEG to accelerate and simplify the licensing procedure applicable to RECs and collective self-consumption.

The policy lab was followed by a session dedicated to the dissemination of good practices from other European Countries. Within this session, Sophie Loots, Member of the Energy Cooperative ZuidtrAnt, and Sergio Olivero, President of the Scientific Committee of Comunità di Energia Rinnovabile di Magliano Alpi, presented their experiences.

The event ended with an interactive session aiming at the validation of the draft action plan, developed by the small group of stakeholders in the third desk meeting. Isabel Azevedo (INEGI) presented the main barriers and drivers identified in the COME RES activities, followed by a description of the actions proposed. The participants were asked to participate in the identification of priority actions, as well as of the key actors for the promotion of RECs. The participants interacted via the *slido* application, being asked the following questions: (1) What entity/entities is/are crucial for the promotion of RECs? (2) Order by level of priority the actions necessary for the implementation of RECs in Portugal? and (3) What is still missing to ensure a large-scale dissemination of RECs and other renewable energy communities?

3.7.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: The online survey

The Portuguese stakeholders contributed to the online survey with over 50 responses, from which 23 were from the target region, Região Norte. Even though all stakeholder groups were represented, there was a larger participation from research organisations, business sector and associations and groups of interest. This difference in the level of participation is probably associated with the reach of the channels of communication used for dissemination of the survey.

The results of the survey were mostly aligned with the results obtained in the previous project activities, including the discussions from previous desk meetings and the focus group interviews performed in the scope of T2.3. Namely, the identification of the main barriers and drivers for the implementation of RECs in Portugal was fully aligned with the previously obtained results.

The lack of clarity of existing legislation, along with the lack of acceptance and trust in the REC concept and the burdensome of the procedures were confirmed as some of the most relevant barriers for implementation. On the other hand, the need for political commitment, the access to adequate information and the adaptation of existing regulatory frameworks to accommodate RECs specificities were identified as key enablers in the promotion of energy community initiatives. The need for adequate national support scheme was also identified as an important driver.

INPUT TO REGIONAL ENERGY ACTION PLANS

The process for drafting the action plan for the Norte Region, in Portugal, had a strong involvement of the national and regional stakeholders, to ensure the robustness and acceptance of the proposed actions. Different forms of interaction and collaboration were used, depending on the number of stakeholders involved and the type of feedback/input desired.

The stakeholders were involved in three distinct moments, which were combined with three of the country desk activities:

- Validation of the main barriers and drivers, accomplished in the first country desk follow-up meeting. In the meeting, Isabel Azevedo (INEGI) presented the preliminary results from Task 2.3, including the main barriers and drivers for RECs implementation in Portugal. These were discussed with the desk stakeholders.
- Elaboration of a draft action plan, with a limited number of stakeholders, corresponding to the second country desk follow-up meeting. This moment corresponded to a co-creative process, where five local actors were asked to brainstorm on what are the key actions to prompt the implementation of RECs in Portugal, with a focus on the Norte Region. This was a highly interactive session, where all participants contributed to the identification of key actions and respective promoters.
- Validation of the action plan and identification of priorities, accomplished as part of the second thematic workshop and policy lab. The event was open to all interested participants, and the

level of participation was considerably high with 95 participants. The validation of the action plan was done as part of the last session of the event, being preceded by a policy lab where local and national policy makers presented ongoing and foreseen policies and actions to promote RECs, and by a session dedicated to the dissemination of good-practices from other European countries. The participants interacted via the *slido* application, being asked the following questions: (1) What entity/entities is/are crucial for the promotion of RECs? (2) Order by level of priority the actions necessary for the implementation of RECs in Portugal? and (3) What is still missing to ensure a large-scale dissemination of RECs and other renewable energy communities? This interaction was used as an input to identify the priority actions to be included in the action plan.

FOCUS GROUPS ON BARRIERS AND DRIVERS

The Portuguese Desk stakeholders were also strongly involved in the identification of barriers and drivers for the implementation of RECs in Portugal (Task 2.3). This was achieved through their active participation in the kick-off meeting and first thematic workshop and policy lab, where these issues were discussed, as well as through the participation of some of the national market actors and stakeholders in the focus groups interviews, performed as part of Task 2.3. A large share of the participants involved in the interviews were also part of the core group of stakeholders from the national desk, and they were key in the identification of the main barriers and drivers for the large scale deployment of RECs. Moreover, the validation of these barriers and drivers was accomplished in the first country desk follow-up meeting.

OTHER ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

Additionally to the activities foreseen in the Grant Agreement as part of the national country desk, INEGI has also been invited to present COME RES results in events organised by core desk stakeholders as well as other projects. Within the most relevant events are the following:

- “Energy Talk APDEN”, Portuguese Association of Energy Law, with the participation of several members from the European Federation of Energy Law Associations (23 April 2021, online)
- “Conferência-Debate Crise Energética – CM Maia”, an event organised by the Municipality of Maia (Portugal) dedicated to Renewable Energy Communities (31 October 2022, online)
- “AGERAR II – Kick-off event”, an INTERREG project focusing on storage and management solutions for Renewable Energy Communities (03 November 2022, Porto)
- “Energy Agencies and RECs, a new path for energy decentralisation”, an event organised by ADENE, while taking over the Presidency of the European Energy Network, a network that brings together 24 national energy agencies from European countries. The COME RES was presented as the project focus, in an event dedicated to RECs and the role of energy agencies in their promotion (25 November 2022, Lisbon and online).

Furthermore, INEGI has also participated in one of the events organised by the Latvian country desk, with the objective of sharing the experience of Portugal in the transposition of the REC provisions established by the RED II.

3.7.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

The different activities held by the Portuguese desk were successful in gathering different stakeholder groups involved in the implementation of RECs in Portugal, and fostering the discussion on how to develop an appropriate enabling framework, in line with the requirements from RED II. The events also fostered the dialogue between policy makers and different market actors (from local authorities to energy cooperatives), enabling the discussion on the alternative actions that may be taken under the process of transposition of the RED II.

The discussions showed that despite the advances regarding the definition of RECs and the establishment of an appropriate regulatory framework, Portugal is still behind in setting up an enabling framework that promotes and facilitates the development of RECs. Indeed, the first experiences of REC initiatives started appearing in 2021, when the legal concept of RECs was established already in the end of 2019.

Nonetheless, there are some of the barriers identified in the first half of the project that have been mitigated or reduced, such as the lack of clarity of key definition, as “proximity”. There were also some advancements regarding the creation of guidance for potential promoters of RECs, and dedicated support at the local level. And a first dedicated programme to financially support the development of RECs and collective self-consumption was also launched.

Some of the remaining suggestions on the improvement of local conditions and the development of an appropriate enabling framework are as follows:

- Clarification and dissemination of the concept, in order to increase the trust of citizens and local communities in energy community initiatives and their potential benefits;
- Build capacity and provide clear and targeted information on RECs, to potential promoters and enablers. This also refers to the municipalities and other local entities as key actors to achieve a wide dissemination of energy community initiatives;
- The adaptation of the existing framework conditions to accommodate RECs specificities, including the simplification and agility of licensing procedures.

3.8. SPAIN

In Spain, the COME RES project focused its activities on four regions: Valencia and Catalonia were considered model regions, given their long historical tradition of energy cooperatives, linked to their industrial development model. On the other hand, the Spanish archipelagos, the Balearic and Canary Islands, were considered the main target regions of the project, where renewable energy communities should be fostered given the specific vulnerabilities, needs and potential derived from their insularity condition.

Over 40 institutions have been engaged throughout the development of the project in the Spanish stakeholder desk. These included policy makers and context setters at the regional, local, and even national level, such as IDAE – the National Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving, as well as flagship associations, community energy initiatives, energy clusters, energy sales and distribution companies, academia, and civil society organisations.

Table 11 - Overview of COME RES activities held by the Spanish Country Desk

Type of Activity	Date	Location	Topic	No. of Participants	No. of Policy Makers*
Kick-off meeting	26.01.2021	Online	State of play of RECs in Spain	37	10
First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab (Canary Islands)	25.05.2021	Online	Policy, regulations and first steps toward REC development in the Canary Islands	75	17
Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab (Balearic Islands)	30.06.2021	Online	Policy, regulations and first steps toward REC development in the Balearic Islands	51	19
First Country Desk Follow-up meeting	08.03.2022	Online	Validation of COME RES interim results	55	5
Second Country Desk Follow-up meeting & Policy Lab	10.11.2022	Las Palmas, Gran Canaria (Spain)	Development of an Action Plan in the Canary Islands	21	3

* Policy makers include elected politicians and ministerial officials

3.8.1. COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

ACTIVITY 1: Kick-off Meeting of the Spanish Desk

The kick-off meeting of the Spanish desk was held on 26 January 2021, online. The aim of the opening event was to discuss the current status and obstacles to the development of energy communities in Spain with a core group of stakeholders.

The meeting was attended by 37 stakeholders and markets actors, including around 35% female audience and 36% female speakers. The core group of participants included policy makers at national and regional level, energy cooperatives, research organisations and other. Figure 52 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. The group of participants was also diverse in terms of geographical scope of action, with local, regional and national actors.

Figure 52 – Breakdown of participants in the kick-off meeting per stakeholder group

During this first gathering, the Spanish desk coordinator, Nicoletta del Bufalo (Ecorys Spain) welcomed all participants and briefly introduced the COME RES project. Pouyan Maleki (Ecorys Spain) presented COME RES objectives and highlights. The EU and national legal framework for community energy was addressed by Sara de la Serna, representative of the Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition’s Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE).

Regional government representatives of one of the model regions, Comunidad Valenciana, and the two target regions, the Balearic and Canary Islands, presented the status of development of RECs and the main barriers perceived. Moreover, three community energy initiatives and cooperatives from the model region (Comunidad Valenciana) and Navarre were highlighted as ground-breaking, innovative experiences.

An interactive session, moderated by Enrique Rodríguez de Azero (ACER), allowed participants to exchange their views on the existing barriers for REC development in Spain. Irene Alonso (Ecorys Spain) presented the plan of foreseen activities and topics to be addressed in 2021.

ACTIVITY 2: First Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab (Canary Islands)

The first thematic workshop and policy lab was held on 25 May 2021 online. The main goal of the meeting was to identify and study the existing potentials and barriers for the development of RECs in the Canary Islands, as defined in the EU Renewable Energy Directive; to analyse them with the open participation of all stakeholders and to support the process of their acceptance at political-social, community and market level.

Figure 53– Breakdown of participants in the first Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group

To this end, the main processes aimed at the constitution of RECs in the Canary Islands were identified and showcased and, subsequently, a dialogue was generated between the main actors involved to strengthen these experiences, considering that their implementation is still incipient in the archipelago.

The meeting was attended by 75 stakeholders and markets actors (102 registered), including around 31% of female audience and 33% female speakers. The core group of participants included policy makers at regional and island level, who constituted the “target” group of the session; energy and innovation associations and agencies; associations and interest groups; electricity system operators; SMEs; community energy initiatives and cooperatives; financial institutions, as well as universities. Figure 53 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group. The group of participants was also diverse in terms of geographical scope of action, with local, regional and national actors.

The workshop was structured in four thematic blocks, with a cascading approach: firstly, the workshop focused on clarifying key concepts and addressing the confusion (one of the main barriers identified at the beginning of the project) around the definition of a Renewable Energy Community, highlighting its constitutive elements and analysing them in contrast to other actors and legal figures. During this first session, Nicoletta del Bufalo (ECORYS) introduced the objectives and working methodology of the COME RES project, presenting the concept of Renewable Energy Community and the preliminary findings of the first report produced in the framework of the project on the starting conditions at technical, legislative, institutional and political level for the development of RECs. Myriam Castanié (REScoop.eu) focused her presentation on various case studies in European countries such as the Netherlands, the United Kingdom and Ireland.

Secondly, having established the basic approaches, the question of the legislative framework applicable to RECs was addressed, as well as the existing enabling policy framework, with a “bottom-up” approach: from the European framework, through the national framework, to the regional level:

1) Ana María Sánchez Infante (DG ENER), responsible for Renewable Energy Policy and CCS in the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Energy, presented the “Clean Energy Package

for all Europeans”, which aims to place end consumers at the heart of the energy transition. To achieve this, he explained, Member States must provide an “enabling framework” to promote renewable energy communities and ensure access to participation for all consumers;

2) Sara de la Serna (IDAE), reported that the transposition of the aforementioned directive, whose deadline is set for 30 June, is still pending in Spain. However, Spanish legislation already includes the figure of renewable energy communities in Royal Decree 23/2020, which in turn provides for the controversial criterion of “proximity” between renewable energy projects and the legal entity that controls them. Over the last year, IDAE has deployed the first support mechanisms, including the expression of interest on renewable energy communities launched during the first quarter of 2021. Likewise, the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan (PRTR) also includes in its policy lever 3 the deployment and integration of renewable energies through the creation of renewable energy communities, for which an amount of 100 million EUR has been allocated.

3) José Luis Figueroa de la Paz, Head of Cabinet of the Canary Islands Government’s Councillor for Ecological Transition, Combating Climate Change and Territorial Planning, summarised the actions in which the Canary Islands Government is currently involved in the field of community energy. Firstly, the issue has been addressed in the draft bill on Climate Change in the Canary Islands, which will be submitted to the government in the near future, article 38 of which provides for the development of energy communities.

Thirdly, through practical examples of both pilot experiences and more developed REC projects, the context of community energy in the Canary Islands was illustrated through different perspectives, including a first case of RECs being developed on the island of Gran Canaria. The CER project Energia Bonita led by La Palma Renovable on the island of La Palma is being given priority by the government. Finally, an interactive session (policy lab) was held with a moderator and 5 participants (representatives from insular governments), aimed at analysing possible synergies between local policies and the development of RECs. The main barriers and drivers identified during the policy lab are presented below:

Barriers identified

- There is a mix of concepts (shared self-consumption, distributed generation, micro-grids) that the regulation should help to clarify. The examples given are of great interest.
- At present, the concept of RECs is not fully developed in legislation, which is a first barrier to their creation, given the limitations of the current Royal Decree 244/2019 on self-consumption of energy. The establishment of fixed distribution coefficients by legislation means that surplus energy production is returned to the grid with minimal compensation. Since storage is not currently a viable option due to its high cost, the profitability of this type of installation depends on subsidies.

- The power limit of 100 kW does not allow, for example, the use of large roofs of public buildings. Also, the limit of 500m for shared proximity self-consumption could exclude areas with a few renewable resources from participating in RECs.
- Lack of harmonisation of local regulations, especially as regards criteria and requirements for photovoltaic installations.

Opportunities and drivers for the development of RECs

- Proximity and direct line of communication between the regional government and the different projects underway, which are given political priority.
- Submission of projects to the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Funds. For example, the Council of Gran Canaria is strongly committed to the creation of RECs in all the municipalities of the island, having presented projects that amount to a total of 41MW of power to be installed and 35MW from industrial estates. Possibility of using the roofs of public buildings.
- Growing interest from the local private sector, particularly from business associations on industrial estates, in the constitution of renewable energy communities. Potential benefits associated with the figure of the demand aggregator in distributed energy generation.

ACTIVITY 3: Second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab (Balearic Islands)

The second thematic workshop and policy lab was held on 30 June 30 2021, online. The main goal of the meeting was:

- To provide clarity and information on Renewable Energy Communities, the applicable legal framework and the routes for their processing, with a comparative approach at European and national level.
- Describe the current panorama of community energy in the Balearic Islands, giving a voice to the representatives of those initiatives that may represent a “first step” or pave the way towards the constitution of RECs.
- To organise a “policy lab” with different social agents at regional level to discuss the existing barriers to the development of Energy Communities in the region, and the relevance of promoting them from the public sector.

Figure 54– Breakdown of participants in the second Thematic Workshop and Policy Lab per stakeholder group

The meeting was attended by 51 stakeholders and markets actors, including with around 30% of female audience and 50% female speakers. The core group of participants included policy makers at regional and island level, who constituted the “target” group of the session; energy and innovation associations and agencies; associations and interest groups; electricity system operators; SMEs; community energy initiatives and cooperatives; financial institutions, as well as universities. Figure 54 shows the disaggregation of the participants per stakeholder group.

Similarly to the first thematic workshop, the event was structured in four thematic blocks, with a cascading approach: firstly, the workshop focused on clarifying key concepts and addressing the confusion around the definition of Renewable Energy Community (one of the main barriers identified at the beginning of the project), highlighting its constitutive elements and analysing them in contrast to other actors and legal figures.

Secondly, having established the basic approaches, the question of the legislative framework applicable to RECs was addressed, as well as the existing enabling policy framework, with a “bottom-up” approach: from the European framework, through the national framework, to the regional level.

Thirdly, through practical examples of both pilot experiences and more developed REC projects, some of the most commonly observed models in the COME RES model regions in Spain (in particular in the Valencian Community) were illustrated, such as RECs with local government participation through the transfer of public spaces; residential cooperative and agro-photovoltaic models. As an example of the first steps towards the creation of RECs in the Balearic Islands, the case of the incipient initiative developed within the industrial estate of Sant Lluís (Menorca) was taken as a model.

Finally, an interactive discussion session or “policy lab” was held with a moderator and 6 participants, structured around a series of questions aimed at analysing possible synergies between local policies and the development of RECs. Following, the main results are summarised under each question:

Question 1: What do you consider to be the main barriers to the development of Renewable Energy Communities in the Balearic Islands at present?

- Lack of information and lack of knowledge on the part of the different actors who should be promoting this type of initiative is considered the most recurrent barrier.
- Lack of previous experience in public-private partnerships and other new initiatives, which are poorly rooted in the legal tradition of the autonomous community.
- Stakeholders are stuck in a way of understanding energy as either grid consumption or individual installations, which constitutes a cultural barrier.
- Lack of interest from different actors, be they public or private entities small municipalities face legislative barriers related to the uses that can be made of municipal public spaces which, in the case of needing modifications, cause delays in the processing of this type of projects.
- Territorial tension in the Balearic Islands due to the scarcity of developable areas.
- Lack of human resources with the necessary training and technical skills in small municipalities Excessive bureaucracy that hampers processing, where the lack of harmonised/unified procedures in different regions and municipalities stands out, as well as the lack of clarity in the information transmitted by the administration.
- “Fear” of the apparent complexity of such projects.
- Definitive and concrete regulations are developing very slowly, leading to confusion about the role of different actors (e.g., marketers).
- There is a lack of pedagogical momentum and examples of RECs in the region that would help the partner to understand what the direct benefits of RECs could be and lead to the creation of new projects with replicability potential. To this end, local councils are a key lever.
- Strong lack of cooperative tradition and individualism.
- Difficult access to RECs for economically vulnerable people, who lack the resources/savings to make the necessary investment.

Question 2: Do you think that Energy Communities should receive a boost or support at regional, island and/or local level? What should this support consist of and why?

- Yes, the Balearic Energy Institute is actively involved in providing technical, administrative and legal advice on the projects submitted to them. A framework document has also been drawn up, which could serve as the basis for a model internal agreement in an energy community, and a web page will soon be made public. There are also plans to publish guidelines for citizen projects, as well as the possibility of investing as a stakeholder in REC projects, which is foreseen in the IBE statutes, with returns being reinvested in new projects. A call for pilot grants

for energy communities has also been launched. Finally, the possibility of ceding public spaces and roofs for renewable installations is foreseen.

- Yes, what is public belongs to everyone, therefore, if there is a popular petition in favour of the creation of RECs, the minimum is that public entities make available the spaces of all for these uses and be subsidiary to the energy facilitation. In the same way that street lighting is guaranteed, it could also be considered a public service to guarantee a minimum energy supply to vulnerable families and groups in need. This would contribute to building a sense of community and belonging to society.
- Yes, guaranteeing energy supply to vulnerable households is a great advantage. Municipalities could play a role by being beneficiaries of part of the production of a REC, and distributing it to the neediest sectors (based on socio-economic data that only these entities have). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953040. The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the COME RES project and does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Also, municipalities have an important role to play in informing citizens, enabling them to be self-convinced.
- Yes, the public administration should be a benchmark for this type of project. Especially in solar self-consumption, there are many public areas that can be used to supply energy to citizens in the surrounding area (currently within a radius of 500m, which is expected to be extended). From a practical point of view, if the public administration implements these projects, citizens will be able to check their viability, producing a "call effect". As good practices in other autonomous communities, the creation of energy advice offices for citizens stands out. The MES (Mechanism for Sustainable Energy) programme in Barcelona is a good example of this.
- Yes, municipal urban planning regulations must be adapted, assuming the declaration of a climate emergency, in order to be able to promote this type of project as a matter of urgency. Municipalities in Mallorca such as Sóller, for example, make self-consumption difficult due to this type of regulation.
- Yes, public administrations should inform about what RECs are, about existing aids, mainly through local councils and aimed at raising awareness among private actors at the micro level (SMEs, homeowners' and residents' associations). A good practice to take into account is the experience of the Balearic Housing Institute in advising on the constitution of housing cooperatives.

ACTIVITY 4: First Country Desk meeting

On 8 March 2022, the Spanish stakeholder desk held the first follow-up meeting of its core group of members. The COME RES project, and particularly its stakeholder roundtable in Spain, was in its second year of implementation and, thus, in a key period in the achievement of its objectives and results.

During 2021, numerous advances have been made on the different activity fronts. In this sense, the follow-up meeting of the stakeholder desk aimed to systematically present the intermediate results achieved in the framework of the project, as well as to gather feedback and validation on key deliverables.

The day was structured around four thematic clusters, focusing on the main packages of analytical work of the COME RES project. For each of the sessions, ECORYS gave a summary presentation of the conclusions of the main reports produced within the framework of the project. These presentations by the COME RES team were complemented in each session by “ad-hoc” presentations by key stakeholders. These speakers were chosen on the basis of their suitability to illustrate the reality of the issues addressed, as they are being developed in the territory, or to provide innovative solutions in these areas. The discussion (questions and answers) was channelled through the online platform chat. The session was recorded for later analysis.

Figure 55 – Breakdown of participants in the first Spanish country desk follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

55 people attended the second meeting of the COME RES stakeholder desk in Spain, including the ECORYS and ACER team. This second meeting was dominated by attendees from the public sector. Specifically, public decision-makers and local and/or regional public authorities reached 38% of the participation. This trend confirms a strong interest and dynamism on the part of key stakeholders of the COME RES project, especially those particularly involved in the design and implementation of national, regional and local public policies central to the development of an enabling framework for community energy in Spain. Equally decisive was the participation of representatives of community energy projects, with different degrees of development in implementation, from consolidated RECs to pilot projects. This fact guarantees that the contents discussed at the stakeholder table show a high degree of concreteness and adjustment to local realities, all to the benefit of the correct identification of barriers, as well as a greater appropriation of the COME RES results by the project participants. Regarding the geographical scope of the organisations involved, institutions with a regional scope predominated (70%), followed by those with a national scope (15%), and as per the regional distribution of the participants, a very balanced distribution among the four target and model regions of the COME RES project in Spain

(Canary Islands, Balearic Islands, Valencia, Catalonia) was observed. In terms of gender equality, the meeting was rather unbalanced with only 26% of participants involved being female.

ACTIVITY 5: Second Country Desk follow-up meeting & Policy Lab

On 10 and 11 November, COME RES was present at the CANAGUA, an international fair that focuses on the development and promotion of clean energies in the Canary Islands, Spain. The event took place in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain) and gathered stakeholders from the renewable energy sector, representatives from municipalities and local initiatives, as well as members from regional governments. The meeting with its 21 participants was quite balanced in terms of gender, as 52% of participants were female. On the first day, Maria Rosaria Di Nucci, COME RES Project Coordinator, gave a presentation on the project and its results so far. During the second day, a policy lab with a core group of the Spanish stakeholder desk was organised by ECORYS Spain and ACER.

Figure 56 - Breakdown of participants in the second Spanish country desk follow-up meeting per stakeholder group

Throughout the development of the event, key stakeholders and the COME RES team joined together to carry out the elaboration of an action plan particularly targeting renewable energy communities in the Canary Islands. The regional government of the Canary Islands was represented by the Head of Cabinet for the Ecologic Transition Office, José Luis Figueroa. Furthermore, the Energy Council of Gran Canaria, and the Renewable Energies Office for Tenerife, formed by technical experts in the field of renewable energies, as well as the Technological Institute of the Canary Islands (ITC) and the Canarias “Green Offices”, were present. In addition to public officials, there was an important representation from municipalities (Tacoronte, El Rosario) and local initiatives from all islands, such as La Palma Renovable.

During the first part of the policy lab, the COME RES project was introduced and explained to all participants. The core development of the lab focused on tailoring the action plan for the archipelago, which was developed thanks to the valuable contributions of all participants, who shared their views on the opportunities and challenges emerging from the exiting regulation of renewable energy communities in Spain. Overall, the lab was considered fruitful by all participants, which actively engaged with each

other to produce a complete set of demands and proposals for the improvement of the situation in the Canary Islands.

3.8.2. ADDITIONAL COUNTRY DESK ACTIVITIES

CONSULTATION WITH THE DESK STAKEHOLDERS: The online survey

47 stakeholders from the Spanish desk took part in the COME RES survey, launched in May 2022. In Spain, the survey focused specifically on the target regions of the Balearic and Canary Islands, and notable differences in responses were observed between the two. Regarding the institutional profile of those who took part in the survey in Spain, an important share represented energy community initiatives or cooperatives - more so in the Balearic -; local public authorities - notably in the Canary Islands -, as well as energy and innovation agencies. Although less frequently, informants from national or regional public authorities; associations; NGOs and research organisations also took part in the survey. As regards the main attitudes from respondents on the different topics observed:

- In the Spanish target regions, familiarity with the provisions for REC in the REDII of the stakeholders consulted was over 75%, which is a reflection of the composition of the sample regionally.
- Concerning the most relevant legal forms, Spanish respondents considered **cooperatives** as the most suitable for RECs in Spain.
- The most promising field of activity for RECs observed in Spain was **electricity generation**, and to a smaller extent, energy storage and heating. In this sense, the Balearic Islands heating, farming and energy storage and flexibility services are considered of less relevant than in the Canary Islands and Spain in general.
- Regarding the main barriers perceived:
 - The need for **reducing administrative burdens** was especially pronounced in Spain, where 83-87 % of the respondents found this highly important. In this regard, the existence of bureaucratic hurdles and the lengthy response times of local and regional administrations to the official procedures for the creation of energy communities and particularly self-consumption installations have been frequently mentioned as a barrier to REC development in Spain. As such, **the reduction of such burdens** was considered the main support measure to be taken by policy makers in Spain.
 - The **lack of awareness of RECs as a concept/model** was also highlighted as one of the key barriers in Spain, a more prominent perception in the Balearic Islands than in the rest of Spain.
 - Interestingly, the **lack of clear legislation** was seen as a less important barrier in the Balearic and Canary Islands than in Spain in general.

INPUT TO REGIONAL ENERGY ACTION PLANS

As discussed above (under Activity 5), the second country desk meeting and policy lab held in Las Palmas served as the occasion to develop an Action Plan for the development of renewable energy communities in the Canary Islands. However, other actions were carried out to feed its elaboration, including preliminary scoping discussions with relevant stakeholders in the region (prior to the policy lab organisation), as well as a feedback/validation round carried out by written procedure.

INPUT TO GOOD/BEST PRACTICE TRANSFER

The Spanish process focused on the transfer of the COMPTEM project from Comunidad Valenciana, Spain, which had been pre-selected as potentially suitable for its transferability to the Canary Islands. In this sense two transfer workshops were organised.

The wider group of stakeholders involved in the Spanish country desk were not directly involved in the transfer process. However, the learning case was built by the transfer team partially on the basis of the barriers and drivers identified in prior Spanish desk activities (mainly regional workshops and policy labs).

OTHER ADDITIONAL ACTIVITIES

In total, three focus groups were organised in late 2021 and early 2022 to contribute to gather qualitative data for the elaboration of Deliverable 2.3 in two Spanish target regions (Canary Islands and Balearic Islands), and at national level.

- **Focus Group I:** Civil Society. 06 October 2021, Online, 5 participants
- **Focus Group II:** Local authorities. 17 December 2021 Online, 5 participants
- **Focus Group III:** SMEs 31 January 2022, Online, 3 participants

Each of the focus group interviews lasted about 90 minutes. Relevant stakeholders for each group were selected from the core group of the Spanish stakeholder desk members. Among other topics, we enquired about the participants' role or involvement in the establishment of RECs, including which technologies they are interested in, their social motivations for engaging in RECs, how they work in general and how they try to promote RECs, who they cooperate with and see as important network, what they experience as key impediments for the establishment and running of RECs (see COME RES Deliverable 2.3). The interviews were conducted as online meetings (via MS Teams).

3.8.3. OUTCOMES AND LESSONS LEARNED

As main outcomes of the activities carried out by the Spanish desk, the active involvement of a wide range of actors across the stakeholder spectrum matrix continued to be ensured, with a strong focus on (local) policy makers and public authorities, associations, energy cooperatives, NGOs and networks, SMEs specialised in renewable energy, etc. From a geographic point of view, different levels of stakeholders have been mobilised (national, regional -Autonomous Communities-, insular and local).

Moreover, as a spin-off from the activities of the Spanish desk, two relevant processes leading to policy development and REC creation in the target regions of the Canary Islands have been initiated. On the

one hand, the Action Plan on Renewable Energy Communities in the Canary Islands received the input and endorsement from key players and market actors in the region. On the other hand, the transfer process facilitated by COME RES initiated a collaboration framework between the selected mentoring organisation (the COMPTTEM best practice promoters) and the Gran Canaria's Energy Council.

All in all, the meetings and workshops organised throughout the project created unique opportunities for interregional networking and collaboration, matchmaking and identification of common grounds for cooperation. The desk activities also served as an important tool for the dissemination and increased visibility of project activities and findings in Spain, with a multiplier effect.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND POSSIBILITIES TO MAINTAIN THE DESK INFRASTRUCTURE

One of the objectives of COME RES is to initiate, engage and feedback with major stakeholders and market actors. In all participating countries, these have been actively involved in regular solution-oriented stakeholder dialogues to co-create solutions to overcome existing barriers for the growth of community energy and setting up an enabling framework. In this way, they supported the processes of transposition and implementation of the EU legal framework for RECs through “policy labs” as a neutral forum for discussing the development of a legal basis, creation of enabling frameworks and consideration of RECs in support schemes. Throughout the project lifetime, the country desks ensured in all participating countries a wide engagement of market actors and stakeholders and created new or reinforced existing networks. Dialogues with major stakeholders in thematic workshops, policy labs and dedicated stakeholder consultations helped to address critical barriers and drivers for RECs in each target region, to identify and select good/best practices and to derive policy recommendations. The stakeholders involved in the desks accompanied all work phases and tasks, provided advice, and supported the dissemination of the results. At the beginning, the desks consisted of a core and committed market actors of each country resp. target region (e.g. municipalities, local/regional authorities, cooperatives, community energy groups, SMEs, associations, policy-makers, NGOs, municipal utility companies, housing companies, energy agencies, etc.). In the course of time, the desks also actively engaged a growing number of experts and stakeholders from the model regions. In this way, the involved stakeholders accompanied all operational work and tasks of the project. Although there are stakeholder groups that are present in each country, there are some stakeholder groups that are more influential in one country than in another or that are specific to a country (e.g. ethnic minorities). Moreover, the activities of the country desks vary from country to country according to the regional needs while being inspired by the same specific objectives. Although all country desks followed a general pattern and had a fixed number of events to organise, plenty of room was left open in order to adjust to the specific local/national needs and time priorities of the participating stakeholders. This meant that sometimes more events were organised as originally planned in the grant agreement and that it was not always possible to organise these events in parallel time slots in the various countries. For this reason - as it can be evinced from the description of the activities of the country desks - all stakeholder analysed the current barriers and evaluated the existing drivers, but with different timing and priorities. Thus, while the lengthy administrative regulations and permitting procedures were identified by all desks as pernicious hindrances for the development of RECs, some other barriers identified were very much specific to the respective countries and determined by particular legal, socio-economic, but also cultural factors.

The engagement of local stakeholders in the so-called target regions represented a valuable resource especially when identifying and discussing major hurdles and the possibilities to co-create solutions in order to overcome existing barriers. They acknowledged the benefits for growth of community energy in their regions by learning from the experience of other COME RES countries and by discussing the chance of implementing best-practices initiated elsewhere. This is also the reason why several partners

or core stakeholders participated in desk events of other countries and offered the opportunity to explain in an informal dialogue how to allocate resources, discuss support possibilities and promising business models. Stakeholders belonging to the various country desks also supported the dissemination of the project results and solutions within their respective interest groups. Moreover, relying on their strong networks, they invited other relevant stakeholders to join the COME RES events.

On the whole, the meetings and workshops organised throughout the project created unique opportunities for interregional and transnational networking and collaboration, matchmaking and identification of common grounds for cooperation. The desk activities also served as an important tool for the dissemination and increased visibility of project accomplishments and findings with a multiplier effect.

This transnational character is best epitomised by the Belgian/Dutch country desk that brought together stakeholders from Flanders (Belgium) and the Netherlands to cooperate in a cross-border desk. The joint transnational stakeholder desk facilitated networking between stakeholders that would otherwise not have connected. Thus, transnational cooperation between diverse COME RES target regions/countries enlarged the stakeholder infrastructure set up with the establishment of the individual country desks and also offered stakeholders from the involved countries a unique experience to get a better perception of how things might be radically different 'across the border', whilst at the same time showing how different countries have to react to the same European legislation.

In particular, the selection and transfer of good/best practice cases illustrated how important cooperation between citizen energy actors and municipalities and municipal utilities can be and how valuable networking and clustering among (international) citizen energy actors is. A very good example is the experience of the Latvian country desk that involved the transfer team of the Italian best practice case and the creation of a WhatsApp-group to enable a continuing dialogue for Latvian stakeholders.

Stakeholders in the majority of countries could emphasise that some of the barriers identified in the first half of the project could be mitigated or reduced, such as the lack of clarity of key definitions, as “proximity” and that COME RES provided valuable input for this. Specifically, in Portugal, it was achieved a strong alignment between the needs identified by the project and the ongoing and foreseen actions from the National Energy Agency (a key stakeholder in the Portuguese desk). There were also some advancements regarding the creation of guidance for potential promoters of RECs, and dedicated support at the local level.

In some countries like Latvia, the process of transposition of the REDII into national law was accompanied from the very beginning by the country desk. The Ministry of Economics was a regular participant in the country desks with the responsible ministerial officials actively engaging in a mutual exchange of information and regularly informed the desk participants about the transposition of the EU’s Clean Energy for all Europeans legislative package into Latvian law and invited them to comment draft legislation and provide opinions. The inspiring role of COME RES has been officially recognised in the annotation of the amended Latvian Energy Law and Electricity Market Law. These contain explicit and

detailed references to the REC potential assessment and the assessment of barrier and drivers carried out within COME RES.

Spain is also an excellent case where a spin-off from the activities of the Spanish Desk occurred: two relevant processes leading to policy development and REC creation in the target regions of the Canary Islands have been initiated. On the one hand, the Action Plan on Renewable Energy Communities in the Canary Islands received the input and endorsement from key players and market actors in the region. Moreover, the transfer process facilitated by COME RES initiated a collaboration framework between the selected mentoring organisation (the COMPTEM best practice promoters) and the Gran Canaria's Energy Council.

During the first and second thematic workshop of the German country desk, the participants assessed the possibilities to transfer good practices from other COME RES countries to the target region. The innovative concept of the 'Multi-functional Energy Gardens', appeared to be particularly promising and highly transferable. In particular, the Thuringian Ministry of Environment, Energy and Nature Conservation, and local energy cooperatives found the project appealing, whilst environmental NGOs, the climate protection foundation Jena-Thüringen and the foundation Landschaftspark Nohra joined forces to initiate the first phase of the project. This interest is bolstered by the Dutch mentoring organisations and the Thuringian main actors signing a memorandum of understanding (MoU) which manifests their commitment to continue the dialogue and cooperation also after the lifetime of COME RES. Moreover, a dedicated brochure with contributions from Dutch and Thuringian experts belonging to the core stakeholder group of the German country desk is going to inform about the transfer concept of Energy Gardens and related multi-use approaches and will be presented during the final COME RES conference in Brussels on 31 January 2023.

Other MoUs are going to be signed between the Canary Island and COMPTEM (see the Spanish section) and between Magliano Alpi (Italy) and Latvian major stakeholders (see the Latvian and Italian sessions).

Thus, at the end of the project, there are positive signals that the infrastructure set up with the establishment of the country desks will find ways for further cooperation and that the core stakeholders will size all the opportunities to ensure the continuation of these networks.

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